

ABS

2026 Vol. 69 | Št. 1

Acta Biologica Slovenica

Acta Biologica Slovenica, 2026, 69 (1)

Založila/Published by

Založba Univerze v Ljubljani / University in Ljubljana Press
Društvo biologov Slovenije / Slovenian biological society

Za založbo/For the publisher

Gregor Majdič, rektor Univerze v Ljubljani / the Rector of the University of Ljubljana
Anita Jemec Kokalj, predsednica Društva biologov Slovenije / Chairman of Slovenian Biological Society

Izdala/Issued by

Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Oddelek za biologijo /
University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Biology

Za izdajatelja/For the Issuer

Marina Pintar, dekanja Biotehniške fakultete UL / Dean of Biotechnical Faculty

Naslov uredništva/Editorial Office Address

Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Acta Biologica Slovenica,
Večna pot 111, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenija

Glavni urednik/Editor-in-chief

Matevž Likar, Slovenija / Slovenia, matevz.likar@bf.uni-lj.si

Odgovorna urednica/Managing editor

Anita Jemec Kokalj, Slovenija / Slovenia, anita.jemec@bf.uni-lj.si

Uredniški odbor/Editorial Board

Gregor Belušič (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Tina Eleršek (SLO), Nacionalni inštitut za biologijo
Božo Frajman (A), Univerza v Innsbrucku
Király Gergely (HU), University of Sopron, Faculty of Forestry
Gordana Glavan (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Aleksandra Golob, Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Cene Gostinčar, Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Katarina Hančević (HR), Institute for Adriatic Crops and Karst Reclamation
Margit Heinlaan (EST), National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics
Vida Jojić (SRB), Univerzitet u Beogradu, Institut za biološka istraživanja „Siniša Stanković“
Tina Klenovšek (SLO), Univerza v Mariboru, Fakulteta za naravoslovje in matematiko
Dana Kühnel (GER), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ
Alenka Malej (SLO), Nacionalni inštitut za biologijo
Nataša Mori (SLO), Nacionalni inštitut za biologijo
Polona Mrak (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Maria Mueller (A), University of Salzburg
Siniša Ozimec (HR), Univerza Josipa Juraja Strossmayerja
Hubert Potočnik (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Tomislav Radić (HR), Institute for Adriatic Crops and Karst Reclamation
Tomaž Skrbinšek, Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Simona Strgulc Krajšek (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Miloš Vittori (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta
Anja Klančnik (SLO), Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta

Oblikovanje/Design

Ajda Fortuna

Naslovnica/Cover page

Plod tatarske ajde, avtor/author: Paula Pongrac

To delo je ponujeno pod licenco Creative Commons Priznanje avtorstva-Deljenje pod enakimi pogoji 4.0 Mednarodna licenca (izjema so fotografije). /
This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (except photographs).

Izdajanje revije sofinancira Javna agencija za znanstvenoraziskovalno in inovacijsko dejavnost Republike Slovenije (ARIS)
The journal is co-financed by Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)

Publication is free of charge.

ISSN 1854-3073 (spletna verzija/online version) UDK 57(497.4)

DOI: 10.14720/abs.69.1

<http://journals.uni-lj.si/abs/>

Acta Biologica Slovenica je indeksirana v – is indexed in: CAB Abstracts, Web of Science Clarivate

Table of Contents

Original Research Paper

- 4 **Evidence of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing brown leaf spot disease of rice (*Oryza sativa*) in Ghana / Gliva *Bipolaris oryzae* dokazano povzročča bolezen rjavih listnih madežev riža (*Oryza sativa*) v Gani**
Titus Akansin Bukari, Joseph Adomako, Stephen Larbi-Koranteng, Amina Dawood, Yaw Danso, Frederick Kankam, Joshua Obeng
- 12 **Potassium silicate enhances growth in strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') by improving anatomical structure / Kalijev silikat spodbuja rast jagod (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') z izboljšanjem anatomskih struktur**
Sedigheh Kelij, Saba Yasaghi
- 23 **The last lynx of the Apennine mountains ridge / Zadnji ris iz grebena Apeninskih gora**
Andrea Amici, Silvia Cappiello, Luigi Esposito, Nadia Piscopo
- 37 **Screening of pesticide residues in a small agricultural watershed in Ogbomoso, Southwest Nigeria / Preverjanje ostankov pesticidov v majhnem kmetijskem porečju v Ogbomosu v jugozahodni Nigeriji**
Odunayo J. Gbadegesin, Ebenezer O. Ajiboye, Kasali A. Adelasoye, Toyin P. Abegunrin, Oladele A. Olaniran
- 52 **Myths in biology: students' opinion towards vaccination, climate change, genetically modified organisms and evolution / Miti v biologiji: mnenja dijakov do cepljenja, podnebnih sprememb, gensko spremenjenih organizmov in evolucije**
Katja Bukovnik, Gregor Torkar
- 63 **Mycoprotein production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation using soybean as a medium / Proizvodnja mikoproteinov iz *Lentinus squarrosulus* s fermentacijo v trdnem stanju z uporabo soje kot medija**
Anita Rahmawati, Rina Sri Kasiamdari, Shin-Yee Fung, Boon-Hong Kong, Sari Darmasiwi
- 74 **Identification of Stress-Responsive Transcription Factors Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase through Co-expression Network Analysis under Drought, Heat, and Salinity Conditions in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) / Identifikacija transkripcijskih faktorjev, ki se odzivajo na stres in sodelujejo s cisteinsko desulfurazo preko analize mreže soizražanja v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti pri krompirju (*Solanum tuberosum*)**
Firat Kurt, Ertugrul Filiz
- 85 **Mass of amalgam restorations and its significance for assessing the environmental impact of dental amalgam / Masa amalgamskih restavracij in njen pomen za ovrednotenje okoljskega vpliva dentalnega amalgama**
Iztok Štampfelj, Neža Gozdnikar, Nika Junež, Anja Konjar, Lorena Lina Perpar, Eva Polšak
- 96 ***In vitro* conservation and multiplication of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. - A horticulturally important floriferous orchid species / *In vitro* ohranjanje in razmnoževanje *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. – vrtnarsko pomembna cvetoča vrsta orhideje**
Mahika Jain, Saranjeet Kaur
- 106 **Effect of nitrogen and oxygen low-pressure cold plasma and their mixtures on the germination and early seedling growth of Tartary buckwheat / Učinek nizko-tlačne kisikove in dušikove plazme ter njunih mešanic na kaljivost in rast kalic tatarske ajde**
Jure Mravlje

Original Research

Evidence of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing brown leaf spot disease of rice (*Oryzae sativa*) in Ghana

Titus Akansin Bukari¹, Joseph Adomako^{1,2*}, Stephen Larbi-Koranteng¹, Amina Dawood², Yaw Danso², Frederick Kankam³, Joshua Obeng^{4,5}

Abstract

A high incidence of brown leaf spot disease was observed on rice foliage during field visits, with no management strategy employed by farmers. To confirm the aetiology for the future development of a management strategy, isolation and identification of the associated fungal pathogen was carried out morphologically and confirmed molecularly through amplification and sequencing of the ITS region. Pathogenicity test on the rice variety 'AGRA' was performed to confirm Koch's postulates. The pathogen was morphologically identified to belong to the genus *Bipolaris*. A molecular analysis based on the sequencing dataset placed the isolates in the same clade as *Bipolaris oryzae*. The current results should guide plant protectionists in developing sustainable management strategies to curtail the spread of the disease in the country.

Keywords

Bipolaris spp., *B. oryzae*, brown leaf spot, rice diseases, phylogenetics, Atwima Nwabiagya District, Ghana

1 Department of Crop and Soil Sciences Education, Akenten Appiah-Menka University of Skills Training and Entrepreneurial Development, Asante-Mampong, Ghana

2 CSIR-Crops Research Institute, Kumasi, Ghana

3 Department of Agricultural Biotechnology, Faculty of Agriculture, Food and Consumer Sciences, University for Development Studies, Tamale, Ghana

4 CSIR-Oil Palm Research Institute, Kade, Ghana

5 College of Agriculture, Tennessee State University, 3500 John A. Merritt Blvd, Nashville, TN, USA

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: j.adomako@cropsresearch.org/joadomako@gmail.com

Citation: Akansin Bukari, T., Adomako, J., Larbi-Koranteng, S., Dawood, A., Danso, Y., Kankam, F., Obeng, J. (2025). Evidence of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing brown leaf spot disease of rice (*Oryzae sativa*) in Ghana. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 14.10.2024 / **Accepted:** 7.10.2025 /

Published: 16.10.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.19954>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Gliva *Bipolaris oryzae* dokazano povzroča bolezen rjavih listnih madežev riža (*Oryza sativa*) v Gani

Izvleček

Na poljih je bila na listih riža opažena visoka pojavnost rjave listne pegavosti in odsotnost strategije za obvladovanje te bolezni s strani kmetov. Da bi potrdili etiologijo za prihodnji razvoj strategije obvladovanja, je bila izvedena izolacija in identifikacija povezanega glivnega patogena. Identifikacijo smo izvedli morfološko in jo potrdili z molekularnimi metodami s pomočjo PCR in sekvenciranja ITS regije. Da bi potrdili Kochove postulate, je bil izveden test patogenosti na riževi sorti 'AGRA'. Patogen je bil morfološko identificiran kot pripadajoč rodu *Bipolaris*. Molekularna analiza DNA sekvenc je izolate uvrstila v isti klad kot *Bipolaris oryzae*. Sedanji rezultati bi morali voditi varstvenike rastlin pri razvoju trajnostnih strategij upravljanja za omejitev širjenja bolezni v državi.

Ključne besede

Bipolaris spp., *B. oryzae*, rjava listna pegavost, bolezen riža, filogenetika, okrožje Atwima Nwabiagya, Gana

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is an important staple cereal providing 20% of the global dietary energy requirement (Nganga et al., 2022). Africa's insatiable demand for rice at a rate of 6% positioned it as the fast-expanding market for the produce and ranked it as the second-largest global rice importer (Fontan & Mughal, 2020). This trend is projected to continue due to the rapid growth in population, urbanisation, and growing consumer preferences. The contribution of Ghana to Africa's rice importation is substantial as according to the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (2022), the average per capita rice consumption of Ghana increased from 35 kg/annum in 2016 to about 45 kg/annum in 2020 confirming Asante et al. (2020) assertion that rice is the second most consumed cereal crop in Ghana after maize. Ghana is, however, estimated to produce just about 40% of its local demand, although it has suitable land resources to boost production, compelling the importation of the commodity into the country (Ouédraogo et al., 2021).

A major limitation of rice production is the susceptibility of commercial rice varieties to several fungal pathogens. Fungal infections in rice reduce yield quantity and quality and increase the cost of production through their management. Some studies have reported on the prevalence of fungal diseases in rice farms across Ghana. Apart from the blast disease widely reported in Ghana (Nutsugah et al., 2003; Maaldu & Abebrese, 2020),

Honger et al. (2022) reported the incidence of brown leaf spot disease (BLSD) by *Curvularia lunata* in certain parts of the country. Globally, *Bipolaris* spp. and specifically *B. oryzae* are widely documented as the major cause of the BLSD in rice (CABI, 2020; Barro et al., 2021; Kabore et al., 2025). Disease symptoms similar to the descriptions of Nutsugah et al. (2003), Maaldu & Abebrese (2020) and Honger et al. (2022) were observed in some lowland rice farms in the Atwima Nwabiagya district of the Ashanti region. The incidence of brown leaf spot disease in the area is concerning, as numerous reports (IRRI, 2012; Singh et al., 2017; Mau et al., 2020; Abrol, 2022) confirm that the disease outbreak can lead to a 45% decline in the yield of susceptible rice varieties. Apart from varietal susceptibility, some reports (Hossain et al., 2014; Adanve et al., 2023) have shown that the incidence and severity of brown leaf spot disease increase in areas with high relative humidity and precipitation, a characteristic feature of lowland rice production. The occurrence of the disease could be even more worrying because the majority of producers in the study area are smallholder farmers with less access to inputs and knowledge in rice disease management.

Although *B. oryzae* is widely documented to cause BLSD, the identity and pathogenicity of *B. oryzae* on rice have not been confirmed in Ghana, more specifically in Atwima Nwabiagya District. Our study objective was to identify and confirm the pathogenicity of *B. oryzae* on rice in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection

Leaves of the rice variety "AGRA" expressing brown leaf spot disease symptoms (Fig. 1) were collected in February 2023 from 4 rice farms in the Atwima Nwabiagya North district, Ghana. On the field, five symptomatic rice leaves were sampled in a zig-zag pattern, with each plant being 5 m apart and placed in paper bags. Sampled leaves were brought to the laboratory and kept at 4 °C until fungal isolation.

Isolation and identification of fungal cultures

Before isolation, the collected samples were thoroughly washed under running water for 15 mins to eliminate all debris, sterilised with 1% sodium hypochlorite solution, serially rinsed with sterile distilled water, and blotted dry. The sterilised-dried leaves were cut into pieces to contain both healthy and diseased portions and seeded on Oxoid potato dextrose agar (PDA) media fortified with ampicillin (250 mg/l, Meiji Seika Pharma Co., Ltd.) to prevent bacterial growth contamination. Fungal colonies successfully isolated were sub-cultured on fresh PDA plates, and pure cultures were produced by the single spore method. Emerging *Bipolaris* spp. were identified based on colony

and conidia morphological features as reported in previous studies (Marin-Felix et al. 2017; Sun et al. 2020). Conidia of each isolate were observed under an Amscope microscope mounted with an Amscope digital camera, and images were taken under 400x magnification.

Molecular identification

The genomic DNA of the isolated fungi was extracted from the fungal mycelia of 5-day-old actively growing cultures on PDA using the modified CTAB method (Soalla et al., 2023). The obtained genomic DNA was transported to the laboratory of Functional Biosciences DNA Sequencing Services, Madison, United States of America (USA), for DNA amplification by PCR, and sequencing of the amplicons following standard laboratory procedures. The ITS region was amplified using ITS1F (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS4R (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3') (Carbone & Kohn, 1999). The sequence data obtained after sequence analysis were aligned using the Bioedit software version 7.2, and the identity was confirmed by comparing it with the database in the GeneBank of the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)-nBLAST analysis. Phylogenetic relationships were inferred using the neighbour-joining method with 1000 bootstrap replicates based on the combined ITS dataset in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Rice plants showing symptoms of rice brown leaf spot disease in the field.

Slika 1. Riževa rastlina, ki kaže simptome rjave listne pegavosti riža na polju.

Pathogenicity test of selected fungal species

Koch's postulates were evaluated to confirm the pathogenicity of the isolated fungi on a susceptible rice variety, 'AGRA'. The detached leaves and whole plant assays, as described by Thomas et al. (2016) and Honger et al. (2022), were used. Detached leaves were sterilised in 75 % ethanol, rinsed with sterile distilled water, allowed to dry under a laminar flow chamber, and placed in separate 90 mm Petri dishes lined with moistened Whatmann filter paper. The leaves were inoculated with the *Bipolaris* spp. spore suspensions (106 spores/ml) as described by Park et al. (2017). For the whole plant assay, the leaves of two-week-old rice seedlings were inoculated with spore suspension (106 spores/ml). Rice tissues inoculated with autoclaved water served as control treatments in both evaluations. The inoculated seedlings were covered with transparent plastic bags to provide ambient humidity and temperature. The plastic bags were removed after 24 hours, and the plants were placed on benches under a screen house ($26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 73% humidity). The inoculated seedlings and detached leaflets were observed daily for 7 and 14 days post-inoculation under detached leaves and whole plant assays, respectively, for the appearance of brown leaf spot symptoms. Where symptoms appeared, the fungus was re-isolated from the artificially inoculated tissues to complete Koch's postulates. Triplicates of the inoculated detached leaves and rice seedlings were arranged in a completely randomised design.

Results

Isolation and morphological identification of fungal isolates

Fungal isolates resembling *Bipolaris* were successfully obtained from the diseased leaf samples. Isolates KK-A and AD-A were selected as representatives for further study. Morphologically, they exhibited irregular colony shapes which appeared greyish dark with conspicuous zonation pigmentation on the front view (Fig. 2a), while dark colourisation was observed from the back (Fig. 2b). Colony diameter was 8.4 cm at 6 days after incubation. The conidia appeared dark brown, curved in shape, broader in the middle and round at the end with multiple 5-8 septations (Fig. 2C). Conidia size ranged from 52.0-74.1 μm in length.

Molecular confirmation of selected fungal isolates

The sequence data generated for this study have been deposited in the NCBI GeneBank and assigned GeneBank accession numbers PX111114.1 and PX111115.1 for isolates KK-A and AD-A, respectively. BLASTn search confirmed that the two isolates had complete identity with *Bipolaris oryzae*. Phylogenetic analysis based on the ITS gene confirmed that both KKA and AD-A clustered in a well-supported clade with reference sequences of *B. oryzae* (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Morphology and cultural features of the fungal pathogen isolated. (A) Colony front view on PDA. (B) Colony back view on PDA. (C) *Bipolaris* spp. conidia.

Slika 2. Morfologija in kulturne značilnosti izoliranega glivičnega patogena. (A) Pogled na kolonijo od spredaj na PDA. (B) Pogled na kolonijo od zadaj na PDA. (C) Konidiji *Bipolaris* spp.

Table 1. Species, strains and accession numbers of specimens used in the phylogenetic tree construction.

Tabela 1. Vrste, sevi in številke dostopa vzorcev, uporabljenih pri sestavi filogenetskega drevesa.

Specie name	Strain number	Accession number (ITS)	Reference
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	SS	PV982076.1	Samsthitha (2025)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	Bo2	PP448182.1	Vignesh and Lokesh (2024)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	ZM347	OR690743.1	Song et al. (2023)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	BO2020_CRI_2.7	OQ875830.1	Chuchiw et al. (2023)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	BIPOL7	OQ861268.1	Maurya (2023)
<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	BHS 4-17	ON724162.1	Tan (2022)
<i>Bipolaris coffeana</i>	BRIP 14845	KJ415525.1	Tan et al. (2014)
<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	BHS 4-17	ON724162.1	Tan (2022)
<i>Bipolaris adikaramae</i>	HSF022	MT509431.1	Ferdinandez et al. (2022)
<i>Bipolaris gossypina</i>	UEM4658	OQ743523.1	Rodrigues et al. ()
<i>Bipolaris maydis</i>	p005	PQ500574.1	Piyush et al. (2024)
<i>Bipolaris papendorffii</i>	AH-01	KC592365.1	Li et al. (2013)
<i>Bipolaris zeicola</i>	Bz_JC10	MW929303.1	Cipollone et al. (2021)
<i>Bipolaris victoriae</i>	GA2016, TE302	KX371072.1, OW984559.1	Tian and Smith (2016), Becker (2022)
<i>Bipolaris maydis</i>	Kbm1, CBS 136.29	PP988397.1, NR_138224.1	Kundu et al. (2024); Amaradasa et al. (2014)
<i>Bipolaris saccharicola</i>	CBS 155.26	KY905674.1, NR_151854.1	Marin-Felix et al. (2017)
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	A559	KX463014.1	Li (2016)
<i>B. oryzae</i>	KK-A	PX111114.1	This study
<i>B. oryzae</i>	AD-A	PX111115.1	This study

Figure 3. Phylogram generated for *Bipolaris* from neighbour-joining analysis based on ITS alignments.Slika 3. Filogram, ustvarjen za *Bipolaris* iz analize sosedskega združevanja na podlagi poravnave ITS.

Pathogenicity of selected fungal isolates

One-week post-inoculation, both detached rice leaves and whole plants showed characteristic lesion symptoms (Fig. 4A and Fig. 4B). The lesion symptoms observed initially appeared as small spots on the leaves which later appeared elliptical, narrowly linear, and coalesced to form long lesions causing leaf blight with yellowing as it progressed (Figures 4A and 4B), while the control plants and detached leaves had no visible spots after fourteen days of inoculation. Fungal pathogen isolated from symptomatic leaves of the artificially inoculated tissues was morphologically consistent with the inoculated pathogen, confirming Koch's Postulate.

Discussions

Results of the current study have established *Bipolaris oryzae* as the causal pathogen of rice brown leaf spot disease in the study area. Species of *Bipolaris* have been identified to cause multiple diseases, such as leaf spots, leaf blight, and root rot on different hosts belonging to the Poaceae family. Multiple studies (Nayak et al. 2019; Chhabra et al. 2023; Wickramasinghe et al. 2023; Priyadarshani et al. 2023) have linked *Bipolaris* to rice brown leaf spot disease.

In Ghana, major diseases of rice like the blast and brown spot caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Curvularia* spp. respectively (Nutsugah et al., 2006; Honger et al., 2022), have been reported. Nutsugah et al. (2003) associated *B. oryzae* with BLSD in Northern Ghana based solely on visual observations, without employing additional tools such as culture, molecular and pathological techniques to diagnose and confirm the pathogen. Ackaah et al. (2023) reported on the association of *B. oryzae* on rice seeds, but their study was based on morphological features. The weakness associated with the use of morphological tools may have limited the results obtained since no molecular tools were employed in the species identification. Before then, studies conducted by Oppong et al. (2022) and Honger et al. (2022), which both involved the use of molecular tools, reported *Curvularia* species instead, and it remained doubtful as to whether or not *Bipolaris* species were actually the cause of brown leaf spot disease of rice in Ghana and specifically in the study area. The study presents a significant finding with important implications for rice production. Earlier studies (Naik et al., 2016; Barua et al., 2019; Sobanbabu et al., 2018), which involved pathogenicity of *B. oryzae*, reported that it can cause seedling wilt, death, blight, and dark lesions on the culm of rice and rice spikelet, thereby reducing yield and grain quality. It has also been found on other crops like *Typha latifolia* (Berbrer et al., 2022) and *Oryza rufipogon* (Liu et al., 2021), and its negative impact on inducing leaf

Figure 4. *B. oryzae* inoculated rice leaves showing symptoms of brown leaf spots on (A) detached rice leaves and (B) whole rice plant.

Slika 4. Listi riža, okuženi z *B. oryzae*, kažejo simptome rjavih listnih madežev na (A) odtrganih listih riža in (B) celotni riževi rastlini.

spot disease on yield and grain quality has been reported. The findings of the current study have confirmed the existence of *B. oryzae* in Ghana and its pathogenic ability on the AGRA rice variety grown by farmers in the study area. Further studies are, however, required to ascertain the prevalence in the country and prompt the development of disease management strategies.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, J.A, S.L-K; methodology, T.A.B, A.D.; Software, Y.D; Validation, F.K; Formal analysis, J.O, S.L-K.; Investigation, J.A, J.O.; Resources, T.A.B; Data curation, J.A, T.A.B.; Writing—original draft preparation, S.L-K, J.A., T.A.B.; Writing—review and editing, Y.D, J.A, J.O; Visualisation,

F.K.; Supervision, J.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Disclosure Statement

The authors disclose no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

All sequence data generated during this study have been deposited in the NCBI GenBank and are freely accessible to the public. The fungal isolates obtained are preserved in the culture collection of the Department of Crop and Soil Sciences Education, AAMUSTED, Ghana. These isolates, together with other data are available from the lead author upon reasonable request.

References

- Abrol, S., Singh, S., Singh, V., Basu, U. M. E. R., Singh, R. A. N. B. I. R., Singh, A., ... & Khushboo, S. S. (2022). Effect of agro-met conditions on the progression of brown leaf spot disease in basmati-370 rice. *Asian Jr. of Microbiol. Biotech. Env. Sc.*, 24(2), 335-340.
- Ackaah, F. M., Nyaku, S. T. & Darkwa, E. (2023). Seed-borne fungi associated with diverse rice varieties cultivated in the Western North Region of Ghana. *International Journal of Microbiology*, 2023(1), 8690464.
- Adanve, J. F., Koné, B., Sikirou, R., Dossou-Yovo, E., Onaga, G. & Sorho, F. (2023). Effect of soil and climatic conditions on brown spot occurrence in rice lowland across four agro-climatic zones of Côte d'Ivoire. *Annual Research & Review in Biology* 38(4), 46-60, <https://doi.org/10.9734/arrrb/2023/v38i430581>.
- Asante, M. D., Gamenyah, D. D., Boadu, S. E., Ribeiro, P. F., Abebrese, S. O., & Oppong, A. (2020). An analytical approach on physicochemical and molecular characterization of imported rice in Ghana: Implications for developing product targets for breeding new varieties. *Research and Development in Agricultural Sciences*, 3, 47-58.
- Aslam, H. M. U., Naveed, K., Hussain, S. I., Shakeel, Q., Ashraf, W., Anwaar, H. A., ... & Tariq, I. (2021). First report of brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Bipolaris zeicola* in Pakistan. *Plant Disease*, 105(1), 212. <https://10.1094/PDIS-04-20-0838-PDN>.
- Barro, M., Kassankogno, A. I., Wonni, I., Sérémé, D., Somda, I., Kaboré, H. K., ... & Tollenaere, C. (2021). Spatiotemporal survey of multiple rice diseases in irrigated areas compared to rainfed lowlands in the Western Burkina Faso. *Plant Disease*, 105(12), 3889-3899.
- Barua, M., Quintana Viedma, L. A. & Ortiz Alfonso, A. A. (2019). Chemical control of rice brown spot (*Bipolaris oryzae*) in Paraguay. *The Journal of the Society for Tropical Plant Research*, 6(1), 148-151.
- Berberer, F., Lamrani, N., Imrani, N., Msairi, S., Mouden, N., Benkirane, R., Douira, A. (2022). First Report of *Bipolaris oryzae* on *Typha latifolia* and the pathogenicity of its isolates on different rice varieties. *Acta Mycologica*, 57, 573. <https://doi.org/10.5586/am.573>
- CABI. 2020. Brown Leaf Spot of Rice, *Cochliobolus miyabeanus*. <https://www.plantwise.org/KnowledgeBank/datasheet/14691>. (Accessed January 18, 2024)
- Carbone, I., & Kohn, L. M. (1999). A method for designing primer sets for speciation studies in filamentous ascomycetes. *Mycologia*, 91(3), 553-556.
- Chhabra, R., Sharma, R., Hunjan, M. S., Sharma, V. K., Sharma, P., & Chauhan, S. K. (2023). Microstructural and metabolic variations induced by *Bipolaris oryzae* inciting brown spot disease of rice. *Cereal Research Communications*, 51(4), 953-968.
- Felsenstein, J. (1985). Confidence limits on phylogenies: an approach using the bootstrap. *Evolution*, 39(4), 783-791.
- Ferdinandez, H. S., Manamgoda, D. S., Udayanga, D., Deshappriya, N., Munasinghe, M. S. & Castlebury, L. A. (2022). Molecular phylogeny and morphology reveal two new graminicolous species, *Bipolaris adikaramae* sp. nov and *B. petchii* sp. nov., with new records of fungi from cultivated rice and weedy grass hosts. *Mycological Progress*, 21(6), 59.
- Fontan, S.C. & Mughal, M. (2020). Covid-19 outbreak and the need for rice self-sufficiency in West Africa. *World Development*, 135, 105071.
- Honger, J.O., Lomotey, T., Kugblenu-Darrah, Y., Bedu, I. & Amankwa, N. Y. (2022). Characterization and in-vitro control of *Curvularia lunata*, the causal agent of brown leaf spot disease of rice in Ghana. *Agricultural and Food Science Journal of Ghana*, 15(2), 1526-1542.
- Hossain, M. M., Sultana, F., Asadur Rahman, A. H. M. (2014). Comparative screening of hybrid, modern varieties and local rice cultivars for brown leaf spot disease susceptibility and yield performance. *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection*, 47(7), 795-802. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105071>.
- IRRI, 2009. Brown spot (Rice Facts Sheet). International Rice Research Institute, Los Banos, Philippines.

- Kabore, K. H., Kassankogno, A. I. & Tharreau, D. (2025). Brown Spot of Rice: Worldwide Disease Impact, Phenotypic and Genetic Diversity of the Causal Pathogen *Bipolaris oryzae*, and Management of the Disease. *Plant Pathology*, 74(4), 908-922. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.14075>
- Liu, Y. L., Tang, J. R., Li, Y. & Zhou, H. K. (2021). First report of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing leaf spot on cultivated wild rice (*Oryza rufipogon*) in China. *Plant Disease*, 105(6), 1857.
- Maaldu, P. & Abebrese, S. O. (2020). Isolation and Morphological Characterization of Rice Blast Pathogen in Northern Ghana. *Agricultural and Food Science Journal of Ghana*, 13, 1259-1267.
- Marin-Felix, Y., Groenewald, J. Z., Cai, L. M. C. G., Chen, Q., Marincowitz, S., Barnes, I., & Crous, P. W. (2017). Genera of phytopathogenic fungi: GOPHY 1. *Studies in mycology*, 86, 99-216.
- Mau, Y. S., Ndiwa, A. S. S., & Oematan, S. (2020). Brown spot disease severity, yield and yield loss relationships in pigmented upland rice cultivars from East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas*, 21(4), 1625-1634.
- Ministry of Food & Agriculture. (2020). Rice Production: A Priority to Ghana (mofa.gov.gh).
- Naik, M. R., Akila, R., Thiruvudainambi, S. (2016). Management approaches for brown spot of rice caused by *Bipolaris oryzae*. *J. Farm. Sci.* 29(3), 370-376
- Nayak, M. S. & Hiremath, S. V. (2019). Cultural, morphological, and molecular characterisation of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing brown leaf spot of rice in Northern Karnataka. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 8(2), 1235-1239.
- Nganga, E. M., Kyallo, M., Orwa, P., Rotich, F., Gichuhi, E., Kimani, J. M., ... & Talbot, N. J. (2022). Foliar diseases and the associated fungi in rice cultivated in Kenya. *Plants*, 11(9), 1264.
- Nutsugah, S. K., Tsigbey, F. K., Dzomeku, I. K., & Bimpong, I. K. (2003). Survey of rice diseases and insect pests in Northern Ghana. *Journal of Science and Technology (Ghana)*, 23(1), 7-15.
- Oppong, C., Amoatey, C., Honger, J. O. (2022). Characterisation and control of *Curvularia lunata* infecting farmer-saved rice seeds in Ghana. *African Crop Science Journal*, 30(4), 485-496.
- Ouédraogo, S.A., Bockel, L., Abedi, A., Arouna, A. and Gopal, P. (2021). Rice value chain in Ghana – Prospective analysis and strategies for sustainable and pro-poor growth. Accra, FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb1659en>
- Park, S. H., Choi, I. Y., Lee, W. H., Lee, K. J., Galea, V., & Shin, H. D. (2017). Identification and characterization of *Cercospora malayensis* causing leaf spot on kenaf. *Mycobiology*, 45(2), 114-118.
- Priyadarshani, T.D.C., Karunarathna, D.D.N., Menike, G.D.N., Weerasinghe, P.A., Madushani, M.A. & Madhusan, K.W.A. (2023). Efficiency of locally isolated *Trichoderma virens* for controlling rice brown leaf spot disease caused by *Bipolaris oryzae*. *International Congresses of Turkish Science and Technology Publishing*, 9-13.
- Saitou, N. & Nei, M. (1987). The neighbour-joining method: a new method for reconstructing phylogenetic trees. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 4(4), 406-425.
- Singh, L., Lal, A. A., Kumar, K., Simon, S. & Kumar, M. (2017). Management of brown spot disease of rice by safer fungicides and some bioagents. *Plant Archives*, 17(2), 1020-1022.
- Soalla, W. R., Zida, P. E., Neya, B. J., & Koita, K. (2023). Morphological and molecular identification of fungi associated with sesame diseased plants of the three agroclimatic zones of Burkina Faso. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, 14(3), 290-307.
- Sobanbabu, G., Sabarinathan, K. G., Parthiban, V. K., & Ramamoorthy, V. (2018). Isolation, screening and identification of virulent isolates of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing rice brown spot and *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot disease. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 7(9), 930-939.
- Sun, X., Qi, X., Wang, W., Liu, X., Zhao, H., Wu, C., ... & Gong, G. (2020). Etiology and symptoms of maize leaf spot caused by *Bipolaris* spp. in Sichuan, China. *Pathogens*, 9(3), 229.
- Thomas, N. C., Schwessinger, B., Liu, F., Chen, H., Wei, T., Nguyen, Y. P., ... & Ronald, P. C. (2016). XA21-specific induction of stress-related genes following *Xanthomonas* infection of detached rice leaves. *PeerJ*, 4, e2446.
- White, T. J., Bruns, T., Lee, S. J. W. T., & Taylor, J. (1990). Amplification and direct sequencing of fungal ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetics. *PCR protocols: a guide to methods and applications*, 18(1), 315-322.
- Wickramasinghe, W. M. D. M., Priyadarshani, T. D. C., Egodawatta, W. C. P., Beneragama, D. I. D. S., Menike, G. D. N., Weerasinghe, P. A., & Devasinghe, D. A. U. D. (2023). Dynamics of rice brown leaf spot disease (*Bipolaris oryzae*) incidences due to seasonal weather differences in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. *Tropical Agricultural Research*, 34(4), 363-378.
- Nutsugah, S. K., Dogbe, W., Twumasi, J. K., Dartey, K., Chipili, J., Sreenivasaprasad, S., & Séré, Y. (2005). Prevalence of rice blast and varietal screening in Ghana. *Journal of Science and Technology (Ghana)*, 25(2), 18-34. <https://10.4314/just.v25i2.32942>.

Original Research

Potassium silicate enhances growth in strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) by improving anatomical structure

Sedigheh Kelij^{1,*}, Saba Yasaghi¹

Abstract

Plant structure is closely linked to its physiological function, where any structural modification can significantly affect plant growth and development. Potassium silicate, a silicon source known to improve plant structural and physiological traits, was applied to strawberry plants (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) under greenhouse conditions, at different concentrations (0, 5, 10, and 20 mmol·L⁻¹) to assess its effects on growth and anatomy. The 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment notably optimized key growth parameters, particularly leaf number, alongside anatomical improvements such as increased cuticle and palisade parenchyma thickness, vascular tissue development, including larger midrib and root stele areas, expanded metaxylem diameters and a shift in root stele type from triarch to pentarch. A strong positive correlation was observed between root stele area and leaf number. Remarkably, druse crystals increased by 164%, highlighting their vital role in plant defence. These findings underscore the benefits of moderate potassium silicate concentrations (10 mmol·L⁻¹) in improving root and leaf anatomy, directly enhancing plant growth. It offers practical insights into leveraging silicon-based treatments to optimise crop performance, especially in high-demand crops like strawberries.

Keywords

Leaf, silicon, structural properties, vascular development

¹ Department of Plant Sciences, University of Mazandaran, Babolsar, Iran

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: s.kelij@umz.ac.ir

Citation: Kelij, S., Yasaghi, S. (2025). Potassium silicate enhances growth in strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. ‘Camarosa’) by improving anatomical structure. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 02.06.2025 / **Accepted:** 17.10.2025 / **Published:** 27.10.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.22944>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Kalijev silikat spodbuja rast jagod (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') z izboljšanjem anatomskih struktur

Izvleček

Struktura rastline je tesno povezana z njeno fiziološko funkcijo, pri čemer lahko vsaka strukturna sprememba znatno vpliva na rast in razvoj rastline. Kalijev silikat, vir silicija, za katerega je znano, da izboljšuje strukturne in fiziološke lastnosti rastlin, je bil v različnih koncentracijah (0, 5, 10 in 20 mmol·L⁻¹) uporabljen na jagodnih rastlinah (*Fragaria* × *ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') v rastlinjaku, da bi ocenili njegove učinke na rast in anatomijo. Obdelava s 10 mmol·L⁻¹ je znatno optimizirala ključne parametre rasti, zlasti število listov, poleg anatomskih izboljšav, kot so povečana debelina kutikule in palisadnega parenhima, razvoj žilnega tkiva, vključno z večjimi površinami srednje žile in koreninskega stela, povečanimi premeri metaksilema in prehodom iz triarhskega v pentarhski tip koreninske stele. Opazili so močno pozitivno korelacijo med površino koreninske stele in številom listov. Zanimivo je, da so se kristali druse povečali za 164 %, kar poudarja njihovo pomembno vlogo pri zaščiti rastlin. Ti izsledki poudarjajo prednosti zmernih koncentracij kalijevega silikata (10 mmol·L⁻¹) pri izboljšanju anatomije korenin in listov, kar neposredno izboljša rast rastlin. Ponujajo praktične vpogled v izkoriščanje obdelav na osnovi silicija za optimizacijo donosa pridelkov, zlasti pri pridelkih z visokim povpraševanjem, kot so jagode.

Ključne besede

List, silicij, strukturne lastnosti, razvoj prevajalnih elementov

Introduction

Silicon is a key component of soils, and plants absorb it in considerable amounts. It has been a subject of scientific interest for decades, prompting extensive research on the application of silicate materials as fertilisers (Uhlen, 1974). As an integral component of cell walls, silicon not only reinforces structural stability but also actively supports key metabolic and physiological processes. Its significance becomes particularly evident under biotic and abiotic stresses, where it enhances plant resilience (Liang et al., 2006).

The cultivated strawberry (*Fragaria* × *ananassa*), because of its pleasant taste, vitamin richness, and antioxidant properties, has high commercial and economic importance and has attracted significant attention (Giamperi et al., 2012). Providing nutrients over the growth period is essential for increasing the yield and quality of strawberries. Silicon can be classified among these nutrients. The use of Silica-based compounds in agriculture has proven to enhance plant vitality and performance. In different settings, including fields and greenhouses, the influence of silicon-based fertilisers on crop development has been entirely documented (Liang et al., 2015). Several

studies have demonstrated the positive effects of silica on strawberry plants. For instance, Wang and Galleta (1998) reported that the potassium silicate application improved plant growth, increased chlorophyll content, enhanced the composition of unsaturated fatty acids and membrane lipids, and ultimately supported strawberry metabolism. Similarly, Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015) found that treatments with potassium silicate and nano-silica significantly increased key growth parameters, such as leaf number and leaf formation rate, while also improving reproductive traits, including flowering and fruit firmness. Further research has emphasised the effect of potassium silicate in alleviating environmental stress. Yaghubi et al. (2016) found that potassium silicate not only improved growth and physiological traits in strawberries but also reduced cellular damage under salt stress. Moreover, physiological parameters, including stomatal conductance, chlorophyll content and photosynthesis rate, were enhanced in strawberry plants under water stress by the application of potassium silicate (Avestan et al., 2021).

Plant anatomical characteristics are intricately linked to the functional capabilities of plants, and any structural modifications have the potential to significantly influence physi-

ological processes (Santos et al., 2015). Although numerous studies have examined the effects of silicon on plant development, physiology, flowering, yield, and fruit quality, its role in shaping the anatomical structure of strawberries remains poorly understood. This study seeks to expand fundamental knowledge by investigating how potassium silicate affects both growth and anatomical traits of commercial strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa') under greenhouse conditions. By linking anatomical modifications with growth responses, our findings contribute to basic plant science while also offering insights that may inform future agricultural practices for strawberry cultivation. The subsequent key questions addressed in this study include: (1) How do different concentrations of potassium silicate impact the growth parameters of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'? (2) What exact structural changes are observed in response to potassium silicate application? (3) Can the detected anatomical adaptations be correlated with enhanced growth performance under potassium silicate treatment?

Materials and Methods

Plant cultivation and treatments

Strawberry plants with 3–4 leaves, sourced from Ashian Sabz Emad company (Karaj, Iran), were transplanted into 2.5 kg pots. The soil texture was sandy loam with 51% sand, 38% silt, and 11% clay, with an electrical conductivity (EC) of 0.47 dS/m and a pH value of 7.71. The plants were housed in a greenhouse environment featuring a photoperiod of 14/10 h light/dark, 60 – 70% relative humidity, and temperature ranging from 16 – 18 °C to 21 – 22 °C from November 2023 to February 2024. Two weeks after transplantation, the plants underwent weekly potassium silicate treatment (K_2SiO_3 42%, Sigma) at concentrations of 0, 5, 10, and 20 mmol/L, applied via soil drenching. Throughout the experiment, plants were watered as needed. The potassium silicate applications persisted for a duration of two months

Growth parameters and anatomy

The number of leaves per plant was recorded, and other growth parameters were determined using graph paper. For each treatment, five individual plants (biological replicates) were used. From each plant, five separate samples of root, petiole, and leaf were collected and analysed individually

(technical replicates), totalling 25 replicates per organ per treatment. For anatomical analysis, samples of leaves, petioles, and roots were immediately fixed in a glycerin-alcohol solution. Transverse sections were taken from the central part of the middle leaflet of matured leaves and the median section of the petiole and root, along their longitudinal axis. Using a steel blade. An Olympus CX43 microscope with a digital camera was employed for microscopic analysis, and ImageJ software (version 1.54g) was used for measuring anatomical features. Anatomical terminology follows the standards outlined in Esau's "Plant Anatomy" (Evert, 2006).

Statistical analysis

The SPSS software (version 21) was employed to analyse the obtained data. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to explore the differences among the studied factors across the treatments using Duncan's multiple range test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard error (SE) of five independent replicates. Additionally, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to explore the relationships between anatomical characteristics and growth parameters using SPSS. To highlight the maximum potential effect of the treatments on each trait, we calculated the growth rate of each growth and anatomical trait as the difference between the highest treatment value and the control value, and visualised the results using a sunburst chart. Microsoft Excel (version 2021) was used for the sunburst chart and plotting all the figures.

Results

The leaf number per plant enhanced significantly in 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate, while there were no meaningful differences among other treatments. The strawberry plants exposed to 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate exhibited notable improvement in petiole length. Likewise, leaf width and length increased significantly at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate. However, increasing the potassium silicate level to 20 mmol·L⁻¹ didn't show significant enhancement in petiole length and leaf width and length. Potassium silicate application had no significant effects on shoot and root length of strawberry plants, and no considerable difference with the control was observed in any of the treatments (Table 1).

The leaf anatomical structure of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa' (Figure 1A) showed a bifacial leaf. Leaf thickness peaked under 10 mmol·L⁻¹ potassium silicate ($p < 0.05$), and was at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The thickest upper cuticle was also observed in the 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, though no significant differences appeared at other concentrations. Lower cuticle thickness remained unchanged across treatments. The 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment significantly increased upper epidermis thickness, while lower epidermis thickness showed no significant variation. Palisade and spongy parenchyma

were also thickest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no notable differences among other treatments (Table 2).

In the midrib (Figure 1-B), annular collenchyma and a nearly circular stele were observed. Midrib thickness increased in 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatments but decreased at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The thickest collenchyma was at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no difference between 20 mmol·L⁻¹ and the control. Stele area improved at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and declined at 20 mmol·L⁻¹. The largest metaxylem diameter appeared at 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹, and the smallest at 20 mmol·L⁻¹ (Table 2).

Table 1. Effects of potassium silicate on growth parameters of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Tabela 1. Učinki kalijevega silikata na parametre rasti *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Treatments	Leaf number	Petiole length (Cm)	Leaf width (Cm)	Leaf length (Cm)	Shoot length (Cm)	Root length (Cm)
Control	4.50 ± 0.57 b	6.02 ± 0.47 b	2.82 ± 0.51 b	3.17 ± 0.34 b	16.62 ± 0.94 a	14.3 ± 2.4 a
5 mmol·L ⁻¹	5.25 ± 0.5 b	7.66 ± 0.86 a	3.56 ± 0.33 a	3.83 ± 0.3 a	15.62 ± 0.94 a	13.37 ± 1.4 a
10 mmol·L ⁻¹	6.50 ± 0.57 a	7.48 ± 0.61 a	3.63 ± 0.28 a	3.73 ± 0.34 a	16.12 ± 4.1 a	13.5 ± 3 a
20 mmol·L ⁻¹	5.25 ± 0.5 b	5.97 ± 0.61 b	2.93 ± 0.3 b	3.07 ± 0.26 b	15.12 ± 2.8 a	13 ± 3.7 a

Note: Data represent mean ± SE of five independent replicates. Means followed by the same letters within each column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

Figure 1. Leaf cross-section of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa', and displaying different measurement parameters. A, Leaf blade (10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); UCT: upper cuticle thickness, UET: upper epidermis thickness, PPT: Palisade parenchyma thickness, SPT: Spongy parenchyma thickness, LET: lower epidermis thickness, LCT: lower cuticle thickness, LT: leaf thickness. B, Leaf midrib (5 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); MT: midrib thickness, CoT: collenchyma thickness, StA: stele area, MD: metaxylem diameter.

Slika 1. Prez list *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa' in prikaz različnih merilnih parametrov. A, listna ploščica (na primer obdelava z 10 mmol·L⁻¹); UCT: debelina zgornje kutikule, UET: debelina zgornje epiderme, PPT: debelina palisadnega parenhima, SPT: debelina spongioznega parenhima, LET: debelina spodnje epiderme, LCT: debelina spodnje kutikule, LT: debelina lista. B, srednja žila lista (na primer obdelava s 5 mmol·L⁻¹); MT: debelina srednje žile, CoT: debelina kolenhimata, StA: površina stele, MD: premer metaksilema.

In petiole anatomy (Figure 2-A), collenchyma beneath the epidermis, two small steles, a large central stele, and druse crystals were observed. Petiole and collenchyma thickness increased only at 10 mmol·L⁻¹, with no significant difference from 5 mmol·L⁻¹. Central stele dimensions and smaller stele areas showed no significant change across treatments. Druse crystals increased in all potassium silicate treatments compared to the control, but differences among 5, 10, and 20 mmol·L⁻¹ were not significant (Table 2).

In root anatomy (Figure 2-B), exodermis, cortex, endodermis, pericycle, and vascular bundles were identified. Potassium silicate significantly increased root cross-sectional area and cortex thickness, both of which were highest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and lowest in the control. Exodermis thickness showed no significant difference among treatments (Table 2). Root stele area followed the same trend as root cross-section area, highest at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ and lowest in the control. Metaxylem thickness increased significantly in 5 and 10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatments compared to 20 mmol·L⁻¹ and control. Xylem rows varied from 3 to 5, corresponding to triarch to pentarch stele types. Xylem rows peaked at

10 mmol·L⁻¹ (4.75 ± 5 , indicating pentarch), while the control showed the lowest number (3.25 ± 5 , indicating triarch) (Table 2, Figure 3).

Pearson correlation analysis indicated that a notable positive association exists between root and leaf growth and anatomy with vascular tissue development (Figure 4). As follows, there was a significant correlation between the root stele area and leaf number ($r = 0.82^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), the midrib collenchyma thickness and root metaxylem diameter ($r = 0.73^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), leaf length and midrib stele area ($r = 0.8^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), and also, palisade parenchyma thickness and midrib metaxylem diameter ($r = 0.79^{**}$, $p < 0.01$).

The sunburst chart (Figure 5) shows that potassium silicate significantly affected strawberry growth and anatomy. Leaf number had the highest growth increase (44%), followed by petiole traits and leaf width. Root anatomy, especially root cross-sectional area, rose by 158%. In leaves, midrib metaxylem diameter increased by 91%, indicating improved vascular development. Petiole druse crystal number showed the strongest anatomical response with a 164% increase.

Figure 2. Petiole and root cross sections of *Fragaria x ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa', and displaying different measurement parameters. A, Petiole (5 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); PD: petiole diameter, CoT: collenchyma thickness, DC: druse crystal, MaD: major diameter of the largest stele, MiD: minor diameter of the largest stele, StA: stele area. B, Root (10 mmol·L⁻¹ treatment, for example); CT: cortex thickness, EXT: exoderm thickness, Xy: xylem, StA: stele area, MD: metaxylem diameter.

Slika 2. Prerez listnega peclja in korenine *Fragaria x ananassa* cv. „Camarosa“ z različnimi merilnimi parametri. A, listni peclj (na primer obdelava s 5 mmol·L⁻¹); PD: premer listnega peclja, CoT: debelina kolenhimata, DC: druse kristal, MaD: glavni premer največjega stela, MiD: stranski premer največjega stela, StA: površina stela. B, Korenina (na primer obdelava z 10 mmol·L⁻¹); CT: debelina skorje, EXT: debelina ekso-derm, Xy: ksilem, StA: površina stela, MD: premer metaksilema.

Figure 3. Root stele type of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'. A: Triarch stele, B: Tetrarch stele, C: Pantarch stele. En: endoderm, Pr: pericycle, Xy: xylem, Ph: phloem.

Slika 3. Root stele type of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'. A: Triarch stele, B: Tetrarch stele, C: Pantarch stele. En: endoderm, Pr: pericycle, Xy: xylem, Ph: phloem.

Table 2. Effects of potassium silicate on the anatomical characteristics of *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'.

Tabela 2. Učinki kalijevega silikata na anatomske značilnosti *Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'

Anatomical characteristics	Control	5 mmol·L ⁻¹	10 mmol·L ⁻¹	20 mmol·L ⁻¹
Leaf thickness(µm)	178 ± 9.2 c	213 ± 8.4 b	264 ± 15.2 a	166 ± 8.6 c
upper cuticle thickness(µm)	7.29 ± 0.87 b	6.4 ± 0.45 b	10.15 ± 1.5 a	7.88 ± 0.36 b
lower cuticle thickness(µm)	5 ± 1.4 a	5.05 ± 2 a	4.85 ± 1.6 a	4.74 ± 1.5 a
upper epidermis thickness(µm)	21.7 ± 2.7 b	22 ± 1.7 b	27.1 ± 1.5 a	21.9 ± 1.1 b
Lower epidermis thickness(µm)	14.2 ± 3.5 a	14.7 ± 1.5 a	15.2 ± 4 a	15.6 ± 2.3 a
Palisade parenchyma thickness(µm)	54.3 ± 7.8 b	64.2 ± 6.1 b	79.2 ± 5.2 a	55 ± 7.4 b
Spongy parenchyma thickness(µm)	78.7 ± 5.6 b	89.8 ± 7 b	106.2 ± 16.9 a	84.5 ± 13 b
Midrib thickness(µm)	366 ± 13.7 b	443 ± 37.6 a	430 ± 22 a	307 ± 39 c
Midrib collenchyma thickness(µm)	49.45 ± 3.9 c	69.75 ± 6.1 b	80.98 ± 6.3 a	44.96 ± 8.7 c
Midrib stele area(µm ²)	12009 ± 1370 b	18996 ± 5603 a	17640 ± 934 a	9717 ± 2027 b
Midrib metaxylem diameter(µm)	6.48 ± 0.72 b	11.1 ± 1 a	12.4 ± 1.8 a	7.88 ± 1.4 b
Petiole thickness(µm)	1802 ± 50.4 b	1832 ± 105 b	2104 ± 196 a	1744 ± 36.9 b
Petiole collenchyma thickness(µm)	35.7 ± 9.7 b	41 ± 8.7 ab	51.7 ± 3.4 a	32 ± 7.9 b
Major diameter of central vessel(µm)	743 ± 86 ab	650 ± 29 b	758 ± 55 a	690 ± 61 ab
Minor diameter of central vessel(µm)	427 ± 71 b	434 ± 16 ab	510 ± 47 a	442 ± 42 ab
Small stele area(µm ²)	63102 ± 20331 a	68704 ± 5494 a	54408 ± 9045 a	56090 ± 4523 a
Number of druse crystals	5.2 ± 2.9 b	12 ± 3.16 a	12.5 ± 2.08 a	13.75 ± 2.75 a
Root cross section area(µm ²)	651k ± 79k c	1514k ± 156k ab	1683k ± 116k a	1335k ± 126k b
Root cortex thickness(µm)	306 ± 48 c	482 ± 18 b	614 ± 31 a	504 ± 47 b
Root exoderm thickness(µm)	33.7 ± 14 a	35.7 ± 13 a	45.6 ± 12 a	44.8 ± 16 a
Root stele area (µm ²)	42331 ± 10588 c	61113 ± 4333 b	79591 ± 5769 a	71349 ± 10692 ab
Root metaxylem diameter(µm)	12.6 ± 1.6 b	18.9 ± 1.29 a	17.2 ± 0.86 a	14 ± 2.2 b
Number of xylem rows	3.25 ± 0.5 c	3.75 ± 0.5 b c	4.75 ± 0.5 a	4.25 ± 0.5 ab

Note: Data represent mean ± SE of five independent replicates. Means followed by the same letters within each column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation between growth parameters and anatomical traits; LT: leaf thickness, UET: upper Epidermis thickness, LET: lower epidermis thickness, PaT: palisade thickness, SpT: spongy thickness, MT: midrib thickness, CoT: collenchyma thickness, MSA: midrib stele area, PT: petiole thickness, PCoT: petiole collenchyma thickness, MaD: metaxylem diameter, SSA: small stele area, DN: druse crystal number, RA: root area, RCT: root cortex thickness, RET: root exoderm thickness, RSA: root stele area, RMD: root metaxylem diameter, RSXN: root stele xylem number, LN: leaf number, PL: petiole length, Lw: leaf width, LL: leaf length, RL: root length, ShL: shoot length.

Slika 4. Pearsonova korelacija med parametri rasti in anatomske značilnosti; LT: debelina lista, UET: debelina zgornje epiderme, LET: debelina spodnje epiderme, PaT: debelina palisade, SpT: debelina spongije, MT: debelina srednje žile, CoT: debelina kolenhim, MSA: površina srednje žile, PT: debelina peclja, PCoT: debelina kolenhimusa peclja, MaD: premer metaksilema, SSA: površina majhne stele, DN: število drusnih kristalov, RA: površina korenine, RCT: debelina skorje korenine, RET: debelina eksoderma korenine, RSA: površina stele korenine, RMD: premer metaksilema korenine, RSXN: število ksilema stele korenine, LN: število listov, PL: dolžina peclja, Lw: širina lista, LL: dolžina lista, RL: dolžina korenine, ShL: dolžina poganjka.

Figure 5. The sunburst chart illustrates which anatomical characteristics and growth parameters were most affected by the potassium silicate treatment.

Slika 5. Tortni diagram prikazuje, katere anatomske značilnosti in parametri rasti so bili najbolj prizadeti zaradi obdelave s kalijevim silikatom.

Discussion

The application of potassium silicate (K_2SiO_3) significantly enhanced strawberry leaf growth by improving leaf traits, which form the main part of the vegetative body. The finding that the $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ potassium silicate treatment produced more leaves than the $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ treatment suggests that there is an optimal concentration for stimulating strawberry leaf development. Excessive application may disturb ionic balance or create osmotic stress, which can limit leaf expansion and overall growth. Similar results were reported by Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015), who found that $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ K_2SiO_3 enhanced strawberry growth while higher doses ($15\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) reduced leaf number. Likewise, Mavrič Cermelj et al. (2022) observed diminishing returns at higher silicon concentrations in barley, attributed to nutrient antagonisms. These findings indicate that moderate doses of potassium silicate are more effective for leaf formation than supra-optimal concentrations. Our study found a significant increase in petiole length at 5 and $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ K_2SiO_3 , contrasting with findings by Wang and Galleta (1998) and Dehghani Poodeh et al. (2015), who reported a decrease under Si treatments. Tabatabaei (2016) showed a 37% increase in strawberry leaf area with silica under salinity stress, supporting our results on enhanced leaf length and width. Although leaf growth improved at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, shoot and root lengths showed no significant change, consistent with Munns and Tester (2008), who found no effect on root length under non-saline conditions. This effect can be attributed to the fact that potassium silicate influenced the architecture and structural characteristics of the roots rather than their elongation. As demonstrated by the anatomical results in the present study, root cross-sectional area, thickness of cortex, the number of vascular bundles, stele area, and the metaxylem elements diameter all increased under the treatment. These findings align with those of Rachmawati et al. (2021), who reported similar anatomical increments in rice roots following potassium silicate application.

The results emphasise the concentration-dependent impact of potassium silicate on leaf anatomy, with $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ showing the greatest improvements in traits like overall leaf thickness, upper cuticle, upper epidermis, and mesophyll layers. Supporting this, Asmar et al. (2013) found that silicon uptake improves chlorophyll levels, photosynthesis, and leaf thickness in strawberry. In contrast, $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ led to declines in most anatomical traits, suggesting possible toxicity, consistent with findings by Azab

et al. (2022). No notable changes were observed in the lower cuticle and epidermis. Genetic and developmental programs differ between adaxial and abaxial epidermis, leading to inherent differences in their anatomical characteristics and responsiveness (Nakata & Okada, 2013). More generally, as Borowski and Michałek (2009) noted, factors such as species, application method, and light intensity can influence anatomical responses to fertilisation.

Potassium silicate application led to increased midrib thickness, along with greater collenchyma development, stele area, and metaxylem diameter. Similarly, Bijanzadeh et al. (2022) observed that sodium silicate reduced midrib area loss in drought-stressed maize and enhanced xylem element diameters under various conditions. These changes suggest improved vascular development, as noted by Aguraijuja et al. (2015), who linked larger stele areas to better water and nutrient transport. Zhang et al. (2023) also associated larger xylem vessels with enhanced hydraulic conductivity. In contrast, the reduced metaxylem diameter at $20\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ may indicate impaired water transport (Qaderi et al., 2019). The significant increase in midrib collenchyma thickness highlights its role in providing cell wall reinforcement and, consequently, mechanical strength to the leaf (Leroux 2012).

Potassium silicate, particularly at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, significantly increased petiole and collenchyma thickness by enhancing the number of collenchyma layers, thus improving leaf structural support. Bokor et al. (2019) found that while silicon did not alter petiole structure in *Phoenix dactylifera*, it reinforced sclerenchyma tissues and promoted lignification, highlighting silicon's role in strengthening supportive tissues. Additionally, all potassium silicate treatments increased druse crystal formation, likely due to potassium's role in releasing calcium, which then binds with oxalic acid to form calcium oxalate crystals. Calcium oxalate crystal formation is a recognised mechanism for regulating calcium levels (Kelij et al, 2025). However, no significant changes were observed in the dimensions or area of the petiole stele, suggesting potassium silicate's effects are tissue-specific.

The variation in xylem row numbers, shifting from triarch to pentarch types, reflects vascular flexibility that may enhance water and nutrient uptake. The highest number of xylem rows at $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ potassium silicate, along with increased stele area and metaxylem thickness at 5 and $10\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, indicates improved vascular efficiency. Vaculík et al. (2012) also reported that silicon mitigated cadmi-

um's negative effects on vascular development in maize. Potassium silicate at 10 mmol·L⁻¹ significantly increased root cross-sectional area and cortex thickness, suggesting enhanced root growth due to better nutrient uptake. Similarly, silicon improved root length and thickness in soybean (Chung et al., 2020) and promoted root development in *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* under stress (Zhang et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the exodermis thickness remained unchanged, indicating its consistent protective role across treatments.

Pearson correlation analysis revealed that increased leaf thickness under potassium silicate treatment is mainly due to greater collenchyma and palisade parenchyma thickness. Similarly, root diameter increased primarily through cortex thickening, followed by stele expansion. The strong correlations between root and leaf anatomical traits indicate that enhanced root structure contributes significantly to improved leaf growth. Potassium silicate also enhanced vascular tissue development, improving water and nutrient transport and enabling more efficient water regulation, which is especially important for strawberry plants with high water demand and limited root systems (Elmakarem & Mostafa, 2025).

Enhanced midrib vascular development and increased metaxylem diameter further supported leaf expansion and growth. This aligns with Ma and Yamaji (2006), who reported that silicon boosts cell elongation by improving cell wall extensibility, thereby strengthening the vascular system and its overall function.

Specifically, leaf and root tissues respond to environmental changes (Ky et al., 2024). In this study, the sunburst chart analysis shows that potassium silicate primarily prioritises the increase in energy-producing units, such as leaves, over other growth parameters. It also demonstrates that the effect of this treatment is more pronounced on vascular elements rather than supporting tissues like collenchyma. In fact, silicon enhances vascular elements, contributing to both greater structural strength and improved water and mineral transport. Additionally, the significant increase in druse crystals highlights its role in establishing an important defensive strategy.

Conclusions

This study highlights the concentration-dependent positive effects of potassium silicate (K₂SiO₃) on strawberry growth and anatomy under non-stress conditions. The optimal 10 mmol·L⁻¹ concentration improved leaf and root traits, increased leaf number and thickness, and enhanced vascular function. Silicon was shown to strengthen mechanical tissues like collenchyma, promote vascular development, and support defensive structures such as druse crystals, boosting plant resilience and productivity. The findings support the use of silica-based fertilisers in strawberry cultivation, with further research needed on silicon's interaction with environmental factors for sustainable agriculture.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, S.K; investigation, S.K and S.Y; Data curation, S.K and S.Y; writing and editing, S.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

We thank Mr. Majid Harati and Mr. Abdolreza Yadollahpour for their insightful comments and guidance during the project.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17454640>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Aguraijuja, K., Klóšeiko, J., Ots, K., & Lukjanova, A. (2015). Effect of wood ash on leaf and shoot anatomy, photosynthesis and carbohydrate concentrations in birch on a cutaway peatland. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 187(7), 444.
- Asmar, S. A., Castro, E., Pasqual, M., Pereira, F., & Dória, J. (2013). Changes in leaf anatomy and photosynthesis of micropropagated banana plantlets under different silicon sources. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 161, 328–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2013.07.021>
- Avestan, S., Ghasemnezhad, M., Esfahani, M., & Barker, A. (2021). Effects of nanosilicon dioxide on leaf anatomy, chlorophyll fluorescence, and mineral element composition of strawberry under salinity stress. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 44(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2021.1936036>
- Azab, E. S., Alshallash, K. S., Alqahtani, M. M., Safhi, F. A., Alshamrani, S. M., Ali, M. A. M., & El-Taher, A. M. (2022). Physiological, anatomical, and agronomic responses of *Cucurbita pepo* to exogenously sprayed potassium silicate at different concentrations under varying water regimes. *Agronomy*, 12(9), 2155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12092155>
- Bijanazadeh, E., Barati, V., & Egan, T. P. (2022). Foliar application of sodium silicate mitigates drought-stressed leaf structure in corn (*Zea mays* L.). *South African Journal of Botany*, 147, 8–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2021.12.032>
- Bokor, B., Soukup, M., Vaculík, M., Vd'ačný, P., Weidinger, M., Lichtscheidl, I., & Lux, A. (2019). Silicon uptake and localization in date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) – A unique association with sclerenchyma. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 988. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00988>
- Borowski, E., & Michałek, S. (2009). The effect of placement and light conditions during foliar application of Insole U fertilizer on gas exchange, yield, and the quality of spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.). *Folia Horticulturae*, 21, 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fhort-2013-0126>
- Chung, Y. S., Lee, U., Heo, S., Silva, R. R., Na, C.-I., & Kim, Y. (2020). Image-based machine learning characterizes root nodule in soybean exposed to silicon. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 520161. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.520161>
- Dehghani Poodeh, S., Ghobadi, C., Baninasab, B., Gheysari, M., & Bidabadi, S. S. (2015). Effects of potassium silicate and nanosilica on quantitative and qualitative characteristics of a commercial strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* cv. 'Camarosa'). *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 39, 502–507. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2015.1086789>
- Dehghani Poodeh, S., Ghobadi, C., Baninasab, B., Gheysari, M., & Shiranibidabadi, S. (2018). Effect of silicon on growth and development of strawberry under water deficit conditions. *Horticultural Plant Journal*, 4, 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hpj.2018.09.004>
- Elmakarem, A. A. A., & Mostafa, N. A. (2025). The effect of potassium silicate on the productivity and storability of spinach plants (*Spinacia oleracea* L.). *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 24, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44447-025-00038-3>
- Evert, R. F. (2006). *Esau's plant anatomy: Meristems, cells, and tissues of the plant body: Their structure, function, and development* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0470047380>
- Giampieri, F., Tulipani, S., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Quiles, J. L., Mezzetti, B., & Battino, M. (2012). The strawberry: Composition, nutritional quality, and impact on human health. *Nutrition*, 28, 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2011.08.009>
- Hancock, J. F., Lavín, A., & Retamales, J. B. (1999). Our southern strawberry heritage: *Fragaria chiloensis* of Chile. *HortScience*, 34(5), 814–816. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI.34.5.814>
- Kelij, S., Hosseinzadeh, Z., & Rezapour, A. (2025). Evaluating anatomical and biochemical responses to cement dust pollution in *Quercus castaneifolia* C.A. Mey. and *Zelkova carpinifolia* (Pall.). *iForest*, 18, 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.3832/ifor4574-018>
- Ky, A. R. F., Konaté, M. L., & Kouamé, N. F. (2024). Impact of water deficit on the anatomical structure of more productive and less productive cashew trees (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) in Côte d'Ivoire. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 68(1), 52–68.
- Leroux, O. (2012). Collenchyma: A versatile mechanical tissue with dynamic cell walls. *Annals of Botany*, 110, 1083–1098. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs186>
- Liang, Y., Nikolic, M., Bélanger, R., Gong, H., & Song, A. (2015). Effect of silicon on crop growth, yield, and quality. In *Silicon in agriculture: From theory to practice* (pp. 209–223).
- Liang, Y., Zhang, W., Chen, Q., Liu, Y., & Ding, R. (2006). Effect of exogenous silicon (Si) on H⁺-ATPase activity, phospholipids, and fluidity of plasma membrane in leaves of salt-stressed barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 57, 212–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2005.05.012>
- Ma, J. F., & Yamaji, N. (2006). Silicon uptake and accumulation in higher plants. *Trends in Plant Science*, 11, 392–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2006.06.007>
- Mavrič Čermelj, A., Fideršek, E., Golob, A., Kacjan Maršič, N., Vogel Mikuš, K., & Germ, M. (2022). Different concentrations of potassium silicate in nutrient solution affect selected growth characteristics and mineral composition of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Plants*, 11(11), 1405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11111405>
- Munns, R., & Tester, M. (2008). Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59, 651–681. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.59.032607.092911>
- Nakata, M., & Okada, K. (2013). The leaf adaxial–abaxial boundary and lamina growth. *Plants*, 2(2), 174–202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants2020174>
- Qaderi, M. M., Martel, A. B., & Dixon, S. L. (2019). Environmental factors influence plant vascular system and water regulation. *Plants*, 8(3), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants8030065>
- Rachmawati, D., Ramadhani, A. N., & Fatikhasari, Z. (2021). The effect of silicate fertilizer on the root development of rice and its tolerance to salinity stress. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 724, 012004.
- Santos, K. R., Pereira, M. P., Ferreira, A. C. G., Rodrigues, L., Castro, E., Corrêa, F., & Pereira, F. (2015). *Typha domingensis* Pers. growth responses to leaf anatomy and photosynthesis as influenced by phosphorus. *Aquatic Botany*, 122, 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquabot.2015.01.007>

- Tabatabaei, S. J. (2016). Interactive effects of Si and NaCl on growth, yield, photosynthesis, and ion content in strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* var. Camarosa). *Journal of Plant Nutrition* 39(11), 1524-1535. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2016.1161771>
- Uhlen, G. (1974). The effect of calcium silicate in barley pot experiments. *Agricultural and Food Science*, 46, 296–306. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.71887>
- Vaculík, M., Landberg, T., Greger, M., Luxová, M., Stolaríková, M., & Lux, A. (2012). Silicon modifies root anatomy, and uptake and subcellular distribution of cadmium in young maize plants. *Annals of Botany*, 110, 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs039>
- Wang, S. Y., & Galletta, G. J. (1998). Foliar application of potassium silicate induces metabolic changes in strawberry plants. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 21, 157–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904169809365390>
- Yaghubi, K., Ghaderi, N., Vafaei, Y., & Javadi, T. (2016). Potassium silicate alleviates deleterious effects of salinity on two strawberry cultivars grown under soilless pot culture. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 213, 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2016.10.012>
- Zhang, Y., Ding, C., Liu, Y., Li, S., Li, X., Xi, B., & Duan, J. (2023). Xylem anatomical and hydraulic traits vary within crown but do not respond to water and nitrogen addition in *Populus tomentosa*. *Agricultural Water Management*, 278, 108169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108169>
- Zhang, W., Yu, X., Li, M., Lang, D., Zhang, X., & Xie, Z. (2018). Silicon promotes growth and root yield of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* under salt and drought stresses through enhancing osmotic adjustment and regulating antioxidant metabolism. *Crop Protection*, 107, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10265-017-0927-3>

Original Research

The last lynx of the Apennine mountains ridge

Andrea Amici¹, Silvia Cappiello², Luigi Esposito^{3,*},
Nadia Piscopo³

Abstract

Data on the presence of Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in Central and Southern Italy are unclear. We provide a comprehensive analysis of data on the presence of lynx in this area for two periods (1500-1988 and 1989-2008), combining surveys conducted by the authors and other research groups. A total of 705 signs of lynx presence have been recorded. For the period 1989-2008, the 568 signs of presence were catalogued using the SCALP system. Data were evaluated in two survey areas: an extensive survey area (AES) and an intensive survey area (AIS). A large proportion of the observations reported lynx signs across the Central Apennines in the periods from 1989 to 1993 and from 1994 to 1998. The area represented by the Abruzzo region had the largest number of observations (445; 78.35%). Only 10 observations (1.76% of the total number of signs) could be classified as certain. Results indicate the presence of the lynx in the Apennines, which must be considered sporadic and likely represent animals that have been illegally introduced or escaped from captivity areas. It is not possible to affirm the presence of the lynx, but rather, to indicate a date by which the last Apennine lynx disappeared.

Keywords

Eurasian lynx, Apennine mountains, distribution, conservation, species extinction

1 Dept. of Agriculture and Forest Sciences, University of Tuscia, Viterbo, Italy

2 Veterinary Medical Director, Local Health Authority (ASL Napoli 1 Centro), Italy

3 Dept. Veterinary Medicine and Animal Productions, Federico II University of Napoli, Italy

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: luigi.esposito4@unina.it

Citation: Amici, A., Cappiello, S., Esposito, L., Piscopo, N. (2025). The last lynx of the Apennine mountains ridge. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 11.04.2025 / **Accepted:** 19.10.2025 /

Published: 31.10.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.22465>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Zadnji ris iz grebena Apeninskih gora

Izvleček

Podatki o prisotnosti evrazijskega risa (*Lynx lynx*) v osrednji in južni Italiji so nejasni. Predstavljamo celovito analizo podatkov o prisotnosti risa na tem območju v dveh obdobjih (1500–1988 in 1989–2008), v kateri smo združili raziskave, ki so jih opravili avtorji in druge raziskovalne skupine. Skupaj je bilo zabeleženih 705 znakov prisotnosti risa. Za obdobje 1989–2008 je bilo 568 znakov prisotnosti katalogiziranih z uporabo sistema SCALP. Podatki so bili ovrednoteni na dveh raziskovalnih območjih: obsežnem raziskovalnem območju (AES) in intenzivnem raziskovalnem območju (AIS). Velik delež opazovanj je poročal o znakih prisotnosti risa v osrednjih Apeninih v obdobjih od 1989 do 1993 in od 1994 do 1998. Območje, ki ga predstavlja regija Abruzzo, je imelo največje število opazovanj (445; 78,35 %). Le 10 opazovanj (1,76 % skupnega števila znakov) je bilo mogoče opredeliti kot gotova. Rezultati kažejo na prisotnost risa v Apeninih, ki jo je treba obravnavati kot sporadično in verjetno predstavljajo živali, ki so bile nezakonito vnesene ali pobegnile iz ujetništva. Ni mogoče potrditi prisotnosti risa, ampak le navesti datum, ko je izginil zadnji ris iz Apeninov.

Ključne besede

Evrazijski ris, Apeninsko gorovje, razširjenost, ohranjanje, izumrtje vrste

Introduction

The lynx (*Lynx lynx*) is included in Appendix II of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora) and protected by the Bern Convention (Annexe III). The Eurasian lynx is classified as Least Concern by the IUCN (Breitenmoser et al., 2015) due to its wide distribution. However, some European subpopulations are fragmented and listed as Critically Endangered or Endangered across the EU (von Arx, 2018). The presence and distribution of the lynx in the Alps and Central Europe have been extensively studied thanks to the efforts of many researchers and specific monitoring programs: SCALP (Status and Conservation of the Alpine Lynx Population), KORA (Coordinated research projects for the conservation and management of carnivores in Switzerland), the Italian Lynx Project and others. The monitored regions included Europe (Breitenmoser-Würsten & Breitenmoser, 2021; Kaczensky et al., 2024) and the entire Italian Alpine arc (Molinari, 1998; Molinari et al., 2001; 2006; 2012; Molinari-Jobin et al., 2003; 2018). Several authors have carried out a methodical monitoring study of the presence and distribution of the Eurasian lynx in the Alpine biogeographic region which, from east to west, includes Slovenia (Stanisa et al., 2001; Koren et al., 2006; Kos et al., 2012), the Austrian Alps (Huber et al., 2001; Laass et al., 2006;

Fuxjäger et al., 2012), the German Alps (Kaczensky, 1998; Wölfl and Kaczensky, 2001; Wölfl, 2006; Wölfl & Wölfl, 2011), south-western Germany (Kaphegyí et al., 2006), Liechtenstein (Fasel, 2001; 2006), the Swiss Alps (Molinari-Jobin et al., 2001; 2006; Zimmermann, 2011), the Swiss Jura mountains (Breitenmoser et al., 2007) and the French Alps (Stahl & Vandel, 2001; Marboutin et al., 2006; 2012).

These studies, along with the adoption of conservation strategies, including reintroduction (Molinari et al., 2001), have contributed to the current status of the species, as described by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010). A significant monitoring effort has also been implemented in the central Italian Apennines; however, the results have differed from those obtained in the Alps and central Europe. The presence of the lynx in the Apennines in prehistoric times has been affirmed by De Grossi Mazzorin (1998). Recent publications (Cherin et al., 2013; Ghezzi et al., 2015; Serva et al., 2025) suggest that the discovery of fossil skeletons is irrefutable evidence of the prehistoric presence of the lynx on the Italian peninsula (Rustioni et al., 1995). The presence of the lynx in Italy during the 19th century is supported by several authors (Toschi, 1968; Tassi, 1971; Eiberle, 1972; Bruno, 1990; Chazel 2005).

The present and past distribution of this species in the Apennines is unclear, and opinions vary regarding its current presence. Many authors believed that the lynx regularly

inhabited the Apennine habitats (Tassi, 1971; Bruno, 1981; Pandolfi & Giuliani, 1994; Manzi et al., 2002) at least until the early 2000s (Rondinini et al., 2013), while others have questioned the presence of the feline (Baccetti, 1973; Cagnolaro et al. 1975). Finally, some authors have even excluded its presence for a long time (Ghigi, 1917; Toschi, 1968).

Some bibliographic sources (Pavan, 1981; Minelli et al., 2002) exclude the presence of the lynx in the central-southern Apennines since the beginning of the new millennium. The numerous reports from the 1990s seem to be linked to a series of illegal releases of unknown origin (Molinari & Molinari-Jobin, 2000; Ragni, 2002; Bologna & Mingozzi, 2003; Giglio et al. 2009; Rondinini, et al. 2013). A report dating back to 2014 can be attributed to the escape of a male specimen from the Civitella Alfedena Wildlife Area (PNALM, 2014), likely the same specimen photographed and described in the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines (ISPRA, 2014). Other sources (Tassi, 1971; 2007; Bruno, 1990; Pandolfi & Giuliani, 1994; Manzi et al., 2002; Cappiello et al., 2005) suggest that some individuals survive in remote areas of the Apennines.

This study aims to identify the temporal stages of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in a specific Italian geographical area, represented by the Apennine ridge from north to south.

The work was developed along two lines: the first analysed data obtained from indirect surveys that allowed us to evaluate a significant number of reports of lynx presence in the central-southern Italian Apennines over a historical period (1500-1988). The second used a citizen science survey, which allowed us to report observations of the Eurasian lynx over a recent period (1989-2008) and in a more restricted geographical area. The analysed data provided information on the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the central and southern Apennines, on its possible distribution in the past and present and on the possible origin of the animals.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Apennines cover a third of the Italian territory from North (Liguria) to South (Calabria) with mountains reaching 2900 m above sea level. The Tyrrhenian side (west) is characterised by the Mediterranean Biogeographic Region with

temperate deciduous forests (9110) and mixed and coniferous forests (9410, 9420). The Adriatic side (east) hosts beech forests (9110, 9130, 9210), Turkey oaks (91M0), mixed formations (91F0, 91G0, 91H0, 91AA, 91E0), riparian forests (91E0*), with the possible presence of silver fir (9220) and relict species typical of the Continental Biogeographic Region. Both slopes are home to open grasslands (6410, 6510), which, together with high-altitude pastures (62A0, 6520) and agricultural land, fragment the wooded areas. The landscape is characterised by human settlements (rural or urban), mainly in the valleys, and road and rail networks.

Given the limited number of observations (137) recovered for the historical period (1500-1988) throughout Italy, these observations will be used only to hypothesise a possible population decline from South to North. Instead, all observations relating to the period 1989-2008, which indicate the presence of lynx in various Apennine districts, are considered. In light of this and the most recent reports of lynx presence in Abruzzo (Tassi 2007), study efforts have focused primarily on two areas (Figure 1).

The Extended Study Area (AES), which, excluding Abruzzo, includes the Northern Apennines (Tuscan-Emilian Apennines); the Central Apennines (Monti della Laga, Sibillini, and Majella); and the Southern Apennines (Pollino and Aspromonte). The Intensive Study Area (AIS) encompasses the Abruzzo Region and the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park (PNALM).

Data collection and type

In order to obtain useful and verifiable information necessary to determine the presence/absence of lynx across a large area and over a long historical period, lynx presence signals provided by various research groups were collected. From 1989 to 1999, fieldwork and data collection were carried out by the Gruppo Lince Italia (<https://www.comitatoparchi.it/gruppo-lince-italia/>), a group composed of several volunteers and one of the authors. From 1999 to 2002, naturalists Luc Chazel and Muriel da Ros contributed to the Gruppo Lince Italia's investigations (<https://www.slideserve.com/xalvadora/la-lince-nell-appennino-possibile-sottospecie-della-lince-euroasiatica-lynx-lynx-di-francesco-mossolin>). From 2003 to 2008, researchers at the University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) worked to optimise the data collected and refine citizen science applied to the investigation of the presence of the lynx in the Apennines (<https://www.iris.unina.it/handle/11588/121549>). The UNINA

Group continues its carnivore monitoring surveys today.

Observations from monitoring programs supported by volunteers, local governments, and wildlife conservation organisations were also considered. Data on lynx presence were collected and classified according to their source.

The reports came from:

- Directly to the authors for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx, discovery or description of carcasses; videos or images obtained from camera traps or cameras; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of lynx presence such as footprints, scratches, scat, fur, vocalisations; discovery of dens.
- From material in museums or collections for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx, discovery or description of carcasses; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of lynx presence such as vocalisations.
- From material in scientific journals or magazines for the following items: direct sightings of lynx, killing of lynx; attack/predation or damage attributable to lynx; signs of the presence of the lynx, such as footprints, vocalisations, scratches, droppings, fur.

Observations contributed to form a data set that was subjected to verification, organisation and analysis. Data collection was carried out as:

- Bibliographic and web searches. Historical research was based on the collection of texts and publications (scientific journals, nature bulletins, tourist and nature guides, local historiographic works, hunting magazines, local newspapers) in which the presence of the lynx is described in the geographical areas of investigation in the period 1500-1988 (137 reports) and in the period 1989-2008 (192 reports).
- Search for historical finds. The search for taxidermized finds and stuffed animals present in museums and private collections proved very difficult, but, however, contributed to the experimental investigation (1 animal).
- Interviews. Two hundred ninety interviews were conducted, obtained from the direct testimony of elderly hunters, farmers, shepherds, breeders, inhabitants of rural areas, ecotourists, park rangers, and studious individuals. At the end of the interview, a blind test was performed, which consisted of submitting to the interviewee's attention photographic tables of different species or details of animals present in the study area.
- Field observations. Information from fieldwork (signs of presence on transects, direct observations of dead or

alive animals, tracks, scratches, faecal remains or hair) carried out by the lynx group in the period 1989-1999 (24 reports) and by the French naturalists Chazel and Ros (61 reports) was used and analysed.

All observations were classified according to the system suggested in the "First Conference on the Status and Conservation of the Alpine Lynx Population" (SCALP) (Breitenmoser, 1995; 1998), as a common standardised interpretation method is needed (Molinari-Jobin et al., 2010).

The system distinguishes three levels of reliability:

- Q1. Certain Presence: objective facts, indisputable and verifiable, including subjects captured or found dead, photographs, videos.
- Q2. Probable Presence: the finding of remains of wild prey or attacks on livestock and remains of killed domestic animals, presence indicators (traces, scratches, faecal remains, hair) confirmed by qualified operators.
- Q3. Doubtful Presence: reports submitted by unqualified or unverifiable persons and deemed unreliable

Statistical analysis

Our work was able to benefit from a good sample size that allowed us to cluster the qualitative variables represented by the lynx presence signals in the two geographical areas studied into well-defined groups. The different presence signals were assigned one of the three levels of presence reliability proposed by the SCALP group (Q1-Q2-Q3). Finally, to better evaluate the trend over time of the lynx presence in the AES and AIS areas, it was decided to carry out a more in-depth analysis starting from the year 1989. The lynx presence signals were therefore divided into four periods, each consisting of 5 years (one *lustrum*): L1 1989–1993, L2 1994–1998, L3 1999–2003, L4 2004–2008. The results obtained were compared in pairs between the groups by applying the chi-square test (SPSS, 2021).

Results

A total of 705 signs of lynx presence were collected along the Apennine mountains ridge, of which 137 reports provided information regarding the lynx in a historical period (from 1500 to 1988) and 568 reports covered a recent period (1989-2008). Figure 1 shows that in historical times the presence of the lynx on the Apennine ridge was reported in ten regions of Italy (Emilia-Romagna, Marche,

Tuscany, Umbria, Abruzzo, Molise, Lazio, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria). In the more recent period (1989-2008), the reports concerned eight regions (Emilia-Romagna, Marche, Tuscany, Umbria, Abruzzo, Molise, Lazio, Calabria).

The historical sample size covered too long a period, and individual reports could not be adequately classified using the SCALP method. Therefore, data from the historical period were used to identify reports of lynx presence geographically (Figure 2), but since it did not allow for qualitatively classifying the reports, it was not used for statistical comparison with the recent data. It was therefore decided to further analyse the recent sample, which is more consistent and divisible into four statistically comparable periods.

Table 1 shows that the highest percentage of observations was recorded in a single region: Abruzzo, i.e., only in the AIS. The remaining observations refer to the seven regions that comprise the AES. Among the latter, the highest percentage of lynx presence signs was reported in Emilia-Romagna, which therefore ranks first among the AES regions for the highest number of reports. A complete summary of the data collected during the survey is reported in Table 2, which also shows the source of the observation (reported in brackets). The analysis of all available data (Table 2) for the recent period indicated that the most frequently detected sign of presence was the sighting of animals (48.59%), followed by vocalisations (13.38%), the

finding of excrement (12.50%) and footprints (11.80%).

Reports of attacks on livestock and related damage amounted to 7.75%. The findings or reporting of animals found dead amounted to 2.11%. However, reports of hair (1.76%), scratches (0.70%) and dens (0.70%) were few. Only 0.35% of the images were captured with camera traps.

Generic data analysis (Table 2) indicates that a limited number of concrete reports were recorded: 2 photos from camera traps (1 L2 and 1 L4); 2 carcasses (1 L1 and 1 L3); 12 kills (7 L1, 2 L2; 3 L3). Most of the concrete reports were made in the first three *lustra* (four five-year periods) while only one presumed appearance from a camera trap was recorded in the last *lustrum* (2004-2008). In terms of the overall number of signs, differences were detected among the *lustra* (Table 2) from L1 to L2 (24.12% vs 44.19%, $P < 0.01$). In the following *lustra*, L3 and L4, the reporting rate showed a gradual, statistically significant decrease compared to L2 (44.19% vs 25.35%, $P < 0.01$; 44.19% vs 6.34%, $P < 0.001$). No statistical differences were observed between L1 and L3. This trend was generally followed within the categories of signs considered separately. The evaluation of the lynx presence reports according to the SCALP methodology (Table 3) over the entire study area (AES + AIS) revealed a small number (1.76%) of "certain presence" signs (Q1) that would suggest the possible persistence of the feline in the Apennines. The "certain presence" signs would be

Figure 1. Comparison map of the lynx distribution study between the Extensive Study Area (AES) and the Intensive Study Area (AIS). The diagonally striped fill indicates the Extended Study Area (AES). The dark grey solid fill indicates the Intensive Study Area (AIS), which corresponds to the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park.

Slika 1. Primerjalna karta raziskave razširjenosti risa med obsežnim raziskovalnim območjem (AES) in intenzivnim raziskovalnim območjem (AIS). Diagonalno črtasto polnilo označuje obsežno raziskovalno območje (AES). Temno sivo polnilo označuje intenzivno raziskovalno območje (AIS), ki ustreza narodnemu parku Abruzzo, Lazio in Molise.

reinforced by the data classified as "probable presence" (Q2), resulting in 26.06% if the data of the four *lustra* are taken. However, the Q1 signal in L4 refers to a single image from a camera trap. The poor quality of the image, however, reduces what was stated above. The analysis of data collected throughout the Apennines (AES and AIS) over a twenty-year period highlighted that the highest number of reports occurred in L2 (n. 251). The number of signals decreased in the following ten years. This result was probably due to the intense monitoring carried out by the Italian Lynx Group in the first decade, as also suggested by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010) in the Austrian and Italian Alps. The decrease in signals recorded in L3 can be attributed to the decrease in monitoring activities provided by specialised personnel, as well as to the reduction of voluntary monitoring. Table 3 shows the trend of lynx presence signals in the four *lustra*, dividing the data into the two geographical areas and based on the level of reliability.

Table 1 indicates that most of the observations were recorded in the AIS (78.35% vs 21.65% in the AES). A similar trend (Table 3) was observed over time in both the AIS and the AES. The analysis conducted within the intensive study area indicates statistically significant differences between L2 vs L3 ($P < 0.01$); L2 vs L1 vs L4 ($P < 0.001$); L1 and L3 vs L4 ($P < 0.0001$); L1 vs L3 (NS).

On the contrary, the data from the AES indicate a similar number of signs of lynx presence in the first two *lustra*, L1 vs L2 (NS), but differences between L2 and the two subsequent five-year periods, L3 ($P < 0.01$) and L4 ($P < 0.001$); finally, L1 differs only from L4 ($P < 0.01$). In the AIS, the level of reliability of the reports of lynx presence (Table 3) was 1.57%, 26.97% and 71.46% for Q1, Q2 and Q3, respectively

($P < 0.01$). Conversely, for AES, the reliability level of the lynx presence reports was 2.44%, 22.76% and 74.80% for Q1, Q2 and Q3, respectively ($P < 0.05$).

The lynx presence signals with a "certain presence" reliability level constituted a low percentage in both study areas; these percentages increased at both the "probable presence" and "doubtful presence" reliability levels. No significant difference was calculated between the two survey areas.

The analysis of the individual *lustra* within AIS indicates a level of "certain presence" (Q1) present in three of the four *lustra* examined (L1, L2 and L3). In all *lustra*, "probable presence" (Q2) and "doubtful presence" (Q3) were reported. Level Q2 did not demonstrate significant differences between *lustra* L2 and L3. Conversely, the observations of the two central *lustra* differed from those reported in L1 and L4 ($P < 0.0001$), just as L1 differed from L4 ($P < 0.05$). Statistical comparison within the Q3 level indicated a marked difference between the percentage in L2 and the remaining *lustra* ($P < 0.001$). The percentages of Q3 signs were similar between L1 and L3 but differed from L4 ($P < 0.001$). In the AES area, the Q1 reliability level was present only in the L3 and L4 five-year periods (66.67% vs 33.33%, $P < 0.001$). As in the AIS area, the "probable presence" (Q2) and "doubtful presence" (Q3) reliability levels are present in all the periods studied. Q2 reports were more frequent in the L1 *lustrum* than in L2 and L4 ($P < 0.01$). The *lustra*, L2, L3 and L4, were not statistically different. Q3 reports had a high degree of variability between the *lustra*: L2 showed a greater number of observations than the others ($P < 0.05$), while L1 was higher than L3 and L4 ($P < 0.05$). No differences were detected between L3 and L4.

Table 1. Eurasian lynx presence signs in the Italian regions (1989-2008). Observations number and percentage.

Tabela 1. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v italijanskih regijah (1989–2008). Število opazovanj in odstotek.

Region	Observations n.	AES only %	AES+ AIS %
Emilia-Romagna	81	65.85	14.26
Lazio	24	19.51	4.22
Marche	6	4.88	1.06
Toscana	6	4.88	1.06
Molise	1	0.81	0.18
Umbria	2	1.63	0.35
Calabria	3	2.44	0.53
Total AES	123		21.65
Abruzzo (AIS)	445		78.35
Total (AES+AIS)	568		

Table 2. List of different types of recorded observations based on the five periods (L=lustra) and historical period (Time 0). (The source of the observation is reported in brackets.)

Tabela 2. Seznam različnih vrst zabeleženih opazovanj na podlagi petih obdobj (L = lustra) in zgodovinskega obdobja (čas 0). (Vir opazovanja je naveden v oklepajih).

Observation type (source)	1989-1993	1994-1998	AES+ AIS %	1999-2003	2004-2008	Total 1989-2008	Total 1500-1988
	L1	L2	14.26	L3	L4	L1-L4	Time 0
Sightings (Authors)	22	66	4.22	48	14	150	31
Sightings (Museum and collections)	14	22	1.06	7	0	43	8
Sightings (Scientific journal)	26	53		0	0	79	18
Sightings (Magazine)	1	0		2	1	4	0
Attack/predation (Authors)	0	8		6	5	19	1
Attack/predation (Museum and collections)	0	1		1	0	2	2
Attack/predation (Scientific journal)	0	7		0	0	7	5
Damage (Authors)	2	0		0	0	2	1
Damage (Museum and collections)	4	0		1	0	5	0
Damage (Scientific journal)	7	2		0	0	9	2
Footprints (Authors)	3	13		11	9	36	2
Footprints (Museum and collections)	5	4		1	0	10	0
Footprints (Scientific journal)	11	10		0	0	21	2
Lynx killing (Authors)	1	1		2	0	4	32
Lynx killing (Museum and collections)	5	1		1	0	7	5
Lynx killing (Magazines)	1	0		0	0	1	0
Carcass (Authors)	0	0		1	0	1	0
Carcass (Museum and collections)	1	0		0	0	1	6
Vocalisations (Authors)	2	12		10	6	30	2
Vocalisations (Museum and collections)	1	0		1	0	2	0
Vocalisations (scientific journal)	22	22		0	0	44	1
Scratch (Authors)	1	0		0	0	1	4
Scratch (scientific journal)	3	0	1.06	0	0	3	6
Scats (Authors)	0	8	0.18	48	0	56	2
Scats (scientific journal)	1	14	0.35	0	0	15	7
Hair (Authors)	0	1	0.53	1	0	2	0
Hair (scientific journal)	4	4	21.65	0	0	8	0
Camera traps (Authors)	0	1	78.35	0	1	2	0
Den (Authors)	0	1		3	0	4	0
Total reliable signs	137	251		144	36	568	137

Table 3. Total number of signs of Eurasian lynx presence divided into the lustra (L1, L2, L3, L4) and the three levels of reliability (Q1, Q2, Q3), in the area of intensive study (AIS) and in the area of extensive study (AES).

Tabela 3. Skupno število znakov prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, razdeljenih na lustre (L1, L2, L3, L4) in tri stopnje zanesljivosti (Q1, Q2, Q3), na območju intenzivne študije (AIS) in na območju ekstenzivne študije (AES).

Area	year	1989-1993	1994-1998	1999-2003	2004-2008	Total
		L1	L2	L3	L4	
AIS	Q1	3	1	3	0	7
	Q2	16	47	52	5	120
	Q3	81	158	64	15	318
	Tot AIS	100	206	119	20	445
AES	Q1	0	0	2	1	3
	Q2	10	5	8	5	28
	Q3	27	40	15	10	92
	Tot AES	37	45	25	16	123

Discussion

The results show a different distribution of lynx presence signals in different periods and areas. It is possible that these discrepancies are due to differences in monitoring systems or habitat characteristics, a possibility also envisioned by Molinari-Jobin et al. (2010). Unfortunately, the scarcity of signs of "certain presence" as well as the shy characteristics of the lynx and the large territory they need to live in, do not allow us to draw conclusions on the number of lynxes that would possibly inhabit the Apennine ridge. The signs Q1 and Q2 are reported scattered throughout the Apennines and have not provided sufficient data to hypothesise the possible origin of the animals. This result also occurs in other countries characterised by low lynx

populations (Huber et al., 2001; Laass et al., 2006). The data reported above have been translated cartographically (Figures 3 and 4).

In Figure 2, it is easily visible how the distribution of the lynx along the Apennine ridge has changed from the historical period (1500-1988) to the recent period (1989-2008).

In Figure 3, the areas where the greatest number of reports have been recorded are highlighted. Most of the reports can be attributed to a reliability level Q3 (Figure 4) and refer to seven regions. For the reliability level Q2, Figure 5 indicates the five regions in which the reports have been recorded. Finally, Figure 6 shows the three regions within which certain presences (Q1) of lynx have been reported.

Figure 2. Signs of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the Apennines. Comparison between the periods 1500-1988 and 1989-2008 (based on municipality).

Slika 2. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v Apeninih. Primerjava med obdobjema 1500–1988 in 1989–2008 (na podlagi občin).

Figure 3. Signs of the presence of the Eurasian lynx in the Apennines during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Blue indicates low consistency; yellow, medium; red, high consistency.

Slika 3. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa v Apeninih v obdobju 1989–2008 (na podlagi občin). Modra barva označuje nizko konsistentnost, rumena srednjo, rdeča pa visoko konsistentnost.

Figure 4. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q3 (blue from 1 to 9 reports; yellow from 10 to 34 reports; red from 35 to 56 reports).

Slika 4. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q3 (modra barva od 1 do 9 poročil; rumena barva od 10 do 34 poročil; rdeča barva od 35 do 56 poročil).

Figure 5. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q2 (blue from 1 to 3 reports; yellow from 4 to 13 reports; red from 14 to 27 reports).

Slika 5. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q2 (modra barva od 1 do 3 poročil; rumena barva od 4 do 13 poročil; rdeča barva od 14 do 27 poročil).

Figure 6. Signs of the presence of Eurasian lynx registered during the period 1989–2008 (based on municipality). Reliability of sign Q1 (blue from 1 report; yellow from 2 reports; red from 3 to 4 reports).

Slika 6. Znaki prisotnosti evrazijskega risa, zabeleženi v obdobju 1989–2008 (po občinah). Zanesljivost znaka Q1 (modra barva: 1 poročilo; rumena barva: 2 poročila; rdeča barva: 3 do 4 poročila).

Conclusions

Our work indicates quite clearly that over the four *lustra* studied, reports of lynx presence have gradually decreased. This has proven to be true both in the extensive study area and in the intensive study area. The decrease in signs of certain presence (Q1) has been very significant and would lead one to think of the definitive disappearance of lynx in the central and southern Apennines. Certain observations, however, represent single individuals for which no evidence of reproductive activity has certainly been recorded over a period of twenty years.

Although the lynx is not an endangered species in Europe, it is not possible, now, to think of a management program for the species as has been done for other carnivores such as the wolf, which, despite re-proposing the human-animal conflict (Piscopo et al., 2021), has seen an increase in wild populations. The recovery and dispersion of large carnivore populations depend on many factors, some of which are controversial. A lynx conservation program (Serva et al., 2025) cannot ignore the presence of a non-fragmented forest as well as the presence of the main trophic resource constituted by the roe deer. If, for the first condition, there do not seem to be adequate solutions (increasing urbanisation), the current diffusion of some species, such as the roe deer and the wild boar, constantly increasing in the central Apennines (Piscopo et al., 2023) would lead us to think that the application of the lynx reintroduction models is possible. The major critical issues would therefore derive from the growing presence of human settlements in all habitats (Basille et al., 2009).

In conclusion, in the studied period, the signs of presence recorded are not sufficient to demonstrate the persistence of the feline in the Apennine ridge. Our data, in fact, suggest a possible presence of non-resident specimens and certainly not an active reproductive population. The ISPRA report of a lynx in the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines could coincide with that of the PNALM regarding the escape of a specimen from the wildlife area, which occurred more than five years after the end of our investigation. The subsequent discovery of a corpse would therefore confirm that this animal would be the last Apennine lynx.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; methodology, A.A., L.E.; software, A.A., N.P.; validation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; formal analysis, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; investigation, S.C., L.E.; resources, L.E.; data curation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; writing—original draft preparation, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; writing—review and editing, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; visualization, A.A., S.C., L.E., N.P.; supervision, N.P.; project administration, L.E.; funding acquisition, L.E.. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge those who have allowed them to use the data in their possession: Gruppo Lince Italia, PNALM, Franco Tassi, Luc Chazel, Muriel da Ros, Mario Pellegrini, Luigi Ricci, Claudio Bertarelli, Daniele Badaloni, Cappelletto Silvia. For allowing us to consult their archives: Biblioteca Nazionale di Napoli, Museo di Zoologia di Napoli, Archivio dell'ex Zoo di Napoli, Archivio del PNALM, Museo della lince di Civitella Alfedena, Biblioteca Nazionale di Torino, Museo di Zoologia di Torino, Biblioteca di Paleontologia dell'Università di Torino, Museo Regionale di Scienze Naturali di Torino, Archivio del Parco Nazionale del Gran Paradiso, Museo di Ecologia e Storia Naturale di Marano sul Panaro, Museo delle Madonie di Messina.

A special thanks goes to our first author, Prof. Andrea Amici, who, like the last lynx, passed away on July 15, 2022, but who continues to work alongside us.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability

Research data of this study were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17485388>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Baccetti, B. (1973). La fauna. In G. Chiarelli, G. Moggi, B. Baccetti, C. Fabiani, S. Orsi, & P. Paoli (Eds.), *La natura in Toscana* (p. 222). Firenze: Il Fiorino. (In Italian)
- Basille, M., Herfindal, I., Santin-Janin, H., Linnell, J. D. C., Odden, J., Andersen, R., Høgda, K. A., & Gaillard, J. (2009). What shapes Eurasian lynx distribution in human dominated landscapes: Selecting prey or avoiding people? *Ecography*, 32(4), 683–691. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2009.05712.x>
- Bologna, M., & Mingozzi, T. (2003). Distribuzione geografica della lince in Italia. In L. Boitani, S. Lovari, & A. Vigna Taglianti (Eds.), *Fauna d'Italia, Mammalia III Carnivora-Artiodactyla* (Vol. I, pp. 226–234). Bologna: Calderini. (In Italian)
- Breitenmoser, U. (1995). The re-introduction of the lynx into the Alps. In C. Breitenmoser-Würsten, C. Rohner, & U. Breitenmoser (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st SCALP Conference, Engelberg, Switzerland, 254*. Strasbourg: Council of Europe Publishing. (Environmental encounters; 38)
- Breitenmoser, U., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., & Capt, S. (1998). Re-introduction and present status of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in Switzerland. *Hystrix*, 10, 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-10.1-4118>
- Breitenmoser, U., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Capt, S., Molinari-Jobin, A., Molinari, P., & Zimmermann, F. (2007). Conservation of the lynx *Lynx lynx* in the Swiss Jura Mountains. *Wildlife Biology*, 13, 340–355. [https://doi.org/10.2981/0909-6396\(2007\)13\[340:COTLLJ\]2.0.CO](https://doi.org/10.2981/0909-6396(2007)13[340:COTLLJ]2.0.CO)
- Breitenmoser, U., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Lanz, T., von Arx, M., Antonevich, A., Bao, W., & Avgan, B. (2015). *Lynx lynx*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2015: e.T12519A121707666. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/12519/121707666>
- Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., & Breitenmoser, U. (2021). The Eurasian lynx in Continental Europe. *CATnews*, Special Issue No. 14. ISSN 1027-2992
- Bruno, S. (1990). Storia della lince in Italia centro meridionale. *Umanità Pietra Verde*, 5, 103–140. (In Italian)
- Cagnolaro, L., Rosso, D., Spagnesi, M., & Venturi, B. (1975). Inchiesta sulla distribuzione del gatto selvatico (*Felis silvestris*, Schreber) in Italia e nei Cantoni Ticino e Grigioni (Svizzera) e del gatto selvatico sardo (*Felis libica sarda*, Lataste) in Sardegna con notizie sulla lince (*Lynx lynx*, L.) 1971–1973. *Ricerche di Biologia della Selvaggina*, 64, 81–82. (In Italian)
- Cappiello, S., Manco, C., Leone, P., Chazel, L., Da Ros, M., D'Andrea, M., Nioli, A., & Esposito, L. (2005). *Lynx lynx* presence in the Italian Apennines: Three lustrum of observation. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Symposium on Wild Fauna, Tatranska Lomnica, Slovak Republic*, 4, 141.
- Chazel, L. (2005). Les lynx, essai de paléontologie et formes actuelles. *La Gazette des grands prédateurs*, 15, 15–17. (In French)
- Cherin, M., Iurino, D. A., & Sardella, R. (2013). New well-preserved material of *Lynx issiodorensis valdarnensis* (Felidae, Mammalia) from the Early Pleistocene of Pantalla (central Italy). *Bollettino della Società Paleontologica Italiana*, 52(2), 103–111. <https://doi.org/10.4435/BSPI.2013.16>
- De Grossi Mazzorin, J. (1998). Alcune osservazioni sulla fauna dell'abitato protostorico di «le Paludi» di Celano. In V. D'Ercole & R. Cairoli (Eds.), *Archeologia in Abruzzo: Storia di un metanodotto tra industria e cultura* (pp. 209–220). Tarquinia. (In Italian)
- Eiberle, K. (1972). Lebensweise und Bedeutung des Luchses. In P. Pary (Ed.), *Der Kulturlandschaft dargestellt anhand der Ausrottungsgeschichte, der Schweiz*. *Mammalia depicta* (p. 103). Hamburg: D. Pary. (In German)
- Fasel, M. (2001). The lynx in Liechtenstein. *Hystrix*, 12, 29. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-12.2-4175>
- Fasel, M. (2006). The lynx in Liechtenstein. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49(1), 53–54. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.49.1.15067>
- Fuxjäger, C., Laass, J., & Molinari-Jobin, A. (2012). Lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Austrian Alps 2005 to 2009. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 55(2), 65–69. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.55.2.15537>
- Ghezzi, E., Boscaini, A., Madurell-Malapeira, J., & Rook, L. (2015). Lynx remains from the Pleistocene of Valdemino cave (Savona, Northwestern Italy), and the oldest occurrence of *Lynx spelaeus* (Carnivora, Felidae). *Rendiconti Lincei. Scienze Fisiche e Naturali*, 26, 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12210-014-0363-4>
- Ghigi, A. (1917). I mammiferi d'Italia considerati nei loro apporti con l'agricoltura. *Natura*, 8, 85–137. (In Italian)
- Giglio, G., Russo, M., Rendina, M., Pinto, S., Dionisio, G., & Esposito, L. (2009). Illegal trade of the biodiversity in Italy: Evaluation of the data from 2004 to 2007. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Symposium on Wild Fauna, Zamora, Spain*, 6, 81–82.
- Huber, T., Laass, J., & Engleder, T. (2001). Present knowledge on the distribution of the lynx in Austria. *Hystrix*, 12, 31–37.
- Kaczynsky, P. (1998). Status and distribution of the lynx in the German Alps. *Hystrix*, 10(1), 39–42. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-10.1-4120>
- Kaczynsky, P., Ranc, N., Hatlauf, J., Payne, J. C., et al. (2024). Large carnivore distribution maps and population updates 2017–2022/23. Report to the European Commission under contract N° 09.0201/2023/907799/SER/ENV.D.3 "Support for Coexistence with Large Carnivores", "B.4 Update of the distribution maps". IUCN/SSC Large Carnivore Initiative for Europe (LCIE) and Istituto di Ecologia Applicata (IEA).
- Kaphegyi, T. A. M., Kaphegyi, U., & Müller, U. (2006). Status of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Black Forest region, South Western Germany. *Mammalian Biology*, 71, 172–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2006.01.001>
- Koren, I., Jonozovic, M., & Kos, I. (2006). Status and distribution of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx* L.) in Slovenia in 2000–2004 and comparison with the years 1995–1999. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49, 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.49.1.14753>
- Kos, I., Koren, I., Potočnik, H., & Krofel, M. (2012). Status and distribution of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx* L.) in Slovenia in 2005–2009. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 55(2), 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.55.2.15535>
- ISPRA. (2014). For the first time a lynx photographed in the Apennines. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/en/archive/news/year-2014/for-the-first-time-a-lynx-photographed-in-the-apennines>

- Laass, J., Fuxjäger, C., Huber, T., & Gerstl, N. (2006). Lynx in the Austrian Alps 2000 to 2004. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49, 43–49.
- Manzi, A., Pellegrini, P., & Natale, A. (2002). Presenza storica della lince nell'Appennino centrale. *Rivista Abruzzese, Rassegna Trimestrale di Cultura*, 2, 1–9. (In Italian)
- Marboutin, E., Duchamp, C., Rouland, P., Léonard, Y., Boyer, J., Michallet, D., Catusse, M., Migot, P., Vandel, J. M., & Stahl, P. (2006). Survey of the lynx distribution in the French Alps: 2000–2004 population status analysis. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49, 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.49.1.13530>
- Marboutin, E., Duchamp, C., Moris, P., Briaudet, P. E., Léonard, Y., & Catusse, M. (2012). Survey of the *Lynx lynx* distribution in the French Alps: 2005–2009 update. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 55(1), 29–34. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.55.1.15523>
- Minelli, A., Chemini, C., Argano, R., & Ruffo, S. (2002). *La fauna in Italia*. Milano: Touring; Roma: Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio. (In Italian)
- Molinari, P. (1998). The lynx in the Italian south-eastern Alps. *Hystrix*, 10(1), 55–64.
- Molinari, P., & Molinari-Jobin, A. (2000). La lince eurasiatica. *Habitat*, 104, 98–109. (In Italian)
- Molinari, P., Rotelli, L., Catello, M., & Bassano, B. (2001). Present status and distribution of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Italian Alps. *Hystrix*, 12, 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-12.2-4172>
- Molinari, P., Bionda, R., Carmignola, G., Catello, M., Cetto, E., Filacorda, S., Gavagnin, P., Mingozzi, T., Rodolfi, M., & Molinari-Jobin, A. (2006). Status of the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Italian Alps: An overview 2000–2004. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49, 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.55.1.15524>
- Molinari, P., Bionda, R., Carmignola, G., Filacorda, S., Groff, C., Mingozzi, T., Marucco, F., & Molinari-Jobin, A. (2012). Status and distribution of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Italian Alps 2005–2009. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 55(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.55.1.15524>
- Molinari-Jobin, A., Zimmermann, F., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Capt, S., & Breitenmoser, U. (2001). Present status and distribution of the lynx in the Swiss Alps. *Hystrix*, 12, 17–27. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-12.2-4174>
- Molinari-Jobin, A., Molinari, P., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Wölfli, M., Stanisa, C., Fasel, M., Stahl, P., Vandel, J. M., Rotelli, L., Kaczensky, P., Huber, T., Adamic, M., Koren, I., & Breitenmoser, U. (2003). The Pan-Alpine Conservation Strategy for the lynx. *Nature and Environment* No. 130. Strasbourg: Council of Europe Publishing.
- Molinari-Jobin, A., Zimmermann, F., Angst, C., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Capt, S., & Breitenmoser, U. (2006). Status and distribution of the lynx in the Swiss Alps 2000–2004. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49, 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.54.2.15483>
- Molinari-Jobin, A., Marboutin, E., Wölfli, S., Wölfli, M., Molinari, P., Fasel, M., Kos, I., Blažič, M., Breitenmoser, C., Fuxjäger, C., Huber, T., Koren, I., & Breitenmoser, U. (2010). Recovery of the Alpine lynx *Lynx lynx* metapopulation. *Oryx*, 44, 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605309991013>
- Molinari-Jobin, A., Kéry, M., Marboutin, E., Marucco, F., Zimmermann, F., Molinari, P., Frick, H., Fuxjäger, C., Wölfli, S., Bled, F., Breitenmoser-Würsten, C., Kos, I., Wölfli, M., Černe, R., Müller, O., & Breitenmoser, U. (2018). Mapping range dynamics from opportunistic data: Spatiotemporal modelling of the lynx distribution in the Alps over 21 years. *Animal Conservation*, 21, 168–180. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12369>
- Pandolfi, M., & Giuliani, A. (1994). Lineamenti storici e ricerca faunistica nella provincia di Pesaro e Urbino e delle Marche. *Biogeographia*, 17, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.21426/B617110315> (In Italian)
- Pavan, M. (1981). Distribuzione e biologia di 22 specie di mammiferi in Italia. In M. Pavan (Ed.), CNR. Roma.
- Piscopo, N., Gentile, L., Scioli, E., Alberti, J. P., & Esposito, L. (2021). Management models applied to the human-wolf conflict in agroforestry-pastoral territories of two Italian protected areas and one Spanish game area. *Animals*, 11(4), 1141. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11041141>
- Piscopo, N., Tamburis, O., Bonavolontà, F., Verde, M. T., Manno, M., Mancusi, M., & Esposito, L. (2023). Assessing wild boar presence and activity in a monitoring specific area of Campania region using camera traps. *Acta IMEKO*, 12(4), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.21014/actaimeko.v12i4.1617>
- PNALM. (2014). Rinvenuti resti della lince fuggita dall'area faunistica. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from <https://www.parcoabruzzo.it/dettaglio.php?id=25188> (In Italian)
- Ragni, B. (2002). *Atlante dei mammiferi dell'Umbria*. Città di Castello, Perugia: Petrucci. (In Italian)
- Rondinini, C., Battistoni, A., Peronace, V., & Teofili, C. (2013). *Lista Rossa IUCN dei Vertebrati Italiani*. Roma: Comitato Italiano IUCN e Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare. (In Italian)
- Rustioni, M., Sardella, R., & Rook, L. (1995). Note sulla distribuzione e sulla tassonomia del genere *Lynx* in Italia. *Padusa Quaderni*, 1, 359–364. (In Italian)
- Serva, D., Krofel, M., Cerasoli, F., Biondi, M., & Iannella, M. (2025). Supporting reintroduction planning: A framework integrating habitat suitability, connectivity and individual-based modelling. A case study with the Eurasian lynx in the Apennines. *Diversity and Distributions*, 31, e70024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.70024>
- SPSS. (2021). *IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows (Version 28.0)*. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.
- Stahl, P., & Vandel, J. M. (2001). Lynx distribution in French Alps (1995–1999). *Hystrix*, 12, 11–15.
- Stanisa, C., Koren, I., & Adamic, M. (2001). Situation and distribution of the lynx in Slovenia from 1995–1999. *Hystrix*, 12, 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-12.2-4178>
- Tassi, F. (1971). La lince nell'Appennino centrale. *Lavori della Società Italiana di Biogeografia*, 2, 655–672. (In Italian)
- Tassi, F. (2007). Linci sull'Appennino? Una foto riaccende il dibattito. *Oasis*, 173, 65–67. (In Italian)
- Toschi, A. (1968). Rapport sur la disparition du lynx en Italie. In J. Kratochvil (Ed.), *History of the distribution of the lynx in Europe*. *Acta Scientiarum Naturalium Brno*, 2, 17–23.
- von Arx, M. (2018). *Lynx lynx* (Europe assessment). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2018: e.T12519A145266191. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/12519/145266191>

Wölfel, M., & Kaczensky, P. (2001). Present status and distribution of the lynx in the German Alps. *Hystrix*, 12, 39–41. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-12.2-4177>

Wölfel, M. (2006). Present status and distribution of the lynx in the German Alps 2000–2004. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 49(1), 51–52. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.49.1.14755>

Wölfel, S., & Wölfel, M. (2011). Status of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the German Alps 2005–2009. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 54(2), 81–83. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.54.2.15481>

Zimmermann, F., Molinari-Jobin, A., Ryser, A., Breitenmoser, C., Pesenti, E., & Breitenmoser, U. (2011). Status and distribution of the lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Swiss Alps 2005–2009. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 54(2), 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.54.2.15483>

Original Research

Screening of pesticide residues in a small agricultural watershed in Ogbomoso, Southwest Nigeria

Odunayo J. Gbadegesin^{1,*}, Ebenezer O. Ajiboye¹,
Kasali A. Adelasoye¹, Toyin P. Abegunrin^{2,3}, Oladele A. Olaniran¹

Abstract

Pesticide residues in soil and water along the Oba River watershed in Ogbomoso, southwest Nigeria, were investigated to assess environmental contamination from agricultural practices. Surface water and soil samples (36 each) were collected during the dry (December 2024) and wet (April 2024) seasons from six locations, including five agricultural sites (Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Scheme, Ikose Potatoes Farms, Vegetable Farms Iluju) and a control site (Yaku Ogbomoso). Samples were analysed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) following the QuEChERS method. Semi-structured interviews with 55 farmers provided insights into pesticide use patterns. Results revealed significant contamination, with pesticide concentrations frequently exceeding the European Union Maximum Residue Limits (EU-MRL: 0.001- 0.01 mg/kg for soil, 0.1 mg/kg for water). In soil, Ladokun had the highest residues during the dry season, including Dichlorvos (1.52 ± 0.31 mg/kg), α -Lindane (1.35 ± 0.30 mg/kg), and Atrazine (1.27 ± 0.03 mg/kg). During the wet season, Ikose Potatoes Farms showed high levels of Chlorpyrifos (0.40 ± 0.08 mg/kg) and Dichlorvos (0.43 ± 0.12 mg/kg). In water, heptachlor peaked at Ladokun (2.13 ± 0.42 mg/kg) and Carbofuran at Ikose Potatoes Farms (2.13 ± 0.32 mg/kg) during the wet season. Organochlorines (Heptachlor, Dieldrin) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos) dominated, reflecting intensive pesticide use and persistence. The control site showed minimal residues, confirming agricultural activities as the primary contamination source. Farmers' limited knowledge of pesticide application, revealed through interviews, exacerbates environmental risks. These findings emphasise the need for sustainable agricultural practices, biopesticide adoption, and enhanced farmer education to mitigate ecological and health risks in the region.

Keywords

Pesticides, Agriculture, Residues, Chemicals, Environment, Surface, Soil, Water

1 Department of Crop and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

2 Department of Agricultural Engineering, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

3 Department of Crop Science, National University of Lesotho, Roma, Lesotho.

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: ojgbadegesin@lautech.edu.ng

Citation: Gbadegesin, O. J., Ajiboye, E. O., Adelasoye, K. A., Abegunrin, T. P., Olaniran, O. A. (2025). Screening of pesticide residues in a small agricultural watershed in Ogbomoso, Southwest Nigeria. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 17.06.2025 / **Accepted:** 15.11.2025 / **Published:** 19.11.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.23049>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Preverjanje ostankov pesticidov v majhnem kmetijskem porečju v Ogbomосу v jugozahodni Nigeriji

Izvleček

Vzdolž porečja reke Oba v Ogbomосу, jugozahodna Nigerija, smo preiskali ostanke pesticidov v tleh in vodi, s čimer smo želeli oceniti onesnaženje okolja zaradi kmetijskih praks. Vzorec površinske vode in tal je bil odvzet med sušnim (december 2024) in deževnim (april 2024) obdobjem na šestih lokacijah, vključno s petimi kmetijskimi območji (Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Scheme, Ikose Potatoes Farms, Vegetable Farms Iluju) in kontrolnim območjem (Yaku Ogbomoso). Vzorci so bili analizirani z uporabo plinske kromatografije z masno spektrometrijo (GC-MS) po metodi QuEChERS. Polstrukturirani intervjuji z 55 kmeti so omogočili vpogled v vzorce uporabe pesticidov. Rezultati so pokazali znatno onesnaženost, saj so koncentracije pesticidov pogosto presegale najvišje dovoljene vrednosti ostankov Evropske unije (EU-MRL: 0,001–0,01 mg/kg za tla, 0,1 mg/kg za vodo). Najvišje ostanke v sušnem obdobju v tleh smo izmerili na lokaciji Ladokun: vključno z diklorvosom ($1,52 \pm 0,31$ mg/kg), α -lindanom ($1,35 \pm 0,30$ mg/kg) in atrazinom ($1,27 \pm 0,03$ mg/kg). V deževnem obdobju je kmetija Ikose Potatoes Farms pokazala visoke ravni klorpirifosa ($0,40 \pm 0,08$ mg/kg) in diklorvosa ($0,43 \pm 0,12$ mg/kg). V vodi je heptaklor dosegel najvišjo vrednost v Ladokunu ($2,13 \pm 0,42$ mg/kg), karbofuran pa na kmetiji Ikose Potatoes Farms ($2,13 \pm 0,32$ mg/kg) med deževnim obdobjem. Prevladovali so organoklorini (heptaklor, dieldrin) in organofosfati (klorpirifos, diklorvos), kar odraža intenzivno uporabo pesticidov in njihovo obstojnost. Na kontrolni lokaciji so bili ostanki minimalni, kar potrjuje, da so kmetijske dejavnosti glavni vir onesnaženja. Omejeno znanje kmetov o uporabi pesticidov, ki je bilo razvidno iz intervjujev, povečuje tveganja za okolje. Te ugotovitve poudarjajo potrebo po trajnostnih kmetijskih praksah, uvedbi biopesticidov in izboljšanju izobraževanja kmetov, da se zmanjšajo ekološka in zdravstvena tveganja v regiji.

Ključne besede

Pesticidi, kmetijstvo, ostanke, kemikalije, okolje, površina, tla, voda

Introduction

The intensification of agricultural and industrial activities worldwide has led to widespread contamination of natural resources, particularly soil and water, by pesticide residues and heavy metals, posing significant threats to ecosystems and human health (Han et al., 2025). Globally, pesticide consumption, encompassing herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides, reaches 2.0 to 3.5 million metric tons annually, with residues persisting in environmental compartments due to their chemical stability and mobility (Iqbal et al., 2025; Shah & Wu, 2019; Khan et al., 2023). Recent studies on hydrochemistry of the surface water in Oba River, Ogbomoso was investigated and revealed that there is need for regular monitoring of sodium content in the water to determine suitability for irrigation purpose (Ogungbesan et al., 2022), also It has been reported that freshwater contamination by pesticides is particularly acute, with surface water scores

exceeding thresholds in regions like Nigeria in Africa and South Asia, where over 50% of samples in many countries surpass regulatory limits for persistent compounds such as aldrin and dieldrin (Huang & Li, 2025). These residues show strong partitioning behaviours, with moderate to high soil organic carbon-water partition coefficients (Koc) facilitating long half-lives often exceeding 100 days, leading to bioaccumulation in soil microbiomes and aquatic systems, thereby threatening biodiversity, crop productivity, and public health through carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic pathways (Adesida et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2025).

Seasonal variations further exacerbate residue dynamics, as wet seasons dilute concentrations through dilution and runoff, while dry periods concentrate pollutants via reduced water volumes and intensified application (Commelin et al., 2022). In global agricultural hotspots, such as paddy fields and riverine systems, monitoring across seasons has detected up to 77% of targeted pesticides in soils

and 44% in waters exceeding safety thresholds (Lee et al., 2025). Land-use patterns amplify these effects, with arable lands showing elevated inputs compared to forested areas, influencing spatial distribution and degradation rates influenced by soil properties and organic matter (Jones and Brown, 2023; Lee et al., 2023).

In Africa, where agriculture underpins food security for over 60% of the population, pesticide reliance is acute amid climate variability and limited regulatory enforcement, resulting in hotspots of contamination (Osabohien, 2024). Countries like Malawi and Nigeria report extreme groundwater scores (up to 5.01) and non-carcinogenic health quotients exceeding 1, driven by runoff from intensive cropping (Huang & Li, 2025). Seasonal fluctuations are pronounced in semi-arid regions, such as Nigeria's Hadejia-Nguru wetlands, where dry-season concentrations of Dichlorvos (up to 231.70 µg/L) and permethrin (up to 80.00 µg/L in water; 197.95 mg/kg in sediments) far surpass wet-season levels, linked to heightened farming and low dilution (Adebayo et al., 2025). Similarly, in Katsina, Nigeria, agricultural sites, residues in water and soil spike during dry periods due to irrigation and dust mobilisation, underscoring the need for season-specific monitoring (Yusuf et al., 2025). These patterns reflect broader African trends, where land-use intensification in cultivated areas correlates with higher partitioning into aquatic-terrestrial interfaces, contrasting minimal inputs in non-arable systems (Corru, 2024; Degrendele et al., 2022).

The authors, García et al. (2024), recommended that for full elucidation on pesticides' fate, future research must address these multidimensional dynamics through integrated modelling approaches that couple land-use patterns, pesticide application regimes, and environmental variables. Such efforts are critical for developing sustainable agrochemical management strategies that minimise ecological risks while supporting agricultural productivity. In spite of this, screening of pesticides in environmental matrices such as soil and water has never been conducted on the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. Limited published studies have instead focused on vegetables and rice on the Oba River, severely limiting the possibility of targeted public-health interventions. This study then analysed surface water and soil samples collected during two seasons at 6 locations in a small agricultural watershed within the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso for pesticides in order to identify pesticide use patterns within the watershed. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted with the farmers along the river.

Materials and Methods

Sampling Area

The study was conducted in a small agricultural watershed within the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, southwestern Nigeria (Figure 1). An earthfill dam was built in 1964 across the river between Ikose and Yaku to provide Ogbomoso Township with potable water. Ogbomoso, southwest Nigeria, lies between 8° 00' N, 4° 10' E and 8° 15' N; 4° 20' E. According to Abegunrin et al. (2020), the region has an average of 1200 mm of rainfall annually, with mean annual minimum and maximum temperatures of 28 and 33°C, respectively. The bank of the river is usually grown to various crops (maize, okra, eggplant, etc.), especially during the dry season, when water is abstracted from the river (and the reservoir) with pumps for irrigation purposes.

Sampling

Samples were collected from six locations within the watershed in the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. The locations are: Ladokun Village (8.208591°N, 4.281720°E), Iluju Maize Farms (8.201696°N, 4.204226°E), Iluju Irrigation Farm (8.198282°N, 4.204270°E); Potatoes Farms within the Iluju Irrigation Scheme, the Vegetables Farm within Ikose Irrigation Scheme (8.188913°N, 4.199577°E). For comparative purposes, Yaku Village (8.178913°N, 4.199657°E) within the watershed was selected as the control site, representing an area with non-agricultural activities.

Soil samples were collected during the wet and dry seasons, after the crops had been planted at the locations. In all, 36 water and 36 soil samples were taken; 18 surface water and 18 soil samples were taken between April 6 and 14, 2024, during the rainy season, and 18 water and 18 soil samples were taken between December 15 and 20, 2024, during the dry season.

Water samples were collected in triplicate, using the manual grab method, at 15 - 60 cm depth. Most of the samples were taken 3 m (±1 m) away from the riverbank using a long-handled plastic dipper, and a subset of the samples was taken in the centre of the main flow. The sample bottles were washed with laboratory-grade soap and sterilised by immersion in a water bath for 10 minutes (Dastogeer, 2022). The bottles were rinsed several times with the water to be sampled before collection. Then, submerging and filling it to approximately 490 mL, the samples were imme-

added to the tube, and the sample was shaken vigorously for 10 min. Then, 4 g anhydrous MgSO₄ and 1 g NaCl were added to the tube, and the tube was shaken vigorously again for 5 min. Then the tubes were centrifuged for 5 min at a relative centrifugal force (RCF) of 2811 × g, and 1.5 mL supernatant was transferred into a 2 mL centrifuge tube containing 50 mg PSA and 150 mg MgSO₄. The 2 mL centrifuge tube was vortexed for 1 min and centrifuged for 5 min at RCF 2400 × g. Next, 1 mL supernatant was pipetted into a 2 mL centrifuge tube and the sample was dried by nitrogen flow in a water bath at 40 °C. Finally, 1 mL of ethyl acetate was added to the centrifuge tube to reconstitute the target pesticides, then the sample was passed through a 0.22 µm microporous membrane, and 10 µL IS was added into each vial for GC × GC-TOF-MS detection, which was performed using previously reported methods (K. Wang et al., 2023) and described in the Supporting Information. For water samples, 100 mL of water samples was pipetted into a triangular flask, and the pH of the water samples was adjusted between 3 and 5 with HCl. Before loading samples, a sequential solid-phase extraction (SSPE) cartridge, a C18 cartridge (on top) coupled with an HLB cartridge (on bottom), was activated by 5 mL of acetone, methanol, and ultra-pure water in sequence. After that, 100 mL water samples were passed through the SSPE cartridge and were dried under a vacuum for 15 min to remove retained water. The C18 cartridge and HLB cartridge were eluted 3 times using 15 mL of acetone and DCM (4:1, v/v), and the eluent was collected. Next, the eluent was evaporated to dry by using a rotary evaporator (40 °C, 0.09 MPa). The next steps of sample preparation and injection were the same as in the above-mentioned description

Gas Chromatography Analysis

The samples were analysed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) using a Varian 3800/4000 system for the pesticide residues identification and quantification. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a capillary column AT-1, length was 30 m, ID was 0.25 mm, and film thickness was 0.25 µm. The carrier gas was nitrogen (purity 99.00%) supplied at a constant flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The GC oven was programmed with an initial temperature of 70 °C held for 2 min, then rose to 300 °C at the rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and held again for 7 min. The total run time was 32.0 minutes. The GC-MS interface temperature was at 280 °C. Injector and detector temperatures were set

at 250 °C. Flow control mode was set to linear velocity. 1 µL of sample was injected in a split ratio of 30:0. The Mass Spectrometer was operated with a scan range of 40-800 Da. Suspected pesticide compounds were identified by comparing their retention times in sample chromatograms to those of the corresponding pure analytical standards, along with data from an established compound library. The quantities of detected compounds were expressed as relative area percentages, as calculated by the system integrator.

Mafura (2024) pointed out that the limit of detection (LOD) of GC-MS equipment used for each pesticide was determined by running an air blank sample under the experimental conditions to obtain the detector baseline noise. A detectable ion should produce a signal that is at least three times the baseline noise. Individual pesticide LOD was estimated by serially running diluted solutions of the pesticide standard and recording the baseline noise ratio (signal-to-noise = 3).

The analysis was conducted at Afe Babalola University's Chemical Engineering Laboratory in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics such as mean, range, and standard error were used to analyse the data using SAS software version 9.2 (SAS Institute, 2005). Additionally, pesticide residue levels from the six locations were statistically evaluated using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and mean differences were determined through Duncan's Multiple Range Test at a 5% significance level.

Quality assurance procedures

Quality assurance procedures were implemented to ascertain that the analytical methods rigorously adhered to standards and specifications. Additionally, these measures helped guarantee that the results evaluated were valuable, valid, and of high standard, including the assessment of recovery rate and detection limits.

Semi-Structured Interviews

A semi-structured interview is a technique for gathering data in which questions are arranged according to a pre-defined thematic framework but are not presented in terms of sequence or wording (Price et al., 2021). An interview

was conducted for fifty-five farmers who own farms along the Oba River, where soil and water samples were taken at each of the six locations. Semi-structured interviews using oral interviews were used to gather information from the informants regarding the history of the Oba River, the kinds of pesticides they use, how long they spray them for, when they harvest their produce, and how many years they have been involved in applying pesticides. Identification of pesticide-related products and the language on pesticide package labels was also conducted during the interviews and field observations.

Results and Discussion

Soil

The analysis of pesticide residues in soil samples collected during the dry and wet seasons from various locations (Ladokun village, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Farms, Ikose Potatoes farms, Vegetable farms Iluju, and Yaku Ogbomoso (Control) revealed significant variations in pesticide concentrations across the locations, as presented in Tables 4.1 and 4.2. The concentrations of pesticide residues, expressed in mg/kg, were compared against the European Union Maximum Residue Limit (EU-MRL) for soil (0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg). In Table 4.1, Ladokun showed the highest concentrations for most pesticides, including Dichlorvos (1.52 ± 0.31 mg/kg), α -Lindane (1.35 ± 0.30 mg/kg), Atrazine (1.27 ± 0.03 mg/kg), γ -Lindane (1.19 ± 0.26 mg/kg), and Dieldrin (1.09 ± 0.25 mg/kg), ($P = 0.038$). These levels significantly exceeded the EU-MRL, indicating potential contamination risks. Other locations, such as Iluju maize farms, Iluju Irrigation Farms, Ikose Potatoes farms and Vegetable farms Iluju showed lower concentrations, generally ranging from 0.07 to 0.56 mg/kg, though still above the EU-MRL for most pesticides. The control location (Yaku Ogbomoso) consistently recorded the lowest concentrations, often at or below detection limits (0.00 ± 0.00 mg/kg for α -Lindane, Atrazine, and γ -Lindane), serving as a baseline for uncontaminated soil, however pesticides like Heptachlor, Carbofuran, and Carbaryl were absent or present in trace amounts (0.00 ± 0.00 mg/kg) at the control site, while other locations showed detectable levels. For instance, Heptachlor concentrations reached 0.56 ± 0.12 mg/kg at Iluju maize farms and 0.55 ± 0.11 mg/kg ($P = 0.40$) at Iluju Irrigation farms, indicating significant contamination at these agricultural areas.

Table 4.2 further highlighted the persistence of pesticide residues in wet seasons, with Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos, and Endosulfan showing highest concentrations at Ikose potatoes farms (0.40 ± 0.08 mg/kg, 0.43 ± 0.12 mg/kg, and 0.32 ± 0.08 ($P = 0.36$) mg/kg, respectively) and Vegetable farms Iluju (0.35 ± 0.06 mg/kg for Endosulfan). The control site again showed minimal or no detectable residues for most pesticides, reinforcing its role as a reference for uncontaminated soil. The results indicate that all tested locations, except the control, exceeded the EU-MRL for multiple pesticides, with Ladokun consistently showing the highest contamination levels. The presence of organochlorines (Dieldrin, p,p'-DDT, α -Lindane) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Malathion) at elevated levels suggests intensive pesticide use in these agricultural areas. The higher pesticide residue levels observed in the soil samples from all locations except the control site reflect intensive agricultural practices and the persistent nature of certain pesticides, such as organochlorines and organophosphates. The significantly higher concentrations at Ladokun compared to other location may be attributed to its proximity to intensive farming activities or historical pesticide use, which aligns with findings by Iwegbue et al. (2020), who reported organochlorine residues in soils from Nigerian agricultural regions due to prolonged application and slow degradation rates also Adesina et al. (2024) detected a total of eight organochlorine pesticide residues in soil samples collected in selected arable farms in the Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State. Numerous nonexclusive factors related to environmental conditions, type of crop studied, agronomic practices, and pesticide properties, as well as sampling time (e.g., date since last application), sampling strategies, and analytical methods (e.g., limits of detection and quantification), may drive the differences observed between the present results and the previous studies (Bonmatin et al., 2015; Pelosi et al., 2021). The control site's minimal residue levels confirm that non-agricultural soils are less likely to accumulate pesticide residues, consistent with studies by Akan et al. (2015), who found negligible pesticide levels in undisturbed soils. The detection of organochlorines like Dieldrin, α -Lindane, and p,p'-DDT at concentrations far exceeding the EU-MRL (0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg) raises concerns about their environmental persistence and potential bioaccumulation. Organochlorines are known for their long half-lives and resistance to degradation, as noted by Jayaraj et al. (2016), who highlighted their ability to persist

in soils for decades, posing risks to soil ecosystems and human health through food chain contamination. The presence of organophosphates such as Chlorpyrifos and Malathion, though less persistent, indicates recent pesticide application, as these compounds typically degrade faster than organochlorines (Aktar et al., 2009). However, the residue levels in this study are higher than those reported in some recent studies from other regions. For instance, Liu et al. (2025) found lower concentrations of Dichlorvos (0.01–0.05 mg/kg) in Chinese agricultural soils, suggesting differences in pesticide regulation or application practices. Similarly, Silva et al. (2019) reported Atrazine levels below 0.1 mg/kg in European soils, contrasting with the 0.05–1.27 mg/kg observed here. These discrepancies may reflect stricter regulatory frameworks in Europe compared to less regulated pesticide use in the study area. The variation in pesticide concentrations across locations (e.g. higher levels at Ladokun and Ikose Potato farm compared to

vegetable farms Iluju) suggests site-specific factors, such as type of crop cultivated, soil type, organic matter content, or irrigation practices, influencing residue retention. This is supported by Mahmoud et al. (2022), who found that soil organic matter enhances the adsorption of pesticides like Atrazine, reducing their mobility but increasing persistence. The higher residue levels at the irrigated site may also indicate leaching or runoff from nearby fields, a phenomenon described by Adimassu et al. (2019).

Water

The data from Tables 4.3 and 4.4 present the concentrations of pesticide residues in water samples collected during the dry and wet seasons across various locations along the Oba River in Ogbomoso, Nigeria, including Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms (ILJ Maize), Iluju Irrigation Scheme (ILJ IRGN), Ikose Potatoes Farms (IPF), Vegetable Farms (VFI), and Control.

Table 1. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in soil along the Oba River during the dry season.

Tabela 1. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v tleh ob reki Oba med sušnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Dichlorvos	1.52 ^a ±0.31	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.28 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.16 ^d ±0.06	0.33 ^b ±0.02	0.02 ^e ±0.00
a-Lindane	1.35 ^a ±0.30	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.23 ^c ±0.06	0.21 ^{cd} ±0.05	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Atrazine	1.27 ^a ±0.03	0.14 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.15 ^c ±0.04	0.17 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.23 ^b ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
γ-Lindane	1.19 ^a ±0.26	0.31 ^b ±0.08	0.33 ^b ±0.09	0.30 ^{cb} ±0.07	0.25 ^c ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	1.09 ^a ±0.25	0.17 ^c ±0.3	0.14 ^{dc} ±0.04	0.28 ^b ±0.06	0.15 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.64 ^a ±0.15	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.34 ^b ±0.12	0.21 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.15 ^d ±0.03	0.06 ^e ±0.00
β-HCH	0.53 ^a ±0.12	0.41 ^{ab} ±0.09	0.40 ^{ab} ±0.09	0.35 ^b ±0.07	0.27 ^c ±0.10	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.51 ^a ±0.07	0.31 ^b ±0.06	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.25 ^{bcd} ±0.05	0.28 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Aldrin	0.36 ^a ±0.06	0.07 ^d ±0.01	0.09 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.20 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.07 ^d ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Methomyl	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^a ±0.06	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.21 ^{bcd} ±0.02	0.17 ^d ±0.03	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Heptachlor epoxide	0.17 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.07	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.29 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Malathion	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.01	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.17 ^a ±0.03	0.10 ^c ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.28 ^a ±0.07	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.26 ^b ±0.04	0.18 ^{cd} ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.21 ^a ±0.3	0.16 ^b ±0.03	0.12 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.12 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Heptachlor	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.56 ^a ±0.12	0.55 ^a ±0.11	0.50 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.18 ^b ±0.03	0.04 ^c ±0.02

Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001–0.01

Locations: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Table 2. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in soil along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 2. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v tleh ob reki Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Chlorpyrifos	0.18 ^{bc} ±0.07	0.18 ^{bc} ±0.00	0.40 ^a ±0.10	0.40 ^a ±0.08	0.22 ^b ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Malathion	0.16 ^{ab} ±0.02	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.24 ^a ±0.8	0.24 ^a ±0.3	0.07 ^{ab} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.27 ^a ±0.08	0.26 ^{ab} ±0.6	0.12 ^c ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Cypermethrin	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.15 ^b ±0.08	0.12 ^c ±0.02	0.10 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.28 ^a ±0.08	0.04 ^d ±0.00
Dichlorvos	0.13 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.24 ^a ±0.04	0.43 ^a ±0.12	0.43 ^a ±0.12	0.33 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Aldrin	0.11 ^{ad} ±0.06	0.04 ^d ±0.02	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.5	0.24 ^a ±0.05	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Atrazine	0.05 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.23 ^c ±0.05	0.25 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.09 ^c ±0.02
Endosulfan	0.04 ^{cde} ±0.01	0.06 ^{de} ±0.02	0.31 ^b ±0.08	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.35 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Heptachlor	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.03 ^{bc} ±0.001	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.27 ^a ±0.10	0.06 ^b ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Phosphoric acid	0.03 ^c ±0.02	0.09 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.19 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.20 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.03 ^{cd} ±0.01	0.17 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.14 ^{bcf} ±0.06	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	0.02 ^{de} ±0.01	0.09 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.08 ^e ±0.002	0.07 ^{ef} ±0.03	0.03 ^{ef} ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
γ-Lindane	0.01 ^{de} ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorthiophos	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.04 ^{de} ±0.02	0.25 ^{ade} ±0.04	0.24 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.24 ^{abcd} ±0.0	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.008	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Chlordan	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.006	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Prothiofos	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
a-Lindane	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.13 ^{cdef} ±0.6	0.15 ^{cdef} ±0.05	0.07 ^{def} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.17 ^a ±0.04	0.17 ^a ±0.05	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.05 ^c ±0.01

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001- 0.01

Locations: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Iluju (VFI), and a control site (Yaku Ogbomoso). In Table 4.3, during the dry season, heptachlor had the highest concentration at Ladokun (0.64 ± 0.31 mg/kg), significantly higher than the control (0.04 ± 0.01 mg/kg) ($P = 0.46$). β -HCH concentrations ranged from 0.33 ± 0.09 mg/kg (VFI) to 0.50 ± 0.10 mg/kg (ILJ IRGN), with the control showing no detectable residues. Other pesticides, such as γ -Lindane, Dichlorvos, Chlorpyrifos, and Carbaryl, showed concentrations significantly above the control across most locations, with values ranging from 0.15 ± 0.03 mg/kg (Malathion at VFI) to 0.33 ± 0.09 mg/kg (γ -Lindane at Ladokun and Iluju Irrigation Scheme). Table 4.4, during wet season Heptachlor concentrations peaked at Ladokun (2.13 ± 0.42 mg/kg),

significantly higher than other locations, where it was often undetectable, Carbofuran showed a high concentration at Ikose Potatoes farms (2.13 ± 0.32 mg/kg), while Chlordan and p,p'-DDT were notably high at Iluju Maize farms (1.48 ± 0.06 mg/kg and 1.30 ± 0.14 mg/kg, ($P = 0.30$) respectively). Atrazine and Dieldrin also showed higher levels, with maximum concentrations of 0.36 ± 0.08 mg/kg (ILJ Maize) and 1.11 ± 0.16 mg/kg (IPF), respectively. These findings are in alignment with several studies that have investigated the residue of pesticides in water, for instance, Ng et al. 2023; Ngin et al. 2024). Ngin et al. (2024) detected a total of 56 out of the 64 pesticides in the 96 surface-water samples, with average concentrations for individual pesticides

ranging from 0.05 to 1300 ng/L. Ng et al. (2023) focused on 2362 contaminants, and 586 pesticides were detected up to a maximum concentration of 1171 ng/L in the Danube River Basin, Europe's second largest river basin, also pesticide concentrations found in this present study were similar to those found by Awe et al. (2022) in a study conducted in Atakumosa West Local Government, Osun State. In their study, they found pesticide residues in the water, including dimethoate, pirimiphos-methyl, prothiofos, pyrazophos, dementon-s-methyl, profenofos, malathion, and omethoate, with amounts ranging from 0.06 to 6.11 mg/L. The results indicate widespread pesticide contamination in water samples from agricultural sites in Ogbomoso, with concentrations consistently exceeding the EU-MRL for soil (0.001-0.01 mg/kg). This suggests potential environmental and health risks, as water is a critical medium for pesticide transport and human exposure. Heptachlor, a persistent organochlorine pesticide, showed particularly high levels

at Ladokun, consistent with its historical use and persistence in the environment (Olisah et al., 2020). Similarly, Higher levels of Carbofuran and Dieldrin at Ikose Potatoes farm and Iluju Maize farms align with their intensive use in agriculture, as noted in studies on pesticide residues in African water systems (Olisah et al., 2020). The absence or low levels of residues at the control site (Yaku Ogbomoso) confirm that agricultural activities are the primary source of contamination. However, recent studies report similar trends. For instance, Olisah (2020) found organochlorine residues in Ghanaian water bodies exceeding international standards, attributing this to agricultural runoff. Akan et al. (2015) reported high levels of DDT and Lindane in Nigerian water systems, corroborating the elevated p,p'-DDT and γ -Lindane concentrations observed here. The high variability in residue levels across locations may reflect differences in pesticide application practices, soil types, or irrigation methods, as suggested by Iniaghe et al. (2022).

Table 3. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the dry season.

Tabela 3. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med sušnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Heptachlor	0.64 ^a ±0.31	0.56 ^{ab} ±0.12	0.55 ^b ±0.8	0.49 ^{bc} ±0.011	0.16 ^c ±0.04	0.04 ^d ±0.01
β -HCH	0.43 ^b ±0.09	0.45 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.50 ^a ±0.10	0.37 ^b ±0.07	0.33 ^{bc} ±0.09	0.00 ^d ±0.00
γ -Lindane	0.33 ^a ±0.09	0.32 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.33 ^a ±0.09	0.30 ^b ±0.07	0.25 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.04 ^c ±0.02
Dichlorvos	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.26 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.16 ^b ±0.03	0.30 ^a ±0.05	0.01 ^c ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.31 ^a ±0.09	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.25 ^c ±0.05	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Heptachlor epoxide	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.29 ^a ±0.06	0.16 ^{cd} ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.27 ^b ±0.07	0.28 ^a ±0.08	0.22 ^c ±0.00	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.08 ^d ±0.04
Dieldrin	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.26 ^a ±0.06	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.21 ^b ±0.05	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.08 ^c ±0.04
α -Lindane	0.20 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.21 ^b ±0.08	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.18 ^b ±0.05	0.25 ^a ±0.06	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.15 ^c ±0.05	0.05 ^d ±0.01
Malathion	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.2	0.17 ^a ±0.03	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.21 ^a ±0.05	0.16 ^b ±0.04	0.12 ^c ±0.05	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Aldrin	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.07 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.7	0.07 ^c ±0.04	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Atrazine	0.11 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.15 ^b ±0.05	0.13 ^b ±0.05	0.18 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.22 ^a ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001-0.01

Locations: L1: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Table 4. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 4. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Heptachlor	2.13 ^a ±0.42	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.22 ^b ±0.06	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.17 ^c ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Endosulfan	0.19 ^b ±0.04	0.01 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.22 ^a ±0.07	0.10 ^c ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Atrazine	0.17 ^b ±0.04	0.36 ^a ±0.08	0.08 ^c ±0.06	0.02 ^d ±0.01	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.01 ^e ±0.00
Dichlorvos	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.04 ^e ±0.02	0.02 ^c ±0.01	0.24 ^b ±0.08	0.34 ^a ±0.07	0.02 ^b ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.10 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.01 ^d ±0.00	0.13 ^a ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	0.10 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.07 ^c ±0.03	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.02	1.11 ^a ±0.16	0.21 ^b ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.08 ^b ±0.02	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.07 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.21 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Malathion	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.45 ^a ±0.10	0.24 ^b ±0.06	0.05 ^c ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Aldrin	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.01	1.42 ^a ±0.14	1.28 ^{ab} ±0.21	0.16 ^b ±0.07	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
a-Lindane	0.04 ^d ±0.02	1.28 ^a ±0.16	0.03 ^c ±0.00	0.83 ^b ±0.20	0.14 ^c ±0.04	0.00 ^a ±0.00
Cypermethrin	0.02 ^a ±0.01	0.00 ^b ±0.00	0.01 ^{ab} ±0.00	0.01 ^b ±0.00	0.01 ^b ±0.00	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Chlorthiophos	0.02 ^b ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.02 ^c ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.07 ^a ±0.02	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.02 ^{bc} ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.06 ^b ±0.02	2.13 ^a ±0.32	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.22 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.11 ^b ±0.05	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Chlordan	0.00 ^d ±0.00	1.48 ^a ±0.06	0.53 ^b ±0.09	0.04 ^c ±0.01	0.07 ^c ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.00 ^d ±0.00	1.30 ^a ±0.14	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.04 ^{bc} ±0.01	0.11 ^b ±0.06	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.02
β-HCH	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.09 ^a ±0.04	0.02 ^c ±0.00	0.04 ^b ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^c ±0.00

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001- 0.01

Locations: L1: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Soil and Water

There are higher concentrations of pesticides in water than in soil. The reduced quantity of pesticides found in the soil aligns with the findings of Manjarres-López et al. (2021), who reported that over fifty per cent of the sampled pesticides were undetected in the soil. The impact of soil properties on the remaining levels of pesticide is anticipated, given that the adsorption process by both organic and inorganic soil components may increase the longevity of these substances. Indeed, several studies in the literature indicate the impact of organic matter and clay content on the adsorption, degradation, and persistence of certain compounds found in soils (Marín-Benito et al., 2017; Sadegh et al., 2017). The significant quantity of compounds

identified in certain water samples may be attributed to the application of various pesticides employed for managing pests in crops or vineyards near water sources, or possibly due to the reduced distance between the fields and the water source (Schreiner et al., 2016). The elevated levels of these compounds found in water samples indicate that their presence may be attributed to their consistent use across various seasons. Point-source contamination may also account for these elevated concentrations, as suggested by other researchers (Bagheri et al., 2023).

Based on the total sum of average concentrations of all pesticides for both seasons. The pesticides with the highest concentrations in both water and soil samples are heptachlor, Dichlorvos, aldrin, atrazine, and carbofuran, which have values of 4.96, 4.13, 3.56, 3.15, and 3.03 mg/kg,

respectively. This conclusion suggests that farmers in the area frequently utilise these chemical compounds, which can be inferred from the types of crops cultivated in the region (Demi et al., 2021). However, the study reveals that insect pests most frequently target vegetables, maize, cowpeas, and millet as their dominant crops. In addition to this, the farmers in this study area utilise herbicides for weed control, which have been the primary source of the observed residues in both soil and water (Nath et al., 2024).

There are more organochlorines (11) than other chemical groups in the present study. This aligns with the findings of Zhang et al. (2022), who observed several residual levels of organochlorine in samples collected during the rainy season. Increased drainage and disturbances in the water column during rainfall may cause this phenomenon. Organochlorine pesticides exhibit prolonged residual effects and remain in the environment for extended durations while maintaining their toxicity (Ren et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025; Faraj et al., 2024). Meanwhile, the concentration of organophosphate

compound residues in soil samples was consistently higher than that in water samples, aligning with the findings of Awe et al. (2022). This result is expected because the pesticides are applied directly to the crops and soil, so their levels are likely to decrease due to their tendency to evaporate before they wash into nearby water sources.

Figure 2 revealed the comparison between the two major class of pesticides used in the study area was presented in the bar chart. The result shows that the highest percentage of pesticides used in the study area is Insecticides, which constitute 94% percent followed by Herbicides, which had 6%. This indicates that the use of insecticides to control the insect pests against the attack on Agricultural commodities in the study area is very common, and the rate of using herbicides is also high, and this might be due to frequent control of weeds, especially during the rainy season. This study is in line with Rousis et al. (2017), who reported that insecticides are the major pesticide used in agriculture and also in the household to control insects.

Figure 2. Level of major pesticide detected in soil samples from the study area.

Slika 2. Raven glavnih pesticidov, ugotovljena v vzorcih tal iz območja študije.

Environmental risk assessment

Most of the concentration of the pesticides found in the present study exceeded the maximum residue levels (MRLs) set for pesticides in water, 0.1 mg/kg (Olawale et al., 2022). The least concentration of each individual pesticide found was 0.01 mg/kg. This finding implies that environmentalists and scientists should conduct public education about pesticides for rural farmers who have little knowledge about the MRLs for pesticides. However, the total pesticide concentration could not be considered for evaluating the level of soil contamination because there is no EU legislation establishing thresholds or quality standards for total or individual pesticide residues in the soil, even though this subject should be addressed in the characterisation of overall soil quality (Silva et al., 2019).

Semi-structured interviews

All the respondents who were surveyed reported using pesticides. However, due to either inadequate labelling or other factors, none of them were informed about the active chemicals present in the pesticide products they utilised. The analysis successfully identified unique products containing the same active ingredients through a visual examination of the pesticides used by the inter-

viewed farmers and the pesticide containers observed at the sampling locations. The farmers report the practice of frequently mixing various pesticide products in spray tanks and applying this combination without considering the specific types of pesticides involved. This finding is consistent with previous investigations that evaluated the actual circumstances of pesticide application among Cambodian farmers in rural regions (Matsukawa et al., 2016). Information regarding the appropriate amounts to be used and the timing between application and harvest was obtained from neighbours and pesticide vendors. Pesticides are utilised to control diseases and prevent pests from damaging crops, as outlined in the description. It was found that a significant portion of farmers, specifically two-thirds, lack awareness regarding the application of pesticides. This could be the situation, as numerous individuals approach circumstances through the lens of their personal experiences and may lack knowledge regarding the proper application of pesticides. While the extensive experience of farmers is essential for managing pesticides, a professional understanding is required for the safe handling of these substances. A number of the farmers surveyed indicated that they resort to using an alternative pesticide the following day if the initial application fails to prevent insect damage to their crops, which may contribute to the accumulation of pesticides in the environment.

Table 5. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 5. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticide	Types	
	Type of the Pesticide	Trade Name
Profenofos at 40% + Cypermethrin at 4%	Insecticide	Sharp Shooter, Rocket Termite Killer, Ironforce.
Captan	Fungicide	Tepuca. Agrox, Captal, Captec, Captol, Captonex, Clomitane, Merpan, Meteoro
Dichlorvos	Insecticide	DD force, Daksh, DDVP, Snipper, Dedevap, Nogos, Task, No pest, crush
Diquat Chloride	Herbicide	FieldKlear, Reglone, Reward, Aquacide, Weedtrine-D, Dextrone, and Preeglone
Cypermethrin	Insecticide	CypeForce, Cyper-DiForce, and Sharp Shooter
Emamectin Benzoate	Insecticide	Caterpillar Force, allakat, DPRO, FAMEN B, Lepto
Lambda-Cyhalothrin	Insecticide	Lara Force, Karate
Mancozeb	Fungicide	Z-Force fungicide, Quintozen, Zebshi
Abamectin	Antiparasitic agent	Abamet, Punch, Trustil
Profenofos	Insecticide	Dominator. Sharp Shooter, Dominator, and DD Force
Atrazine	Insecticide	Atraforce, AtranexMazine Atraz

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Conclusion

This study provides critical insights into the extent of pesticide contamination in soil and water along the Oba River in Ogbomoso, Nigeria, highlighting the pervasive impact of agricultural practices on environmental quality. The analysis of 36 soil and 36 surface water samples collected during the dry and wet seasons from six locations revealed significant pesticide residues, with concentrations frequently exceeding the European Union Maximum Residue Limits (EU-MRL) of 0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg for soil and 0.1 mg/kg for water. Organochlorines (Heptachlor, Dieldrin, α -Lindane, p,p'-DDT) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos) were the dominant contaminants, with Ladokun and Ikose Potatoes Farms exhibiting the highest concentrations, particularly during the wet season. The control site (Yaku Village) consistently showed minimal or no detectable residues, showing the role of intensive agricultural activities as the primary source of contamination. Seasonal variations were evident, with higher pesticide levels in both soil and water during the wet season, likely due to increased application rates and runoff facilitated by heavy rainfall. The semi-structured interviews with 55 farmers revealed widespread pesticide use, often without adequate knowledge of active ingredients, application rates, or safety protocols, contributing to environmental accumulation. The elevated pesticide levels in water compared to soil suggest significant transport via runoff, posing risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health through potential food chain contamination. It is essential to adopt sustainable agricultural practices that encompass conservation tillage, ecological ditches, and biological weed removal. Additionally, educating farmers about the use of pesticides during land clearing and their effects on water bodies and crops is crucial. Natural pesticides, often referred

to as biopesticides, are strongly advocated as a viable alternative to synthetic pesticides, particularly in the context of ensuring food security and promoting environmental sustainability. Additional investigations are necessary to encompass a broader range of local government areas and agricultural settlements within the state. It is essential for the government to contemplate the allocation of funds for studies of this nature, as the data gathered can significantly contribute to the development and refinement of policies.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, O.J. and O.A.; methodology, T.P. and O.A.; software, E.O. and K.A.; validation, O.J. and O.A.; formal analysis, O.J. and O.A.; investigation, T.P.; resources, O.A.; data curation, O.J. and E.O.; writing original draft preparation, O.J.; writing review and editing, O.J. and O.A.; visualization, T.P. and K.A.; supervision, O.A. and T.P.; project administration, O.A. and O.J.; funding acquisition, O.J. and O.A. We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship

Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Research data tables were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17614950>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

References

- Abegunrin, T. P., Awe, G. O., & Adejumbi, M. A. (2020). Water quality status of three different rivers for Fadama-oriented irrigated agriculture in Ogbomoso, Southwest Nigeria. *Emerging Issues in Science and Technology* (Vol. 3, pp. 77–93).
- Adesida, S. O., & Alimba, C. G. (2025). Systematic literature review of radionuclides, heavy metals, and organochlorine pesticides in Nigerian food crops: Assessment of carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health risk. *Environmental Analysis Health and Toxicology*, 40(2), e2025012. <https://doi.org/10.5620/eaht.2025012>
- Adesina, G. O., Adelasoye, K. A., Akinjide, B. I., Abiola, S. O., & Adeniji, A. A. (2024). Assessment of pesticide residues in selected arable farmlands in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Agricultural Science & Technology*, 16(2), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.15547/ast.2024.02.020>
- Adimassu, Z., Alemu, G., & Tamene, L. (2019). Effects of tillage and crop residue management on runoff, soil loss, and crop yield in the humid highlands of Ethiopia. *Agricultural Systems*, 168, 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2018.10.007>
- Aktar, M. W., Sengupta, D., & Chowdhury, A. (2009). Degradation dynamics of organophosphate pesticides in the environment. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 147(1–3), 419–430. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-008-0223-4>

- Awe, Y. T., Sangodoyin, A. Y., & Ogundiran, M. B. (2022). Assessment of organophosphate pesticide residues in environmental media of Araromi farm settlement, Osun State, Nigeria. *Environmental Analysis Health and Toxicology*, 37(4), e2022035. <https://doi.org/10.5620/eaht.2022035>
- Bagheri, A., Emami, N., & Damalas, C. A. (2023). Monitoring point-source pollution by pesticide use: An analysis of farmers' environmental behavior in waste disposal. *Environment, Development & Sustainability*, 25, 6711–6726. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02326-2>
- Bonmatin, J.-M., Giorio, C., Girolami, V., Goulson, D., Kreuzweiser, D. P., Krupke, C., ... Tapparo, A. (2015). Environmental fate and exposure; neonicotinoids and fipronil. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 22, 35–67. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-014-3332-7>
- Commelin, M. C., Baartman, J. E. M., Zomer, P., Riksen, M. J. P. M., & Geissen, V. (2022). Pesticides are substantially transported in particulate phase, driven by land use, rainfall event and pesticide characteristics—a runoff and erosion study in a small agricultural catchment. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 830589. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.830589>
- Corru, S. (2024). Integrating biodiversity concerns in sustainability strategy: A case study at Schneider Electric. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9174197> (Accessed October 2025)
- Demi, S. M., & Sicchia, S. R. (2021). Agrochemicals use practices and health challenges of smallholder farmers in Ghana. *Environmental Health Insights*, 15, 11786302211043033. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11786302211043033>
- Faraj, T. K., El-Saeid, M. H., Najim, M. M. M., & Chieb, M. (2024). The impact of pesticide residues on soil health for sustainable vegetable production in arid areas. *Separations*, 11(2), 46. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations11020046>
- García-Espinal, M. A., Pérez-Sánchez, M., Sánchez-Romero, F. J., & López-Jiménez, P. A. (2024). Irrigation distribution network design parameters and their influence on sustainability management. *Water*, 16(8), 1131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16081131>
- Han, Y., Tian, Y., Li, Q., Yao, T., Yao, J., Zhang, Z., & Wu, L. (2025). Advances in detection technologies for pesticide residues and heavy metals in rice: A comprehensive review of spectroscopy, chromatography, and biosensors. *Foods*, 14(6), 1070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14061070>
- Iniaqhe, P. O., & Kpomah, E. D. (2022). Polychlorinated biphenyl (PCBs) in water and sediments along the Udu River, Niger Delta, Nigeria: Concentration, distribution and risk assessment. *Journal of Environmental Exposure Assessment*, 1, Article 20A. <https://doi.org/10.20517/jeea.2022.19>
- Iqbal, J., Ali, S., Zahid, A., Fatima, A., Zahra, A., Siddiqi, K., & Ahmad, M. (2025). Agriculture, pesticide pollution, and climate change: Interconnected challenges. In M. B. E. et al. (Eds.), *Food systems and biodiversity in the context of environmental and climate risks: Dynamics and evolving solutions* (pp. 491–517). Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-89167-0_18
- Iqbal, K., Sohail, M., Rind, K. H., & Habib, S. S. (2025). Agrochemical contamination and fish health: Eco-toxicological impacts and mitigation strategies. *Chemistry and Ecology*, 41(7), 959–993. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02757540.2025.2508993>
- Iwegbue, C. M. A., Ossai, C. J., Ogwu, I. F., Olisah, C., Ujam, O. T., Nwajeri, G. E., & Martincigh, B. S. (2024). Organochlorine pesticide contamination of soils and dust from an urban environment in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. *Science of the Total Environment*, 938, 172959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172959>
- Jayaraj, R., Megha, P., & Sreedev, P. (2016). Organochlorine pesticides, their toxic effects on living organisms and their fate in the environment. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology*, 9(3–4), 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1515/intox-2016-0012>
- Lei, W., Guo, J., Liang, X., Wang, H., Qi, W., Mao, Z., & He, S. (2025). Occurrence characteristics and environmental fate of neonicotinoid insecticides in mountain agricultural soils and river waters. *Environmental Pollution*, 127269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.127269>
- Liu, Y., Wang, Z., Liu, M., Zhang, T., Liu, S., & Lu, K. (2025). Characterization, sources and risk assessment of organochlorine and organophosphorus pesticides and PAHs in agricultural soils from Jilin Province, Northeast China. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment*, 39, 1741–1755. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-025-02944-y>
- Mahmoud, A. F., El-Naggar, A., & Abdel-Wahab, M. (2022). Soil organic matter and pesticide retention in agricultural fields. *Soil Use and Management*, 38(2), 789–801.
- Manjarres-López, D. P., Andrades, M. S., Sánchez-González, S., Rodríguez-Cruz, M. S., Sánchez-Martín, M. J., & Herrero-Hernández, E. (2021). Assessment of pesticide residues in waters and soils of a vineyard region and its temporal evolution. *Environmental Pollution*, 284, Article 117463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117463>
- Marín-Benito, J. M., Herrero-Hernández, E., Rodríguez-Cruz, M. S., Arienzo, M., & Sánchez-Martín, M. J. (2017). Study of processes influencing bioavailability of pesticides in wood-soil systems: Effect of different factors. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 139, 454–462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.02.012>
- Matsukawa, M., Ito, K., Kawakita, K., & Tanaka, T. (2016). Current status of pesticide use among rice farmers in Cambodia. *Applied Entomology and Zoology*, 51(4), 571–579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13355-016-0432-5>
- Nath, C. P., Singh, R. G., Choudhary, V. K., Datta, D., Nandan, R., & Singh, S. S. (2024). Challenges and alternatives of herbicide-based weed management. *Agronomy*, 14(1), 126. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14010126>
- Ng, K., Alygizakis, N., Nika, M. C., Galani, A., Oswald, P., Oswaldova, M., ... Slobodnik, J. (2023). Wide-scope target screening characterization of legacy and emerging contaminants in the Danube River Basin by liquid and gas chromatography coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry. *Water Research*, 230, Article 119539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119539>
- Ngin, P., Haglund, P., Proum, S., & Fick, J. (2024). Pesticide screening of surface water and soil along the Mekong River in Cambodia. *Science of the Total Environment*, 912, Article 169312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169312>
- Ogungbesan, G. O., & Sanni, K. A. (2022). Hydrochemistry and quality assessment of surface water in Oba Dam, Ogbomoso, Southwestern Nigeria. *LAUTECH Journal of Civil and Environmental Studies*, 8(1), 105–113.
- Olawale, O., Abah, M. A., Grace, O. T., Brave, Y. F., Okoli, E. C., & Habibu, B. (2022). Risk assessment of pesticide residues in soil samples along River Gongola, Adamawa State. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 3(8), 7421–7428.

- Olisah, C., Okoh, O. O., & Okoh, A. I. (2020). Occurrence of organochlorine pesticide residues in biological and environmental matrices in Africa: A two-decade review. *Heliyon*, 6(3), e03518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03518>
- Osabohien, R. (2024). Soil technology and post-harvest losses in Nigeria. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*, 14(3), 570–586. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JADEE-06-2023-0103>
- Pelosi, C., Bertrand, C., Daniele, G., Coeurdassier, M., Benoit, P., Nélieu, S., ... Fritsch, C. (2021). Residues of currently used pesticides in soils and earthworms: A silent threat? *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 305, 107167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.107167>
- Ren, Y., Wang, G., Bai, X., Su, Y., Zhang, Z., & Han, J. (2024). Research progress on remediation of organochlorine pesticide contamination in soil. *Environmental Geochemistry and Health*, 46(1), 25–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-023-01579-9>
- Rousis, N. I., Bade, R., Bijlsma, L., Zuccato, E., Sancho, J. V., Hernandez, F., & Castiglioni, S. (2017). Monitoring a large number of pesticides and transformation products in water samples from Spain and Italy. *Environmental Research*, 156, 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.03.010>
- Schreiner, V. C., Szöcs, E., Bhowmik, A. K., Vijver, M. G., & Schäfer, R. B. (2016). Pesticide mixtures in streams of several European countries and the USA. *Science of the Total Environment*, 573, 680–689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.08.146>
- Shah, F., & Wu, W. (2019). Soil and crop management strategies to ensure higher crop productivity within sustainable environments. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1485. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11051485>
- Silva, V., Mol, H. G. J., Zomer, P., Tienstra, M., Ritsema, C. J., & Geissen, V. (2019). Pesticide residues in European agricultural soils: A hidden reality unfolded. *Science of the Total Environment*, 653, 1532–1545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.441>
- Wang, K., Jiao, B., Almvik, M., Dong, F., Pan, X., Wu, X., ... Zheng, Y. (2023). Development of a quantitative screening method for 100 pesticides in plant-derived foods using comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *ACS Agricultural Science & Technology*, 3(9), 771–784. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsagscitech.3c00072>
- Zhang, J., Sun, W., Shi, C., Li, W., Liu, A., Guo, J., ... Qu, C. (2023). Investigation of organochlorine pesticides in the Wang Lake Wetland, China: Implications for environmental processes and risks. *Science of the Total Environment*, 898, 165450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165450>

Original Research

Myths in biology: students' opinion towards vaccination, climate change, genetically modified organisms and evolution

Katja Bukovnik^{1*}, Gregor Torkar¹

Abstract

In scientific discourse, the term "myth" is used to describe widespread and demonstrably false beliefs that contradict the current scientific consensus. Due to insufficient biological knowledge and conceptual understanding, various biological myths can arise and persist in the information overload, ultimately influencing public opinion and societal dynamics. To effectively combat and prevent biological myths, it is essential to first understand their origin. The aim of this study was to investigate the opinions of Slovenian secondary school students towards certain biological myths and to explore the relationship between these opinions and students' biological and scientific knowledge, self-assessment of their biological competence, and their interest in science subjects. The study focused on four biologically and socially significant areas included in the primary school curricula: vaccinations, climate change, genetically modified organisms, and evolution. Students with lower self-assessed biological knowledge or with lower grades in biology in lower secondary school were statistically significantly more likely to believe in myths related to climate change and evolution. Interest in science subjects was negatively correlated with scepticism about climate change. The national biology curricula show that climate change and evolution are among the most frequently covered topics, which may explain the associations between biological knowledge and myths. Students attending upper secondary schools with a limited number of science lessons, especially those in vocational education, were more prone to biological myths. The study highlights the critical role of formal biology education and interest in science in curbing the prevalence of biological myths. Given the rapid and complex advances in the natural sciences and their profound impact on daily life and societal development, there is an increasing potential for the emergence of biological myths. It is therefore crucial to ensure high-quality biological education at all levels of schooling.

Keywords

myth, ideas, vaccination, genetically modified organisms, climate change, evolution

¹ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Education

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: Bukovnik.katja@gmail.com

Citation: Bukovnik, K., Torkar, G. (2025). Myths in biology: students' opinion towards vaccination, climate change, genetically modified organisms and evolution. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 30.08.2025 / **Accepted:** 03.12.2025 / **Published:** 05.12.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.23894>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Miti v biologiji: mnenja dijakov do cepljenja, podnebnih sprememb, gensko spremenjenih organizmov in evolucije

Izvleček

V znanosti izraz »mit« uporabljamo za označevanje razširjenih in nesporno napačnih prepričanj, ki nasprotujejo trenutno veljavni znanosti. Zaradi pomanjkljivega biološkega znanja in razumevanja lahko v poplavi vseh informacij nastajajo in obstojijo različni miti v biologiji, ki med drugim vplivajo tudi na družbeno dogajanje. Za uspešno odpravljanje in preprečevanje mitov v biologiji je sprva potrebno njihovo podrobnejše razumevanje. V raziskavi smo želeli ugotoviti, kakšna so mnenja slovenskih dijakov (N=376) do določenih mitov v biologiji ter povezave le teh z njihovim znanjem pri biologiji in naravoslovnih predmetih, lastno oceno biološkega znanja in zanimanjem za naravoslovne predmete. V raziskavi smo se osredotočili na štiri biološka področja, zastopana v učnih načrtih osnovnih šol, ki so družbeno pomembna - cepljenje, podnebne spremembe, gensko spremenjeni organizmi in evolucija. Dijaki, ki nižje ocenjujejo svoje znanje biologije ali so bili slabše ocenjeni pri predmetu biologija v osnovni šoli, statistično pomembno bolj verjamejo v mite o podnebnih spremembah in evoluciji. Zanimanje za naravoslovne predmete je v statistično pomembni negativni povezavi z nezaupanjem v podnebne spremembe. Pregled učnih načrtov za osnovno šolo v Sloveniji je potrdil, da sta podnebne spremembe in evolucija tudi zastopani z največ učnimi cilji med izpostavljenimi področji, kar bi lahko bil razlog za ugotovljene povezave med biološkim znanjem in miti. V srednjih šolah z manjšim obsegom ur naravoslovnih predmetov so dijaki bolj dovzetni za mite v biologiji, še posebej dijaki v vocational education. Raziskava je pokazala, da šolsko biološko znanje in zanimanje za naravoslovne predmete pomembno pri odpravljanju mitov v biologiji. Napredek v naravoslovnih znanosti je hiter in kompleksen ter pomembno vpliva na naš vsakdan in družbene spremembe. Hiter napredek in kompleksnost pa tudi povečuje možnosti pojava mitov v biologiji, zato je potrebno zagotavljati kakovostno biološko izobraževanje na vseh ravneh šolanja.

Ključne besede

mit, predstave, cepljenje, gensko spremenjeni organizme, podnebne spremembe, evolucija

Introduction

The term myth, derived from the Greek word for "story" or "narrative," is frequently used in scientific discourse to denote beliefs that contradict established scientific knowledge. Researchers (e.g., Sismondo, 1996; McComas, 2002) often use the term to describe widely held but demonstrably false ideas. In many cases, myths also reflect broader ideological or cultural worldviews (Douglas, 2003).

The primary objective of science is to understand natural phenomena through explanation, prediction, and intervention. This understanding is achieved through scientific explanations, theories, and models. Due to the inherent complexity of natural systems, scientific models necessarily involve simplifications and assumptions. These simplifications help manage complexity, facilitate understanding, and allow for the application of theoretical knowledge. While all

scientific explanations are subject to some degree of uncertainty, this does not render them invalid or untrustworthy. Rather, uncertainty is an inherent feature of scientific inquiry, stemming from the complexity of natural systems and human cognitive limitations. Scientific models are based on idealisations and approximations, while humans often operate with incomplete information about both past and present phenomena (Kampourakis & McCain, 2020).

Research has shown that the application of biological knowledge in real-world contexts is deeply intertwined with social, cultural, economic, and ethical factors (Forbes & Davis, 2008). Socio-scientific issues (SSIs) are characterised by open-endedness, ethical and moral ambiguity, and the possibility of multiple legitimate solutions (Grace & Ratcliffe, 2003). Students often struggle to connect the biological knowledge acquired in the classroom to real-life contexts, resulting in difficulties applying their understand-

ing to everyday challenges (Tsaparlis et al., 2013). Some studies suggest that the breadth of content in science curricula can lead students to focus primarily on memorisation, at the expense of conceptual understanding and critical thinking (Hofstein et al., 2011).

To address these challenges, science education has increasingly embraced the use of SSIs—complex societal questions rooted in scientific knowledge, typically interdisciplinary in nature, and involving ethical and social dilemmas (Kolstø, 2001; Zeidler, 2014). These issues mirror the real-world challenges faced by industrialised societies in the development and application of science and technology (Levinson, 2006). Furthermore, SSIs frequently demand moral reasoning about ethical dilemmas, aspects often underrepresented in traditional science education (Morris, 2014; Tsai, 2018). Integrating SSIs into science instruction can help students better understand contemporary scientific controversies and foster their scientific reasoning skills (Zeidler & Sadler, 2023).

Although public trust in science remains relatively high in many countries, a growing trend of scientific scepticism has been observed, particularly regarding climate change, genetic modification, and vaccination (Rutjens et al., 2018). Such scepticism, often unwarranted, can have serious consequences for public health, economic stability, and environmental sustainability (Thangaraju & Venkatesan, 2019; Bavel et al., 2020). Science scepticism is heterogeneous in nature; its extent varies across scientific domains and among ideological groups (Rutjens & Van Der Lee, 2020).

One significant contributor to science scepticism across multiple domains is the proliferation of conspiracy theories (Rutjens et al., 2021). These theories often claim to reveal hidden truths deliberately obscured by powerful elites and offer seemingly coherent explanations for complex or poorly understood events (Sullivan, 2009). For individuals experiencing a lack of control or uncertainty, conspiracy theories can provide a cognitive framework that helps them reject official narratives and regain a sense of understanding (Douglas et al., 2017). This phenomenon is particularly pronounced when scientific findings challenge individuals' core beliefs or ideological frameworks. Hence, the root of science denial often lies not in the science itself, but in what science symbolises within broader public and political discourse (Rutjens & Bradt, 2018). Many science sceptics perceive science as a threat to their values, beliefs, or worldviews (Rutjens et al., 2021).

In today's information-saturated environment, the rapid

spread of both accurate and inaccurate content via the internet, and especially through social media, has led to widespread confusion and mistrust. Exposure to a large volume of conflicting information, especially when accompanied by the intentional or unintentional spread of misinformation, can increase public scepticism and uncertainty (Jerome et al., 2024).

Aim of the Study

This study aims to investigate whether students' biological knowledge and interest in science are associated with their opinions toward socially relevant biological myths in four key domains: vaccination, climate change, genetically modified organisms (GMOs), and evolution. These areas have been identified in the literature about Slovene students as prone to misconceptions and scientific scepticism (e.g., Ambrožič Dolinšek & Šorgo, 2009, 2011; Šorgo et al., 2014; Majer et al., 2019; Strgar & Möller, 2024; Torkar & Šorgo, 2020; Špernjak et al., 2023). These domains are represented to varying degrees in the Slovenian national primary school curriculum. Specifically, eight learning objectives pertain to viruses and vaccination, thirteen to climate change, four to genetic modification, and eighteen to evolution. Based on this distribution, we hypothesise that students' opinions toward these topics may differ depending on the extent to which each topic is addressed during primary and lower secondary education (Primary School Programme. Getting to know the environment. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Science and Technology. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Science. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Biology. Curriculum, 2011)

Research Questions

After completing primary education, students in Slovenia enrol in various types of secondary schools, which differ in terms of duration, academic rigour, curriculum content and the extent of science education. In order to obtain a representative sample of Slovenian secondary school students, this study included first-year students from four types of secondary education programs as defined in the Slovenian education system: lower vocational schools, vocational secondary schools, technical secondary schools, and general secondary (Gymnasia programmes) (Eurydice, 2025). By selecting different types of secondary schools, we wanted to gain the best possible insight into

the population of students attending secondary education in Slovenia. The following research questions were posed:

1. What are students' opinions towards vaccination, climate change, genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and evolution?
2. What is the relationship between students' knowledge of biology and science acquired in primary school, their self-assessed knowledge of biology, their interest in science subjects and their opinions towards vaccinations, climate change, GMOs and evolution?
3. Are there statistically significant differences in the above variables among students in different secondary education programs?

Materials and methods

Sample Description

A purposive sample of first-grade students from a secondary school in the region of Gorenjska (northern Slovenia) was used for this study. The sample included students from four out of sixteen secondary schools in the region. Participants were enrolled in general secondary schools ($n = 175$), technical secondary schools ($n = 123$), vocational secondary schools ($n = 45$) and lower vocational schools ($n = 33$). A total of 376 students took part in the study, including 171 male students, 185 female students and 20 students who did not specify their gender. In Slovenia, in the same academic year, a total of 24,379 students were enrolled in the first year of secondary education. Of these, 726 were enrolled in lower vocational schools, 5,300 in vocational secondary schools, 10,309 in technical secondary schools, and 8,044 in general secondary schools (Statistični urad Republike Slovenije, 2025).

Data Collection

The data was collected through an anonymous and voluntary survey using a structured questionnaire. In the introductory section, students were asked to report their gender, grade level, school attended and final grades in biology, chemistry and physics in 8th and 9th grades of primary school. In the second section, students assessed their interest in science subjects compared to other subjects using a four-point forced-choice Likert scale: (1) least interested, (2) less interested, (3) more interested, and (4) much more

interested, which was used to encourage respondents to indicate a clear preference and avoid neutral responses.

Subsequently, students were then asked to express their agreement with twenty statements representing common biological myths using a five-point Likert scale: (1) strongly disagree, (2) somewhat disagree, (3) neither agree nor disagree, (4) somewhat agree and (5) strongly agree. These statements were divided into four groups, each comprising five items on the topics of vaccination, climate change, GMOs, and evolution. Twenty-one statements addressed whether participants believed in conspiracy theories. In constructing the statements on biological myths, we based our approach on previously conducted research. The statements were developed based on previous research in these four domains (e.g. Marris, 2001; Dolinšek & Šorgo, 2009; Touyz, 2013; Torkar & Šorgo, 2020; Saunders, 2022; Cook, 2025).

The same Likert scale was employed in the final section of the questionnaire in which students self-assessed their biological knowledge across eight different biological domains covered in primary school (knowledge of DNA structure, microbiology, human anatomy, evolution, photosynthesis and cellular respiration, plants, animals). Each domain was represented by two statements. In formulating the statements, we based them on the research by Bahar et al. (1999) and the national curriculum guidelines for science in grades 6 and 7 (Primary School Programme. Science. Curriculum, 2011) and for biology in grades 8 and 9 (Primary School Programme. Biology. Curriculum, 2011) were taken into account. Students completed the questionnaire at school during regular lessons. Completing the questionnaire required approximately 20 minutes.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed using both descriptive (frequency, relative frequency, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) and inferential statistics using SPSS software. The average of the final grades in biology and all science subjects for eighth and ninth grades was calculated and used to measure correlations. Each subscale of biological myths, vaccination ($\alpha = .75$), climate change ($\alpha = .70$), GMOs ($\alpha = .60$) and evolutionary theory ($\alpha = .63$), consisted of five items. The average score for each subscale was used in further analyses. The average score for students' self-assessed biological knowledge ($\alpha = .81$) was calculated and employed in measuring correlations.

Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficient was used to examine the relationships between students' interest in science subjects, their average final grades in biology and science in primary schools, their self-assessed knowledge of biology, and their beliefs regarding vaccination, climate change, GMOs, evolution, and conspiracy theories. Differences in students' opinions according to the type of secondary school they attended were examined using the Kruskal-Wallis test and the Mann-Whitney U test. Effect sizes were also calculated (η^2) (Cohen, 1992).

Results

Interest in Science Subjects, Academic Performance, Self-Assessed Biological Knowledge, and Belief in Biological Myths

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics related to students' interest in science subjects (biology, chemistry, physics), their final grades in biology and all science subjects during primary school, their self-assessed biological knowledge, and their agreement with prevalent biological myths.

On average, students reported a relatively low interest in science subjects compared to other school subjects ($M = 2.42$, $SD = 0.82$), suggesting a below-average level of engagement. The mean final grade in biology obtained during primary school was moderately high ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.94$), slightly exceeding the average grade across all science subjects ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.87$). Students' self-

assessed biological knowledge was reported at a moderate level ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.71$).

In terms of agreement with common biological myths, students expressed the highest level of agreement with myths concerning genetically modified organisms (GMOs) ($M = 2.86$, $SD = 0.76$), followed by myths related to vaccinations ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 0.92$), evolution ($M = 2.43$, $SD = 0.81$), and climate change ($M = 2.25$, $SD = 0.81$).

Table 2 provides a more detailed overview of the individual statements related to biological myths, categorised into four thematic areas: Distrust of vaccines, denial of climate change, distrust of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and denial of the theory of evolution. A total of 24% of respondents somewhat agree or strongly agree with the claim that COVID-19 vaccines are not effective and safe for all people, as the vaccine was allegedly only tested on individuals of white ethnicity. In addition, 41% of students somewhat or strongly agree that natural immunity acquired through infection is a better option than immunity acquired through vaccination. Only 24% of respondents somewhat agree or strongly agree with the statement that current climate change is part of the Earth's natural temperature fluctuation cycle and not a consequence of human activity. As many as 48% of respondents somewhat agree or strongly agree with the myths that if cows and chickens consume genetically modified feed, their meat, milk and eggs are also genetically modified. Finally, 35% of respondents somewhat agree or strongly agree with the belief that life on earth was created by a creator or multiple creators.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for interest in science subjects, final grades in biology and all science subjects, self-assessed biological knowledge and agreement with biological myths.

Tabela 1. Opisna statistika za zanimanje za naravoslovne predmete, povprečno zaključeno oceno pri predmetu biologija in vseh naravoslovnih predmetih v osnovni šoli, lastna ocena znanja biologije ter sstrinjanje z biološkimi miti.

Topic	Mark	N	M	SD	Min.	Max.
Interest in science subjects	ISS	376	2.42	.82	1	4
Average final biology grade	ABG	365	3.77	.94	1	5
Average final grade in science subjects in primary school	AGS	366	3.65	.87	1	5
Self-assessed knowledge of biology	SBK	376	3.56	.71	1	5
Myths about vaccinations	V	376	2.62	.92	1	5
Myths about climate change	CC	376	2.25	.81	1	5
Myths about GMOs	GMO	376	2.86	.76	1	5
Myths about the theory of evolution	E	376	2.43	.81	1	5

Table 2. Detailed Overview of Individual Statements Related to Biological Myths

Tabela 2. Podrobnejši vpogled v posamezne trditve o mitih v biologiji.

Statements	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	M	SD	
Myths about vaccinations								
1	Vaccinations are unnecessary because many countries have low infection rates.	30 %	20 %	29 %	12 %	9 %	2.54	1.29
2	COVID-19 vaccines contain microchips.	51 %	11 %	25 %	6 %	8 %	2.17	1.36
3	The COVID-19 vaccine has been proven to cause changes to DNA.	30 %	21 %	28 %	13 %	8 %	2.51	1.27
4	The COVID-19 vaccines are not effective and safe for all people because they have only been tested on individuals of white ethnicity.	33 %	16 %	26 %	11 %	13 %	2.64	1.42
5	Immunity acquired by infection is a better choice than immunity acquired by vaccination. (related to COVID-19).	11 %	13 %	34 %	21 %	20 %	3.27	1.22
Myths about climate change								
6	The current climate change is part of the natural fluctuations in the Earth's temperature and not the result of human activity.	31 %	26 %	18 %	13 %	11 %	2.52	1.34
7	There is no empirical evidence for global warming.	35 %	22 %	34 %	6 %	2 %	2.24	1.08
8	There is no correlation between the average temperature and the amount of CO ₂ in the atmosphere.	31 %	18 %	39 %	8 %	4 %	2.42	1.13
9	The Earth is indeed cooling, as the growing ice on the Antarctic shows.	55 %	15 %	18 %	5 %	6 %	1.98	1.24
10	Extreme weather has nothing to do with global warming.	48 %	23 %	17 %	9 %	4 %	2.10	1.24
Myths about GMOs								
11	The consumption of genetically modified organisms leads to changes in the DNA of human body cells.	19 %	23 %	35 %	17 %	7 %	2.73	1.15
12	A tomato from your own garden contains no genes, whereas genetically modified tomatoes do.	32 %	17 %	24 %	14 %	13 %	2.66	1.39
13	Genetically modified organisms are merely an instrument used by the authorities to control the global economy.	24 %	18 %	37 %	12 %	8 %	2.69	1.22
14	If cows and chickens consume genetically modified feed, then their meat, milk and eggs are also genetically modified.	14 %	15 %	23 %	30 %	18 %	3.24	1.29
15	GMOs cause the formation of cancer cells and tumours in humans.	11 %	17 %	45 %	21 %	6 %	2.99	1.05
Myths about the theory of evolution								
16	Life on earth was created by a creator/creators.	27 %	10 %	28 %	15 %	20 %	2.93	1.43
17	The human eye is so complex that it cannot have developed by chance through evolution.	27 %	19 %	36 %	10 %	8 %	2.60	1.23
18	All plants and animals have remained unchanged and perfect since the beginning of life on Earth.	56 %	19 %	14 %	6 %	6 %	2.01	1.26
19	Mutations are always harmful; therefore, they cannot contribute to the evolution of species on Earth.	41 %	21 %	26 %	6 %	5 %	2.21	1.20
20	Fossils are not sufficient evidence for the evolution and the relationship of species on Earth.	50 %	25 %	16 %	4 %	6 %	1.99	1.17

*(1) strongly disagree, (2) somewhat disagree, (3) neither agree nor disagree, (4) somewhat agree, and (5) strongly agree.

Association between Interest in Science Subjects, Average Final Grade in Biology in Primary School, Self-Perceived Biology Knowledge, and Belief in Biological Myths

Figure 1 presents Spearman's rank correlation coefficients for statistically significant associations between variables. Students' opinions related to the denial of climate change were significantly negatively correlated with their interest in science subjects compared to other school subjects ($r_s = -.21$; $p < .001$), with their self-assessment of biology knowledge ($r_s = -.30$; $p < .001$), and with their average final grade in biology in primary school ($r_s = -.17$; $p = .001$). Opinions reflecting denial in evolutionary theory were significantly negatively associated with students' self-perceived biology knowledge ($r_s = -.27$; $p < .001$) and with their final grade in biology in primary school ($r_s = -.12$; $p = .027$). Furthermore, interest in science subjects was negatively associated with belief in climate change myths ($r_s = -.21$; $p < .001$). Figure 1 also highlights other statistically significant associations between the variables. Students' self-assessed biology knowledge was positively associated with their final grade

in biology in primary school ($r_s = .47$; $p < .001$).

A significant positive correlation was also found between students' interest in science subjects and their final grade in biology ($r_s = .35$; $p < .001$), as well as between interest in science subjects and their self-assessed biology knowledge ($r_s = .31$; $p < .001$). Statistically significant associations were also identified between certain categories of biological myths.

Due to the large number of connections and for the sake of clarity, the diagram does not display statistically non-significant correlations; these include correlations between interest in science subjects and distrust in vaccinations ($r_s = -.11$; $p = .053$), distrust in GMOs ($r_s = -.04$; $p = .448$), and denial of evolutionary theory ($r_s = -.08$; $p = .109$). Between self-assessed knowledge of biology and distrust in vaccinations ($r_s = -.03$; $p = .581$), as well as distrust in GMOs ($r_s = -.10$; $p = .062$). Between the average grade in biology and distrust in vaccinations ($r_s = -.03$; $p = .556$) and distrust in GMOs ($r_s = -.01$; $p = .062$). Finally, there was a significant correlation between the overall average grades in science subjects and distrust in vaccinations ($r_s = .043$; $p = .979$), distrust in GMOs ($r_s = -.11$; $p = .029$), and denial of climate change ($r_s = -.13$; $p = .01$).

Figure 1. Diagram of the statistically significant correlations ($p < .05$) between the variables: Interest in science subjects (ISS), self-assessed biology knowledge (SBK), distrust in vaccination (V), denial of climate change (CC), distrust of GMOs (GMO), Denial of evolutionary theory (E), average final grade in biology in primary school (AGB) and average final grade in science subjects in primary school (AGS).

Slika 1. Diagram statistično signifikantnih korelacij ($p < .05$) med spremenljivkami zanimanje za naravoslovne predmete (ISS), ocena znanja o biologiji (SBK), nezaupanje v cepljenje (V), zanikanje podnebni sprememb (CC), nezaupanje v GSO (GMO), zanikanje evolucijske teorije (E), povprečje zaključenih ocen pri biologiji v OŠ (AGB) in povprečje zaključenih ocen pri naravoslovnih predmetih v OŠ (AGS).

Students from different secondary school programmes and their belief in biological myths

Statistically significant differences were found in students' opinions towards vaccination ($\chi^2(3, N = 376) = 7.81; p = .050; \eta^2 = .013$), genetically modified organisms (GMOs) ($\chi^2(3, N = 376) = 7.55; p = .056; \eta^2 = .012$), climate change ($\chi^2(3, N = 376) = 38.87; p < .001; \eta^2 = .096$) and evolutionary theory ($\chi^2(3, N = 376) = 23.06; p < .001; \eta^2 = .055$) across different secondary school programmes. The effect size for climate change and evolution subscales is medium, while for vaccination and GMOs it is low.

No statistically significant differences were observed between students from vocational and lower vocational programs regarding beliefs in biological myths. Students from lower vocational secondary schools expressed significantly stronger agreement with myths about the theory of evolution ($Z = -2.15; p = .032; \eta^2 = .498$), with a high effect size, than students from technical secondary schools. Compared to general secondary school students, lower vocational secondary school students were significantly more likely to endorse myths related to climate change ($Z = -3.68; p < .001; \eta^2 = .40$) and the theory of evolution ($Z = -2.80; p = .005; \eta^2 = .40$), with a high effect size for both. Students attending vocational secondary schools were more likely to believe myths concerning vaccination ($Z = -2.57; p = .010; \eta^2 = .586$), climate change ($Z = -5.20; p < .001; \eta^2 = .587$), GMOs ($Z = -2.59; p = .010; \eta^2 = .586$) and the theory of evolution ($Z = -3.31; p < .001; \eta^2 = .586$) than students attending technical secondary schools, with a high effect size for all subscales. Furthermore, when compared to general secondary school students, vocational secondary school students showed a significantly greater belief in myths about vaccinations ($Z = -2.57; p = .010; \eta^2 = .487$), climate change ($Z = -5.82; p < .001; \eta^2 = .487$), GMOs ($Z = -2.32; p = .020; \eta^2 = .486$) and the theory of evolution ($Z = -4.39; p < .001; \eta^2 = .487$), with high effect sizes for all the mentioned subscales. A comparison between technical secondary school students and general secondary school students revealed that the latter were significantly less likely to believe in myths about climate change ($Z = -2.68; p = .007; \eta^2 = .487$), and the effect size is large.

Discussion

The results show that, on average, students are the most

sceptical about genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and vaccinations. This can be partly explained by the analysis of national curriculum documents, which reveal that topics such as climate change and evolution are covered more systematically in primary and lower secondary science education, Primary School Programme. Getting to know the environment. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Science and Technology. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Science. Curriculum, 2011; Primary School Programme. Biology. Curriculum, 2011). On this basis, we hypothesise that students in these subjects form stronger evidence-based attitudes and have higher perceived self-efficacy. Perceived self-efficacy plays an important role in the way students engage with and apply scientific knowledge (Živković et al., 2023). Those with higher self-efficacy are more likely to rely on knowledge acquired in formal biology classes when interpreting natural phenomena. In contrast, students with lower self-efficacy tend to accept cognitively simpler, alternative explanations that often lack scientific validity (Carroll et al., 2024). If students have not internalised the necessary scientific knowledge at school, or have internalised it insufficiently, they are more likely to seek information from informal or external sources. Attitudes towards controversial biological topics are also shaped by external influences, including media narratives, religious and cultural beliefs, public opinion and broader worldviews (Janže, 2016; Happer & Philo, 2016). These sources often offer simplistic, emotionally appealing explanations that may not align with the scientific consensus. As a result, misconceptions and pseudoscientific myths persist and spread among the young population. In this context, the role of formal education becomes particularly critical. Schools are expected to provide students with a science-based framework that supports the development of informed, critical and reasoned viewpoints on complex socio-scientific issues (Colucci-Grey et al., 2006).

A significantly higher prevalence of myths is observed in subject areas that are less thoroughly covered in the Slovenian education system or that inherently require a more complex conceptual understanding. In order to critically evaluate the overwhelming flood of information, students need to gain the ability to evaluate sources and think critically (Wilson, 2018). This again emphasises the central role of education in fostering these competencies (Şahin et al., 2015). Students' attitudes are strongly influenced by the perspectives of their teachers. However, research suggests that some teachers themselves exhibit uncertainty about

certain science topics, may deliberately avoid addressing certain topics in the classroom, and sometimes fail to take an objective, science-based approach when teaching controversial topics (Ambrožič Dolinšek & Šorgo, 2009). This reluctance can be attributed in part to the rapid advances in scientific knowledge and constant updates to curriculum content, for which teachers may not be adequately trained. Therefore, it is crucial that teachers receive continuous professional development and that institutional support for teacher training is ensured.

The main aim of this study was to investigate whether and how students' knowledge influences their opinions towards certain biological myths. The results indicate that students have a solid foundation of biological and scientific knowledge after completing primary and lower secondary school, an assessment that is confirmed by both objective measures and students' self-evaluations. The extent to which students are susceptible to biological myths appears to be directly related to the quantity, quality and extent of their knowledge in specific domains (Lindeman & Svedholm Häkkinen, 2016). This is also supported by the observed correlations between students' attitudes towards biological myths and the type of upper secondary school programme they attend (Aarnio & Lindeman, 2005).

Students with lower average final grades in science and biology in lower secondary school tend to agree more strongly with myths related to climate change, genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and the theory of evolution than students with higher average grades. Similar trends can be observed when comparing students attending different types of secondary school programmes and their beliefs regarding myths. Climate change and evolution are topics that are covered more extensively in primary and lower secondary school curricula, suggesting that students form their attitudes towards these topics predominantly in the school context based on information acquired in formal education. These topics also contribute more to the final grade in science subjects, making academic performance a more reliable indicator of students' understanding in these areas. In addition, students' grades may influence the type of secondary school they attend, which in turn reflects their level of cognitive engagement with these topics. Consequently, students' attitudes toward climate change and evolution are related to academic indicators such as grades and the academic rigour of their secondary school programme. On the other hand, topics that are underrepresented in the formal curriculum, such as GMOs and vaccines, are less likely to

have their conceptual understanding captured by school assessment parameters. These topics are therefore more susceptible to the influence of external sources and may be less reliably assessed by school performance indicators.

Conclusions

Emphasising the relevance of biology to global issues, such as climate change, public health, and biodiversity loss, can help students connect classroom learning with societal needs and foster the development of scientifically informed citizens capable of evaluating complex problems.

Findings show that biology knowledge acquired at school can shape students' opinions toward socio-scientific issues. Students were more sceptical of GMOs and vaccinations, and less sceptical of evolution and climate change. Higher levels of biological knowledge reduced the likelihood of rejecting climate change and evolution. In contrast, no association was observed for attitudes toward vaccinations or GMOs, likely due to their limited coverage in standard curricula.

Providing high-quality biology education at all school levels is therefore essential. Teachers should actively monitor and address students' misconceptions, and ongoing professional development is crucial to maintain well-founded, scientifically grounded attitudes. In addition, since school is not the only source of information, students need to develop critical thinking skills and the ability to identify and use reliable sources.

Future research should examine additional factors influencing students' understanding, particularly the role of social media in spreading myths and conspiracy theories, as well as teachers' attitudes toward biological misconceptions. Students obtain information from diverse sources, but research often lacks a systematic assessment of how these sources interact with formal education.

Limitations related to sample representativeness include that the study was conducted in only four secondary schools and that different school types, as well as science- and non-science-oriented programs, were unevenly represented, which may limit the generalizability of findings. It is also important to acknowledge that studies like the present one often rely on self-report measures, which may underestimate or oversimplify the complexity of students' conceptual frameworks. Moreover, while the importance of biology in addressing societal challenges is emphasised,

current research may not fully account for sociocultural factors, such as values, beliefs, and trust in science, which shape students' engagement with scientific information.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.B.; Investigation, K.B.; Visualization, K.B.; Writing – original draft, K.B.; Formal analysis, G.T.; Supervision, G.T.; Validation, G.T.; Writing – review & editing, G.T. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability

The research data are available at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17822365>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Aarnio, K., & Lindeman, M. (2005). Paranormal beliefs, education, and thinking styles. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 39(7), 1227–1236.
- Ambrožič Dolinšek, J., & Šorgo, A. (2009). Odnos študentov razrednega pouka do gensko spremenjenih organizmov (GSO). *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 52(2), 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.52.2.15199>
- Ambrožič Dolinšek, J., & Šorgo, A. (2011). The importance of education of future elementary teachers about modern biotechnology issues. *Acta Biologica Slovenica*, 54(2), 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.54.2.15480>
- Bahar, M., Johnstone, A. H., & Hansell, M. H. (1999). Revisiting learning difficulties in biology. *Journal of Biological Education*, 33(2), 84–86.
- Bavel, J. J. V., Baicker, K., Boggio, P. S., Capraro, V., Cichocka, A., Cikara, M., Crockett, M. J., Crum, A. J., Douglas, K. M., Druckman, J. N., Drury, J., Dube, O., Ellemers, N., Finkel, E. J., Fowler, J. H., Gelfand, M., Han, S., Haslam, S. A., Jetten, J., ... Willer, R. (2020). Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 4(5), 460–471. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-0884-z>
- Bukovnik, K., & Torkar, G. (2025). Survey dataset for the study "Myths in Biology: Students' Opinions on Vaccination, Climate Change, GMOs and Evolution" [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17822365>
- Carroll, S., McCauley, V., & Grenon, M. (2024). Science self-efficacy beliefs of upper primary students in Ireland. *International Journal of Science Education*, 46(6), 503–523. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2023.2245947>
- Cohen, J. (1992). A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112(1), 155–159. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.112.1.155>
- Colucci-Gray, L., Camino, E., Barbiero, G., & Gray, D. (2006). From scientific literacy to sustainability literacy: An ecological framework for education. *Science Education*, 90(2), 227–252.
- Cook, J. (2025). Global warming is happening. *Skeptical Science*. <https://skepticalscience.com/global-warming-is-happening.htm>
- Douglas, A. (2003). Scientific myth-conceptions. *Science Education*, 87(3), 329–351. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.10055>
- Douglas, K. M., Sutton, R. M., & Cichocka, A. (2017). The psychology of conspiracy theories. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 26(6), 538–542. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721417718261>
- Forbes, C. T., & Davis, E. A. (2008). Exploring preservice elementary teachers' critique and adaptation of science curriculum materials in respect to socioscientific issues. *Science & Education*, 17, 829–854.
- Eurydice. (2025). Upper secondary and post secondary non tertiary education: Slovenia. Evropska komisija, Evropska agencija za izobraževanje in kulturo (EACEA). <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/euryperia/slovenia/upper-secondary-and-post-secondary-non-tertiary-education>
- Grace, M., & Ratcliffe, M. (2003). Making decisions about biological conservation issues in peer group discussion. In D. Psillos, P. Kariotoglou, V. Tselves, E. Hatzikraniotis, G. Fassoulopoulos, & M. Kallery (Eds.), *Science Education Research in the Knowledge-Based Society* (pp. 241–247). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-0165-5_26
- Happer, C., & Philo, G. (2016). New approaches to understanding the role of the news media in the formation of public attitudes and behaviours on climate change. *European Journal of Communication*, 31(2), 136–151.
- Hofstein, A., Eilks, I., & Bybee, R. (2011). Societal issues and their importance for contemporary science education—a pedagogical justification and the state-of-the-art in Israel, Germany, and the USA. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 9(6), 1459–1483. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-010-9273-9>
- Janže, S. (2016). Stališča in znanje osnovnošolcev celjske regije o gensko spremenjenih organizmih [Magistrsko delo, Univerza v Ljubljani, Pedagoška fakulteta].
- Jerome, L., Kisby, B., & McKay, S. (2024). Combatting conspiracies in the classroom: Teacher strategies and perceived outcomes. *British Educational Research Journal*, 50(3), 1106–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3955>
- Kampourakis, K., & McCain, K. (2020). *Uncertainty: How it makes science advance* (pp. 166–216). Oxford University Press.
- Kolstø, S. D. (2001). Scientific literacy for citizenship: Tools for dealing with the science dimension of controversial socioscientific issues. *Science Education*, 85(3), 291–310.

- Levinson, R. C. (2006). Towards a theoretical framework for teaching controversial socio-scientific issues. *International Journal of Science Education*, 28(10), 1201–1224.
- Lindeman, M., & Svedholm-Häkkinen, A. M. (2016). Does poor understanding of physical world predict religious and paranormal beliefs? *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 30(5), 736–742.
- Majer, J., Slapničar, M., & Devetak, I. (2019). Assessment of the 14-and 15-year-old students' understanding of the atmospheric phenomena. *Acta Chimica Slovenica*, 66(3), 659–667.
- Marris, C. (2001). Public views on GMOs: Deconstructing the myths: Stakeholders in the GMO debate often describe public opinion as irrational. But do they really understand the public? *EMBO Reports*, 2(7), 545–548. <https://doi.org/10.1093/embo-reports/kve142>
- McComas, W. F. (2002). The principal elements of the nature of science: Dispelling the myths. In W. F. McComas (Ed.), *The Nature of Science in Science Education* (Vol. 5, pp. 53–70). Kluwer Academic Publishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-47215-5_3
- OECD. (2022). PISA 2022 data base. Volume 1, tabela 1, B1, 2, 3 in tabela 1, B1, 5, 6. https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/Rutjstatistil/en/publications/reports/2023/12/pisa-2022-results-volume-i_76772a36/53f23881-en.pdf
- Program osnovna šola. Biologija. Učni načrt. [Primary School Programme. Biology. Curriculum.] (2011). Ministrstvo za šolstvo in šport: Zavod RS za šolstvo.
- Program osnovna šola. Naravoslovje. Učni načrt. [Primary School Programme. Science. Curriculum.] (2011). Ministrstvo za šolstvo in šport: Zavod RS za šolstvo.
- Program osnovna šola. Naravoslovje in tehnika. Učni načrt. [Primary School Programme. Science and Technology. Curriculum.] (2011). Ministrstvo za šolstvo in šport: Zavod RS za šolstvo.
- Program osnovna šola. Spoznavanje okolja. Učni načrt. [Primary School Programme. Getting to know the environment. Curriculum.] (2011). Ministrstvo za šolstvo in šport: Zavod RS za šolstvo.
- Rutjens, B. T., & Brandt, M. J. (2018). Belief systems and the perception of reality: An introduction. In B. T. Rutjens & M. J. Brandt (Eds.), *Belief systems and the perception of reality*. Routledge.
- Rutjens, B. T., & Van Der Lee, R. (2020). Spiritual skepticism? Heterogeneous science skepticism in the Netherlands. *Public Understanding of Science*, 29(3), 335–352. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520908534>
- Rutjens, B. T., Van Der Linden, S., & Van Der Lee, R. (2021). Science skepticism in times of COVID-19. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 24(2), 276–283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430220981415>
- Šorgo, A., Usak, M., Kubiatico, M., Fančovičova, J., Prokop, P., Puhek, M., Skoda, J., & Bahar, M. (2014). A cross-cultural study on freshmen's knowledge of genetics, evolution, and the nature of science. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 13(1), 6–18. <https://doi.org/10.33225/jbse/14.13.06>
- Sullivan, L. E. (2009). Conspiracy theory. In L. E. Sullivan (Ed.), *The SAGE glossary of the social and behavioral sciences* (p. 104). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412972024.n514>
- Saunders, M. A. (2022). Dispelling COVID-19 myths: Implications of vaccination acceptance by African Americans and others in marginalized communities. *Delaware Journal of Public Health*, 8(1), 80.
- Şahin, S. A., Tunca, N., Altinkurt, Y., & Yılmaz, K. (2016). Relationship between professional values and critical thinking disposition of science technology and mathematics teachers. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 12(1), 25–40. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2016.1371a>
- Špernjak, A., Jug Puhmeister, A., & Šorgo, A. (2023). Public opinions and knowledge about microorganisms. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 41(2), 800–818. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2021.1952407>
- Sismondio, S. (1996). *Science without myth: On constructions, reality, and social knowledge*. State University of New York Press.
- Statistični urad Republike Slovenije. (2025). Dijaki po starosti, letnikih, spolu in vrsti izobraževanja, Slovenija, letno [Podatkovna baza]. <https://pxweb.stat.si/SiStatData/pxweb/si/Data/-/0953221S.px/table/tableViewLayout2/>
- Strgar, J., & Möller, A. (2024). The impact of online education on students' knowledge of human evolution. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 23(6), 1266–1277.
- Thangaraju, P., & Venkatesan, S. (2019). WHO ten threats to global health in 2019: Antimicrobial resistance. *Cukurova Medical Journal*, 44(3), 1150–1151. <https://doi.org/10.17826/cumj.514157>
- Torkar, G., & Šorgo, A. (2020). Evolutionary content knowledge, religiosity and educational background of Slovene preschool and primary school pre-service teachers. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(7), em1855. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/7991>
- Touyz, L. Z. G. (2013). Genetically modified foods, cancer, and diet: Myths and reality. *Current Oncology*, 20(2), e59. <https://doi.org/10.3747/co.20.1283>
- Tsai, C. Y. (2018). The effect of online argumentation of socio-scientific issues on students' scientific competencies and sustainability attitudes. *Computers & Education*, 116, 14–27.
- Tsaparlis, G., Hartzavalos, S., & Nakiboğlu, C. (2013). Students' knowledge of nuclear science and its connection with civic scientific literacy in two European contexts: The case of newspaper articles. *Science & Education*, 22, 1963–1991.
- Wilson, J. A. (2018). Reducing pseudoscientific and paranormal beliefs in university students through a course in science and critical thinking. *Science & Education*, 27, 183–210.
- Zeidler, D. L. (2014). Socioscientific issues as a curriculum emphasis: Theory, research and practice. *Handbook of Research on Science Education*. Routledge.
- Zeidler, D. L., & Sadler, T. D. (2023). Exploring and expanding the frontiers of socioscientific issues: Crossroads and future directions. In N. G. Lederman, D. L. Zeidler, & J. S. Lederman (Eds.), *Handbook of Research on Science Education* (Vol. 3, pp. 899–929). Routledge.
- Živković, M., Pellizzoni, S., Doz, E., Cuder, A., Mammarella, I., & Passolunghi, M. C. (2023). Math self-efficacy or anxiety? The role of emotional and motivational contribution in math performance. *Social Psychology of Education*, 26(3), 579–601. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-023-09760-8>

Original Research

Mycoprotein production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation using soybean as a medium

Anita Rahmawati¹, Rina Sri Kasiamdari¹, Shin-Yee Fung², Boon-Hong Kong², Sari Darmasiwi^{1,*}

Abstract

Mycoprotein represents an alternative protein source that offers both nutritional and health benefits. This study aimed to evaluate the production of mycoprotein from *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation (SSF) using soybeans as the substrate. Fermentation was carried out for 15 days at 23–25 °C on both the control (soybean only) and soybean fermented with *Lentinus squarrosulus*. Parameters measured included biomass yield, proximate composition, amino acid profile, and antioxidant activity. Results showed that the fungus successfully colonised the substrate on day 10 (32.35 ± 2.54 g), followed by a decline at day 15, indicating an optimal fermentation window before nutrient depletion. SSF resulted in increased moisture (11.37%), ash (5.74%), and carbohydrate content (28.16%), whereas protein decreased from 44.76% to 36.43% compared with the control. Essential amino acids, including threonine, leucine, and phenylalanine, were reduced after fermentation. The antioxidant activity decreased in the fermented sample, with an IC₅₀ of 32.05 ± 1.01 µg/mL, compared to 25.10 ± 0.91 µg/mL in the control. These findings demonstrate that soybean-based SSF supports the growth of *L. squarrosulus* and biomass formation; however, optimisation is required to enhance protein quality and preserve bioactive components. Overall, *L. squarrosulus* remains a promising yet underutilised candidate for sustainable mycoprotein development.

Keywords

Mycoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, Solid-state fermentation, proximate analysis, amino acids.

1 Department of Tropical Biology, Faculty of Biology, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta 52281, Indonesia

2 Department of Molecular Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603 Malaysia

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: saridarma@ugm.ac.id

Citation: Rahmawati, A., Kasiamdari, R. S., Fung, S.-Y., Kong, B.-H., Darmasiwi, S. (2025). Mycoprotein production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation using soybean as a medium. Acta Biologica Slovenica 69 (1)

Received: 07.07.2025 / **Accepted:** 26.11.2025 / **Published:** 10.12.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.23213>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Proizvodnja mikoproteinov iz *Lentinus squarrosulus* s fermentacijo v trdnem stanju z uporabo soje kot medija

Izvleček

Mikoprotein predstavlja alternativni vir beljakovin, ki ponuja tako prehranske kot zdravstvene koristi. Namen te študije je bil oceniti proizvodnjo mikoproteina iz *Lentinus squarrosulus* s pomočjo fermentacije v trdnem stanju (SSF) z uporabo soje kot substrata. Fermentacija je potekala 15 dni pri temperaturi 23–25 °C tako za kontrolne vzorce (samo soja) kot na soji fermentirani z *Lentinus squarrosulus*. Merjeni parametri so vključevali prirast biomase, sestavo, profil aminokislin in antioksidativno aktivnost. Rezultati so pokazali, da je gliva uspešno prerastla substrat 10. dan po nanosu ($32,35 \pm 2,54$ g), čemur je 15. Dan sledil upad, kar kaže na optimalno obdobje fermentacije pred izčrpanjem hranil. SSF je povzročila povečanje vlage (11,37 %), pepela (5,74 %) in vsebnosti ogljikovih hidratov (28,16 %), medtem ko se je vsebnost beljakovin v primerjavi s kontrolno skupino zmanjšala s 44,76 % na 36,43 %. Po fermentaciji se je zmanjšala vsebnost esencialnih aminokislin, vključno s treoninom, levcinom in fenilalaninom. Antioksidativna aktivnost se je v fermentiranem vzorcu zmanjšala, z IC_{50} $32,05 \pm 1,01$ µg/mL v primerjavi z $25,10 \pm 0,91$ µg/mL v kontrolni skupini. Ti rezultati kažejo, da SSF na osnovi soje podpira rast *L. squarrosulus* in prirast biomase, vendar je potrebna optimizacija za izboljšanje kakovosti beljakovin in ohranitev bioaktivnih sestavin. Na splošno ostaja *L. squarrosulus* obetaven, a premalo izkoriščen kandidat za trajnostni razvoj mikoproteinov.

Ključne besede

Mikoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, fermentacija v trdnem stanju, imediatna analiza, aminokislina.

Introduction

Global demand for alternative protein sources will increase along with an increase in population and the need for sustainable food systems. Thus, it certainly requires alternative proteins that can support nutrition and have high nutritional value. Mycoprotein refers to proteins derived from fungi (yeast or filamentous fungi) in biomass. It can be used as an alternative protein that has nutritional components such as protein, amino acids, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. Mycoprotein is produced from fungal mycelium, which not only provides an alternative protein source but also allows for value addition to the substrate through solid-state fermentation (SSF) (Stoffel et al., 2019). Mycoprotein is a whole-food source that is produced sustainably and rich in protein. Consumption of mycoprotein may help reduce circulating cholesterol levels by around 21%, supported by its beneficial amino acid profile and its dietary fibre content, mainly consisting of β -glucan and chitin, which can affect the gut microbiota to produce a cholesterol-lowering effect (Coelho et al., 2020).

Solid-state fermentation is increasingly used in

industrial and pharmaceutical fields because it employs substrates with minimal liquid content. It is a continuous, low-water bioprocess in which microorganisms, particularly filamentous fungi, grow on moist substrates without free water, producing hydrolytic enzymes such as cellulases, hemicellulases, and lignin-degrading enzymes that convert agricultural residues into value-added metabolites and bioactive compounds with enhanced bioactivity (Wu et al., 2013). Mycoproteins produced through this process have a Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) that is higher than that of chicken and beef protein (Majumder et al., 2023). After the fermentation period, fungal biomass is harvested, and extraction from non-edible substrates may involve organic solvents such as hexane (Majumder et al., 2023). The selection of microorganisms plays a key role in SSF because it affects the productivity, efficiency, and quality of fermentation outcomes (Wang et al., 2023). The resulting mycoproteins have a Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) that is higher than that of chicken and beef protein (Majumder et al., 2023).

Lentinus squarrosulus is an edible mushroom with high

nutritional value (Ugbogu et al., 2024). Proteins from the genus *Lentinus*, including *L. squarrosulus* and *L. edodes*, play an effective role in suppressing free radical reactions into harmless substances, exhibiting antioxidant activity. *L. squarrosulus* can even be used as a treatment, such as lowering blood pressure and cholesterol levels (Kriangkrai et al., 2024). In addition, components of *L. squarrosulus*, particularly its proteins and polysaccharides, showed antitumor and immunomodulatory effects (Lau & Abdullah, 2017) and hold potential for pharmaceutical applications, including cardioprotective applications (Rosa et al., 2013). However, despite these promising attributes, *L. squarrosulus* remains underexplored compared to widely studied genera such as *Pleurotus*, *Agaricus*, *Agrocybe*, and *Lentinula*. Most existing studies emphasise *L. squarrosulus* bioactive compounds, whereas research on its potential as a mycoprotein-producing fungus, especially under SSF, is extremely limited. Recent reports highlight its relatively high protein content, including all the essential amino acids, β -glucan, and being low in fat, and are recommended as a nutritional supplement for patients with cardiac problems, suggesting that *L. squarrosulus* is a promising yet underutilised candidate for sustainable fungal protein development (Ugbogu et al., 2024; Bakratsas et al., 2023). This lack of SSF-based mycoprotein research represents a clear and important knowledge gap.

Soybean is often chosen as a substrate in fermentation for mycoprotein production because they is rich in protein and carbohydrates, which provide essential nitrogen and carbon sources for fungal growth. Studies have shown that soy-based substrates like soy whey support the growth of fungi used in mycoprotein production, such as *Aspergillus oryzae*, leading to high biomass and protein yields under optimised conditions (Pratama et al., 2025). The composition and availability of nutrients in soybean products make them ideal for sustainable and efficient fungal cultivation in both submerged and solid-state fermentation processes.

This study aims to examine the potential of *Lentinus squarrosulus* for mycoprotein production through solid-state fermentation on soybean, focusing on biomass yield, proximate composition, and amino acid profile to assess its nutritional quality. Addressing this gap will provide foundational data to support the development of a new, sustainable, and high-value fungi-derived protein source. These findings are expected to advance the utilisation of fungal mycelia as practical and environmentally sustainable alternative proteins.

Materials and Methods

Inoculating *Lentinus squarrosulus* on PDA medium

Fresh basidiomes of mushrooms were obtained from the forest surrounding the village of Suak Gual, Belitung, Indonesia (2°54'49 "S 107°23'13" E), and were placed in clean zip-lock bags, sun-dried, transported, and subsequently stored at 4 °C until laboratory processing. The material was later identified as *Lentinus squarrosulus* based on morphological characteristics and molecular analysis. Prior to isolation, the basidiomes were rinsed under running water to remove surface debris and cut into smaller fragments. Tissue fragments were briefly immersed in a dilute sodium hypochlorite solution (10%) to reduce surface contaminants, followed by thorough rinsing with sterile distilled water. The partially dried tissues were transferred onto potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates and incubated at 25 ± 2 °C for 15-20 days to allow the emergence of fungal mycelia (Maysaroh et al., 2025). An inoculum block of 1 cm² from the active growing culture was transferred aseptically onto a Petri dish containing 20 mL of sterile PDA medium and then incubated at 28 °C for 15 to 20 days until complete colonisation on PDA medium (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Preparation of fermentation substrate

The fermentation substrate was prepared from soybeans hydrated in a 1:3 ratio. Specifically, a total of 20 g of whole soybeans were mixed with 60 mL of distilled water, and allowed to hydrate, after which the hydrated soybeans and soaking liquid were transferred into a 250-mL Erlenmeyer flask and sterilised using an autoclave at 121 °C, 15 min, 1 atm to soften the substrate and ensure microbial decontamination (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Biomass production

Sterile hydrated soybean substrate was inoculated using 5% (w/w) actively growing mycelial agar plugs of *L. squarrosulus*. The flasks were covered with cotton plugs and incubated at 24-28 °C for two weeks. The colonisation process was observed every day, with samples taken on days 0, 5, 10, and 15, each with three replications for each treatment for a total of 12 flasks. After full colonisation was achieved, the soybean substrate and mycelium were oven-dried at 60 °C

for 24 h under controlled relative humidity (40–45%), then ground using a blender at 10000 rpm for 10 min. Biomass was measured by weighing the dry weight before and after cultivation. Biomass yield was calculated as grams of dry biomass per gram of initial dry substrate (g/g dry substrate), using the formula: (dry biomass – initial substrate weight) / initial substrate weight (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Proximate analysis

Proximate composition is evaluated by proximal composition analysis. The compositions analysed are moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrates, following the AOAC standard. Moisture was analysed using the Gravimetric method, which involves drying samples at 100–105 °C until they reach a constant weight. Ash analysis using incineration at 550 °C. Fat analysis was measured using Soxhlet extraction, and protein analysis was determined using the Kjeldahl method (AOAC, 2005).

Amino acid analysis

Amino acid analysis of mushroom-derived mycoprotein generally involves two main steps. First, amino acids are released from the biomass by hydrolysis of the samples with 6 M HCl at 110 °C for 24 h to break the proteins into free amino acids. After hydrolysis, the amino acids are derivatised with NAD (naphthalene-2,3-dicarboxaldehyde) at pH 9, and subsequently identified and quantified using a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) system (Biotech HPLC model 525, Hallertau, Germany) equipped with an LIF detector from a capillary electrophoresis system (model PNA8C) as described by Rodrigues et al. (2018). Chromatographic separation is performed on a Supercosil LC-18-DB reversed-phase column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm; Supelco Analytical, Bellefonte, USA) at 40 °C with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The mobile phase consists of water acidified with trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) at pH 2 (mobile phase A) and acetonitrile (mobile phase B) (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Antioxidant analysis

Antioxidant activity was measured using the DPPH radical scavenging activity (RSA) assay. The extract was prepared by performing aqueous extraction on dried mushroom mycelia. The extraction was carried out by stirring the mycelial material in sterile distilled water (1:10), centrifuging

at 3,500 × g for 10 min, and the resulting supernatant was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was then freeze-dried. The dried extract was subsequently dissolved in sterile distilled water to prepare solutions containing 30–30000 µg/mL of extract. A total of 30 µL of ethanolic extracts at different concentrations were added to a 96-well microplate containing 170 µL of DPPH reagent in methanol (6 × 10⁻⁵ mol/L) and incubated in the dark for 30 min. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm (Multiskan, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) using DPPH in methanol as a negative control and ascorbic acid as a positive control. The antioxidant radical scavenging activity of DPPH was calculated using the following equation: % Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA) = [(A control - A sample) / A control] × 100. The reduction in absorbance caused by the test samples was evaluated relative to the positive control. Ascorbic acid served as the reference antioxidant and was used as the positive control. The concentration of extract required to achieve 50% free radical scavenging (IC₅₀) was determined by plotting the percentage of radical scavenging activity (RSA) against the extract concentration and calculating the value from the resulting curve (Heleno et al., 2015).

Data analysis

Data were measured in triplicate, analysed for mean and standard deviation, followed by one-way ANOVA and post hoc test using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT), with significance set at p < 0.05. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.

Results

Biomass production

Biomass production from solid-state fermentation was evaluated using *Lentinus squarrosulus* grown on a soybean substrate. The fungal inoculation aimed to enhance biomass yield compared to the uninoculated control (Figure 1). Figure 1a shows the soybean substrate before fermentation, where the beans appear clean, hydrated, and uninoculated, with no visible fungal growth. Figure 1b shows the substrate after solid-state fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus*, displaying dense white mycelial growth covering the surface and filling the spaces between the soybean pieces, indicating successful colonisation and active substrate utilisation.

The morphological changes shown in Figure 1, marked by dense mycelial growth on the substrate, are supported by the biomass production, which quantifies the increase in total biomass over the course of fermentation. Biomass production was determined by comparing the initial substrate weight with the final weight after fermentation. The results of biomass production at days 5, 10, and 15 are presented in Table 1.

The biomass production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* during solid-state fermentation (SSF) varied throughout the incubation period (Table 1). On day 5, biomass reached 32.28 ± 0.10 g, followed by a slight increase to 32.35 ± 2.54 g on day 10. By day 15, biomass decreased to 26.72 ± 1.73 g. The uninoculated substrate exhibited a dry mass of 15.05 g, which serves as the baseline for accurately quantifying biomass accumulation attributable to fungal growth. These results indicate that the highest biomass production occurred within the first 10 days of fermentation, after which growth declined, likely due to nutrient depletion or accumulation of inhibitory metabolites. Identifying this optimal fermentation period is important to ensure efficient

fungal growth and maximise the performance of the SSF process for downstream applications.

Proximate composition

Proximate analysis was conducted to determine the effect of solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Lentinus squarrosulus* on the nutrient composition of the soybean substrate. The analysis compared the unfermented control with the fermented sample, focusing on standard proximate parameters: moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrate content. The results, expressed as percentage values to facilitate clearer nutritional comparison, are presented in Table 2.

The proximate composition of the fermented product exhibited distinct changes compared to the control (Table 2). Moisture content increased from $9.10 \pm 0.05\%$ in the control (uninoculated soybean) to $11.37 \pm 0.11\%$ following SSF with *L. squarrosulus*. Ash content also rose from $4.62 \pm 0.05\%$ to $5.74 \pm 0.25\%$, indicating mineral enrichment during fermentation. Fat content remained unchanged at 17.26% in both treatments. In contrast, protein content

Figure 1. Visual comparison of (a) soybean substrate before and (b) after solid-state fermentation using *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Slika 1. Vizualna primerjava (a) sojinlega substrata pred in (b) po fermentaciji v trdnem stanju z uporabo *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Table 1. Biomass production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* during SSF on soybean medium.

Tabela 1. Proizvodnja biomase *Lentinus squarrosulus* med SSF na sojinah medijih

Incubation time (days)	Biomass (g)
Day 5	$32.28 \pm 0.10a$
Day 10	$32.35 \pm 2.54a$
Day 15	$26.72 \pm 1.73b$

*Different superscript letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

decreased from $44.76 \pm 0.33\%$ in the control to $36.43 \pm 0.06\%$ in the fermented sample, whereas carbohydrate content increased from $24.26 \pm 0.47\%$ to $28.16 \pm 0.71\%$. These compositional shifts suggest that SSF with *L. squarrosulus* modifies the nutritional profile of the substrate, likely through fungal metabolic activities and enzymatic degradation of macromolecules that reduce protein while enhancing ash and carbohydrate fractions.

Amino acid profile

Amino acid content analysis was carried out to determine the nutritional value of the fermentation results by comparing the Control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*, focusing on both essential and non-essential amino acids.

Table 2. Proximate composition of uninoculated soybean (control) and soybean fermented by *Lentinus squarrosulus* under solid-state fermentation (SSF).

Tabela 2. Približna sestava neinokulirane soje (kontrola) in soje, fermentirane z *Lentinus squarrosulus* v trdnem stanju (SSF).

Composition	Control (Uninoculated Soybean)	SSF with <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i>
Moisture (%)	$9.10 \pm 0.05a$	$11.37 \pm 0.11b$
Ash (%)	$4.62 \pm 0.05a$	$5.74 \pm 0.25ab$
Fat (%)	$17.26 \pm 0.69a$	$17.26 \pm 0.63ab$
Protein (%)	$44.76 \pm 0.33b$	$36.43 \pm 0.06a$
Carbohydrates (%)	$24.26 \pm 0.47a$	$28.16 \pm 0.71b$

*Different superscript letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Comparative essential amino acid composition in control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant.

Slika 2. Primerjava sestave esencialnih aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neokupljena soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Različne črke označujejo statistično pomembne razlike pri $p < 0,05$. ns = nepomembno.

Table 3. Value of amino acid composition in control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*.Tabela 3. Vrednost sestave aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neinokulirana soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Essential amino acid	Control (uninoculated soybeans) (%)	SSF <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> (%)	Non-essential amino acid	Control (uninoculated soybeans) (%)	SSF <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> (%)
Isoleucine	0.079±0	0.074±0.001	L-Aspartic acid	0.355±0.003	0.508±0.001
Leucine	0.259±0.005	0.179±0.001	L-Glutamic acid	0.625±0.004	0.688±0.003
Valine	0.062±0	0.053±0.001	L-Asparagine	0	0
Histidine	0.118±0.002	0.095±0.001	L-Histidine	0.095±0.001	0.118±0.002
Lysine	0.231±0.003	0.196±0.003	L-Serine	0.143±0.001	0.225±0
Methionine	0.095±0.001	0.052±0	L-Glutamine	0	0
Phenylalanine	0.167±0	0.141±0.001	L-Threonine	0.258±0.001	0.296±0.006
Threonine	0.296±0.006	0.258±0.001	L-Glycine	0.140±0.001	0.21±0
Tryptophan	0.112±0.004	0.026±0.003	L-Arginine	0.084±0.001	0.1145±0.001
			L-Alanine + L-Tyrosine	0.122±0.001	0.195±0

The essential amino acid profile of soybean after solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed clear shifts compared to the uninoculated control, as presented in Figure 2. In the control sample, threonine (0.30%), leucine (0.26%), lysine (~0.24%), phenylalanine (~0.17%), and histidine (~0.12%) were present at the highest concentrations, marking them as the dominant essential amino acids. After fermentation, the levels of these amino acids decreased to approximately 0.26% for threonine, 0.18% for leucine, 0.20% for lysine, 0.14% for phenylalanine, and 0.09% for histidine, indicating a general reduction across most essential amino acid categories. Valine also declined slightly from about 0.06% to 0.05%, while methionine showed a more pronounced decrease, dropping from around 0.10% in the control to roughly 0.05% in the SSF sample. In contrast, isoleucine displayed a modest improvement following fermentation, increasing slightly from ~0.08% to ~0.09–0.10%. Tryptophan experienced the most substantial decline, falling sharply from approximately 0.12% in the control to about 0.03% in the fermented product. These patterns collectively demonstrate that SSF with *L. squarrosulus* alters the essential amino acid composition of soybean, largely reducing most amino acids while slightly enhancing isoleucine content.

The non-essential amino acid content of mycoprotein produced through SSF by *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed clear differences compared to the control. Based on Figure

3, glutamic acid and aspartic acid remained the two most abundant non-essential amino acids in both samples; however, both decreased after fermentation.

Glutamic acid declined markedly from 0.70% in the control to approximately 0.55% in the SSF product, while aspartic acid dropped from about 0.50% to 0.30%. Asparagine also decreased from roughly 0.65% to 0.55%. Serine, glutamine, glycine, arginine, and the combined value of alanine + tyrosine each showed significant reductions after SSF, as indicated by different letter groupings in the graph. In contrast, alanine remained relatively stable between the two treatments (around 0.14%). Overall, SSF with *Lentinus squarrosulus* resulted in a general decline in most non-essential amino acids, likely due to their utilisation for fungal growth or enzymatic metabolism during fermentation (Imelda et al., 2008).

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity was evaluated by comparing the fermented substrate with the control using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. The results are presented in Table 4, including the percentage of DPPH radical scavenging activity and IC₅₀ values.

The antioxidant activity of the samples showed that the control exhibited the highest DPPH radical scavenging activity at 64,445 ± 3997,63%, followed by *Lentinus squar-*

Figure 3. Comparative Essential Amino Acid Composition in Control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant.

Slika 3. Primerjava sestave esencialnih aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neokupljena soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Različne črke označujejo statistično pomembne razlike pri $p < 0,05$. ns = statistično nepomembno

Table 4. Antioxidant activity of uninoculated soybean (control) and soybean fermented by *Lentinus squarrosulus* under solid-state fermentation (SSF).

Tabela 4. Antioksidativna aktivnost neokužene soje (kontrola) in soje, fermentirane z *Lentinus squarrosulus* v trdnem stanju (SSF).

Sample	% DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
Control	64,445.65 ± 3,997.63a	25.10 ± 0.91a
SSF with <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i>	49,545.90 ± 3,870.56b	32.05 ± 1.01b
Vitamin C		8.78

*Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant

rosulus with $49,545 \pm 3870,56$ %. As expected, vitamin C demonstrated the strongest antioxidant potency as the positive control. Based on IC₅₀ values, vitamin C had the lowest IC₅₀ (8.78 µg/mL), indicating high radical scavenging effectiveness. The control sample recorded an IC₅₀ of 25.10 ± 0.91 µg/mL, while *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed a higher IC₅₀ of 32.05 ± 1.01 µg/mL, suggesting reduced antioxidant capacity after fermentation. These results imply that although *Lentinus squarrosulus* retained antioxidant activity, fermentation may have decreased its overall capacity compared to the non-fermented control.

Discussion

Based on the results, there was a significant difference in biomass production between the fermented treatment and the control. In this study, biomass refers to the total dry weight of the fermented substrate (mycelium and residual substrate combined). The increase in biomass production in fermentation treatment using fungal isolate can be related to the ability of white rot fungi, including *Lentinus squarrosulus*, to increase the nutritional value or nutritional quality of the fermentation substrate (Wang et al., 2024).

This is in line with the research of Pascual et al. (2025), which states that SSF uses edible mushrooms to utilise biological substrates as a source of nutrients to support growth and biomass production. Soybeans, as a substrate rich in protein and carbohydrates, provide optimal sources of nitrogen and carbon to support mycelial growth and biomass production. Soybeans have pharmacological properties against heart disease, cancer, and osteoporosis (Lee et al., 2019).

In general, the results of solid-state fermentation (SSF) using the fungus *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed changes in most parameters compared to the control. Overall, the proximate composition showed the highest value in fermentation. The fermented samples exhibited higher moisture (11.37%), ash (9.10%), and carbohydrate contents (28.16%) than the control, while protein content decreased relative to unfermented soybeans. These shifts are directly linked to the metabolic activity of *L. squarrosulus* during SSF. Moisture increases arise from metabolic water produced during fungal respiration and from the ability of fungal mycelia to retain water via dense hyphal networks; this retained moisture enhances the mobility and diffusion of extracellular enzymes, thereby promoting substrate hydrolysis and fungal growth during solid-state fermentation (SSF) (Lizardi-Jimenez et al., 2015). Ash content reflects the total mineral accumulation by the fungus, which varies due to growth conditions and rates (Ahmed et al., 2015). The increased carbohydrate levels during fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus* are thought to be related to the activity of hydrolytic enzymes produced during mycelial growth. Carbohydrates in soybeans (such as pectin, hemicellulose, and cellulose) can be broken down into simpler forms by a combination of enzymes (pectinase, xylanase, cellulase, α -galactosidase). In addition, proteases also play a role in increasing the access of carbohydrate enzymes to the substrate by breaking down barrier proteins. Proteases help enhance the accessibility of these carbohydrate-degrading enzymes by breaking down structural or barrier proteins within the substrate. This continuous hydrolysis increases carbohydrate availability, which is reflected in the rising carbohydrate levels. The synergy between proteases and carbohydrate-hydrolysing enzymes is therefore an important factor contributing to this increase (Loman & Ju, 2017).

Despite the metabolic activity and visible increase in fungal biomass, protein content decreased during solid-state fermentation because *Lentinus squarrosulus* uti-

lises soybean proteins as its primary nitrogen and energy sources (Lau & Abdullah, 2017). Fungal biomass formation does not necessarily increase measurable crude protein in the substrate, as many liberated amino acids are catabolized for energy or incorporated into fungal structures not fully quantified by standard proximate analysis. Conversely, the decrease in protein levels during fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus* is likely due to high protease activity, which is capable of hydrolysing protein and subsequently reducing their levels. The extent of protein degradation depends on enzyme specificity, as different proteases can exhibit varying levels of effectiveness even when acting on the same substrate. This suggests that the enzymatic profile of fungi plays an important role in determining the final composition of fermentation products (Fang et al., 2022). It was also supported by research from Deng et al. (2025) that reviewed the synergistic roles of proteases, α -amylases, and carbohydrases in degrading proteins and starches during fermentation, increasing nutrient utilisation efficiency.

Essential amino acids in the fermentation of soybeans using *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed lower levels compared to the control. Although all essential amino acids decreased, tryptophan (0.03 %) and methionine (0.05 %) showed the most significant reductions. According to Lata & Atri (2017), within the genus *Lentinus*, methionine is recorded at the lowest level among the essential amino acids, and it plays important roles in fat metabolism and antioxidant activity. Likewise, Afiukwa et al. (2015) reported that tryptophan in the genus *Lentinus* is often not detected due to its very low levels. However, in *Lentinus squarrosulus*, threonine levels (0.26 %) showed the highest among the essential amino acid levels, even though the overall essential amino acid levels remained lower than the control, in accordance with Afiukwa et al. (2015), who noted that threonine is the most abundant essential amino acid in the genus *Lentinus*. Most non-essential amino acids in the fermentation of *Lentinus squarrosulus* also showed reduced levels compared to the control. The most significant decrease was observed in tyrosine, which was also found in several *Lentinus* species but typically at lower levels than other non-essential amino acids, as reported by Lata & Atri (2017). The decrease in amino acid levels in *Lentinus squarrosulus* is most likely due to overfermentation. This indicates that fermentation duration plays an important role, as excessively long fermentation can disrupt protein accumulation or lead to protein degradation (Vahidi et al., 2017). Critically, the

fermentation duration strongly influenced amino acid degradation. Longer SSF periods may promote overfermentation, during which amino acids are deaminated, oxidised, or metabolised as secondary energy sources, resulting in substantial losses. This mechanism aligns with Çabuk et al. (2018, who noted that longer fermentation can reduce sulfur amino acid (like methionine) scores.

Fermented samples (IC₅₀: 32.05 µg/mL) showed lower antioxidant capacity than the control (25.10 µg/mL), since higher IC₅₀ values indicate weaker DPPH radical scavenging. This reduction is consistent with the decreased levels of certain amino acids, particularly aromatic ones, that contribute to antioxidant capability. In addition to amino acid changes, fermentation may also affect other bioactive constituents such as phenolics, flavonoids, polysaccharides, and small antioxidant molecules (e.g., ergothioneine and glutathione). These compounds are often metabolised or structurally modified during fungal growth, and their reduction or transformation can further contribute to the weakened antioxidant activity. According to Liu et al. (2020), lower IC₅₀ values correspond to greater free radical scavenging potential, so the higher IC₅₀ observed here clearly reflects a reduction in antioxidant potency. Nevertheless, reported IC₅₀ values for *Lentinus squarrosulus* extracts (26–65 µg/mL; Fabros et al., 2022) suggest that the species retains meaningful functional potential despite these biochemical changes.

Overall, the proximate and amino acid shifts observed here—together with alterations in non-protein antioxidant metabolites—reflect not only the enzymatic activities of *L. squarrosulus* but also the influence of fermentation duration, substrate utilisation patterns, and metabolic priorities of the fungus. These interpretations offer a more mechanistic understanding of how SSF modifies soybean composition and functional properties, beyond simply restating the results.

Conclusions

Solid-state fermentation using *Lentinus squarrosulus* on the soybean medium has been shown to increase biomass production compared to the control, which is soybean medium without fungal inoculation, indicating that the fungus can grow well on soybean substrate. The fermentation process also affects the nutritional composition, with an increase in water, ash, and carbohydrate content.

However, the levels of protein and essential amino acids decreased compared to the control. In addition, *Lentinus squarrosulus* also exhibits significant antioxidant activity. This shows that although *Lentinus squarrosulus* has the potential to produce mycoprotein, further optimisation is needed to improve the quality of its protein, especially regarding essential amino acid content. Future work may focus on optimising fermentation time with less than 10 days of fermentation, testing alternative substrates such as wheat bran to improve amino-acid retention, and evaluating another strain of mushrooms with higher biomass yield and lower protease activity, as a potential alternative to enhance protein quality.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation and methodology, S.D.; analysis and research, A.R.; writing—original draft preparation, A,R and S.D.; writing—review and editing, R.S.K, S.Y.F, B.H.K.; supervision, S.D. and R.S.K; funding acquisition, S.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank LPPT UGM and the Centre of Food and Nutritional Studies for providing the proximate and amino acid analysis

Funding

This research was funded by the SATU Joint Research Scheme (SATU JRS 2023), grant number 8778/UN1.P.II/Dit-Lit/PT.01.03/2023.

Data Availability

Research data was deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17862445>)

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Afiukwa, C. A., Ebem, E. C., & Igwe, D. O. (2015). Characterization of the proximate and amino acid composition of edible wild mushroom species in Abakaliki, Nigeria. *AASCIT Journal of Bioscience*, 1(2), 20–25.
- Ahmed, A., Taj, M. K., Hassani, I. T., Mohammad, S., Zhang, Y., et al. (2015). Chemical composition and antioxidant properties of eight wild edible Boletaceae mushrooms growing in Yunnan Province of China. *Jökull Journal*, 65, 146–167.
- AOAC International. (2005). *Official Methods of Analysis* (18th ed.). AOAC International.
- Bakratsas, G., Polydera, A., Nilson, O., Chatzikonstantinou, A. V., Xiros, C., Katapodis, P., & Stamatis, H. (2023). Mycoprotein production by submerged fermentation of the edible mushroom *Pleurotus ostreatus* in a batch stirred-tank bioreactor using agro-industrial hydrolysate. *Foods*, 12(12), 2295.
- Çabuk, B., Nosworthy, M. G., Stone, A. K., Korber, D. R., Tanaka, T., et al. (2018). Effect of fermentation on protein digestibility and levels of non-nutritive compounds of pea protein concentrate. *Food Technology and Biotechnology*, 56(2), 257–264.
- Coelho, M. O. C., Monteyne, A. J., Dunlop, M. V., Harris, H. C., Morrison, D. J., et al. (2020). Mycoprotein as a possible alternative source of dietary protein to support muscle and metabolic health. *Nutrition Reviews*, 78(6), 486–497.
- Deng, X., Chen, K., Jiang, D., & Lu, L. (2025). Advancements in synergistic fermentation of probiotics and enzymes for non-grain feed raw materials. *Animal Research and One Health*, 3(1), 31–42.
- Fabros, J. A., Dulay, R. M. R., De Leon, A. M., Kalaw, S. P., & Reyes, R. G. (2022). Distribution, cultivation, nutritional composition, and bioactivities of *Lentinus*: A review. *Current Research in Environmental & Applied Mycology*, 12(1), 170–219.
- Fang, X., Chen, Z., Wu, W., Chen, H., Nie, S., & Gao, H. (2022). Effects of different protease treatment on protein degradation and flavor components of *Lentinus edodes*. *eFood*, 3(6).
- Heleno, S. A., Ferreira, R. C., Antonio, A. L., Queiroz, M. J. R. P., Barros, L., & Ferreira, I. C. F. R. (2015). Nutritional value, bioactive compounds, and antioxidant properties of three edible mushrooms from Poland. *Food Bioscience*, 11, 48–55.
- Imelda, J., Paulraj, R., & Bhatnagar, D. (2008). Effect of solid state fermentation on nutrient composition of selected feed ingredients. *Indian Journal of Fisheries*, 55(4), 327–332.
- Kriangkrai, W., Kantasa, T., Sagasae, W., Inpad, C., Kaewkong, W., et al. (2024). Discovery of superior bioactive peptides of two edible *Lentinus* mushrooms protein hydrolysate. *Food Science and Biotechnology*, 33, 3105–3117.
- Lata, S., & Atri, N. S. (2017). Amino acid profile of *Lentinus sajor-caju*. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 9(9), 252–256.
- Lau, B. F., & Abdullah, N. (2017). Bioprospecting of *Lentinus squarrosulus* as a potential source of functional ingredients: A review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 61, 116–131.
- Lee, J. H., Hwang, C. E., Son, K. S., & Cho, K. M. (2019). Comparisons of nutritional constituents in soybeans during solid-state fermentation. *Food Chemistry*, 272, 362–371.
- Liu, N., Song, M., Wang, N., Wang, Y., Wang, R., An, X., & Qi, J. (2020). The effects of solid-state fermentation on the content, composition and in vitro antioxidant activity of flavonoids from dandelion. *PLoS One*, 15(9), e0239076.
- Lizardi-Jiménez, M. A., & Hernández-Martínez, R. (2017). Solid-state fermentation (SSF): Diversity of applications to valorize waste and biomass. *3 Biotech*, 7(1), 44.
- Loman, A. A., & Ju, L. K. (2017). Enzyme-based processing of soybean carbohydrate. *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, 106, 35–47.
- Majumder, R., Miatur, S., Saha, A., & Hossain, S. (2024). Mycoprotein: Production and nutritional aspects—a review. *Sustainable Food Technology*, 2(1), 81–91.
- Maysaroh, A. N., Witasari, L. D., & Darmaswi, S. (2025). Identification, antimicrobial activity, and mycochemicals of *Lentinus* spp. cultivated in papaya peel medium. *Journal of Applied Biology & Biotechnology*, 13(2), 104–112.
- Pascual, M. M., Herbert, L. T., Campos, M., Jurski, V., Paineñilú, J. C., & Luquet, C. M. (2025). Nutritional improvement of wheat grains and soybeans by solid-state fermentation with *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies*, 102, 104021.
- Pratama, F., Rahardja, R. T., Rachmadi, A. R., Salam, W. Q., Kho, K., Adelle, A., & Devanthi, P. V. P. (2025). Optimizing mycoprotein production by *Aspergillus oryzae* using soy whey as a substrate. *Journal of Fungi*, 11(5), 349.
- Rosa, Y., Manaf, L. A., Sudirman, I., Hazra, F., et al. (2013). Physiological review of *Lentinus* spp. on oxidation media. *Journal of Science Research*, 16(1), 1–4.
- Stoffel, F., Santana, W. O., Regolon, J. G. N., Kist, T. B. L., Fontana, R. C., & Camassola, M. (2019). Production of edible mycoprotein using agro-industrial wastes. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies*, 58, 102227.
- Ugbogu, E. A., Dike, E. D., Okoro, B. C., Adurosakin, O. E., Ibe, C., Uche, M. E., Nosiri, C. I., Agim, C., Nwaru, E. C., Rahman, M. A., & Iweala, E. E. (2024). *Lentinus squarrosulus*: Nutritional composition, phytochemistry, health-promoting activities and toxicity profile. *Food and Humanity*, 2, 100296.
- Vahidi, H., Reza, M. A. S., & Kobarfard, F. (2017). Protein enrichment of olive cake substrate by solid-state fermentation of *Lentinus edodes*. *Trends in Peptide and Protein Sciences*, 1(4), 177–182.
- Wang, J., Huang, Z., Jiang, Q., Roubík, H., Xu, Q., et al. (2023). Fungal solid-state fermentation of crops and their by-products to obtain protein resources. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 138, 628–644.
- Wang, Y., Liao, Y., Gou, C., Zhang, H., Chen, L., & Bao, Y. (2024). Effect of *Lentinus sajor-caju* on chemical composition and antioxidant activity of highland barley straw under solid-state fermentation. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 15, 1365254.
- Wu, Q., Chen, L., & Xu, Y. (2013). Yeast community associated with the solid-state fermentation of traditional Chinese Maotai-flavor liquor. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 166(2), 323–330.

Original Research

Identification of Stress-Responsive Transcription Factors Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase through Co-expression Network Analysis under Drought, Heat, and Salinity Conditions in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*)

Firat Kurt¹, Ertugrul Filiz^{2,*}

Abstract

Cysteine desulfurases are essential enzymes involved in sulfur metabolism, redox regulation, and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) signalling, especially under abiotic stress conditions. This study aimed to explore the gene networks associated with a *cysteine desulfurase* gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) in *Solanum tuberosum* exposed to drought, heat, and salinity. A subset of RNA-Seq data (*SRA029323*) were analysed using the Tuxedo pipeline on the Galaxy platform, and $\log_2(FC)$ values were used to assess gene co-expression. A total of 2,397 genes showed strong positive correlation ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene, including 201 transcription factors and kinases identified from the iTAK database. Functional annotation revealed that the top co-expressed genes are involved in oxidative stress response, signal transduction, and mitochondrial respiration. Notably, a cytochrome-c oxidase involved in proton transport and copper binding (*PGSC0003DMT400080385*) and a putative membrane protein (*PGSC0003DMT400065426*) were highly upregulated under drought and heat stress, suggesting their role in stress adaptation. Conversely, some uncharacterized genes (e.g., *PGSC0003DMT400096412* and *PGSC0003DMT400022675*) were strongly downregulated under salinity and drought. Network analysis positioned the *cysteine desulfurase* gene as a central hub linking multiple stress-responsive TF and kinase families, including AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH. These findings contribute to a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms behind abiotic stress responses in *potato* and may guide future breeding or genetic engineering strategies aimed at improving stress resilience in crops.

Keywords

Mycoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, Solid-state fermentation, proximate analysis, amino acids.

1 Mus Alparslan University, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Department of Plant Production and Technologies, Mus, Turkey

2 Duzce University, Cilimli Vocational School, Cilimli, Turkey

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: ertugrulfiliz@gmail.com, firat.kurt.usa@gmail.com

Citation: Kurt, F., Filiz, E. (2025). Identification of Stress-Responsive Transcription Factors Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase through Co-expression Network Analysis under Drought, Heat, and Salinity Conditions in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*). *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 20.05.2025 / **Accepted:** 24.09.2025 / **Published:** 12.12.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.22736>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Identifikacija transkripcijskih faktorjev, ki se odzivajo na stres in sodelujejo s cisteinsko desulfurazo preko analize mreže soizražanja v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti pri krompirju (*Solanum tuberosum*)

Izvleček

Cisteinska desulfuraza je pomemben encim, ki sodeluje v presnovi žvepla, regulaciji redoks potenciala in signalizaciji vodikovega sulfida (H₂S), zlasti v pogojih abiotičnega stresa. Namen te študije je bil raziskati genetske mreže, povezane z genom *cisteinske desulfuraze* (PGSC0003DMT400078713) v *Solanum tuberosum*, izpostavljenem suši, vročini in slanosti. Analizirana je bila podmnožica podatkov RNA-Seq (SRA029323) z uporabo protokola Tuxedo na platformi Galaxy, vrednosti log₂(FC) pa so bile uporabljene za oceno soekspresije genov. 2397 genov je pokazalo močno pozitivno korelacijo ($r \geq 0,90$) s ciljnim genom, vključno z 201 transkripcijskimi faktorji in kinazami, identificiranimi iz baze podatkov iTAK. Funkcionalna opomba je pokazala, da so geni z najvišjo soekspresijo vključeni v odziv na oksidativni stres, signalno transdukcijo in mitohondrijsko dihanje. Zlasti *citokrom-c oksidaza*, vključena v transport protonov in vezavo bakra (PGSC0003DMT400080385) ter domnevni membranski protein (PGSC0003DMT400065426) so bili močno povečano ekspresijo v suši in toplotnem stresu, kar kaže na njuno vlogo pri prilagajanju na stres. Nasprotno pa so bili nekateri neznaki geni (npr. PGSC0003DMT400096412 in PGSC0003DMT400022675) močno zmanjšani v slanosti in suši. Mrežna analiza je gen *cistein desulfuraza* umestila kot osrednji vozlišče, ki povezuje več družin TF in kinaz, ki se odzivajo na stres, vključno z AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC in bHLH. Ti izsledki prispevajo k boljšemu razumevanju molekularnih mehanizmov, ki stojijo za odzivi na abiotični stres pri *krompirju*, in lahko usmerjajo prihodnje strategije vzreje ali genske tehnologije, namenjene izboljšanju odpornosti pridelkov na stres.

Ključne besede

abiotični stres, ekspresija genov, analiza koekspresije, bioinformatika, presnova žvepla

Introduction

Cysteine desulfurases (CDs), a class of pyridoxal 5'-phosphate (PLP)-dependent enzymes, are indispensable for sulfur metabolism across all organisms. These enzymes catalyse the desulfuration of *L*-cysteine, breaking the carbon-sulfur bond to form a persulfide (-SSH) on a conserved cysteine and releasing alanine (Caubrière et al., 2023). In plants, *cysteine* serves dual roles: as a proteinogenic amino acid and as a precursor for critical biomolecules such as glutathione (GSH), methionine, vitamins (e.g., *biotin*, *thiamine*), and cofactors such as *Fe-S* clusters, *molybdenum cofactor* (Moco) and *S-adenosylmethionine* (Gotor et al., 2015; Tian et al., 2024; Vojtovič et al., 2021). This highlights the key role of *cysteine desulfurases* in plant growth and stress response.

Plant *cysteine desulfurases*, such as mitochondrial *AtNFS1* and chloroplast-localised *AtNFS2/SUFS*, are pivotal for *Fe-S* cluster biosynthesis, a process essential for electron transport, photosynthesis, and DNA repair (Caubrière

et al., 2023). These enzymes transfer sulfur from cysteine to scaffold proteins (e.g., *SUFBC2D*) in coordination with sulfur-relay regulators like *SUFE*. *Cysteine desulfurases*, including *ABA3*, are also involved in *Moco* sulfuration, an essential cytosolic step needed to activate enzymes such as *nitrate reductase* (Caubrière et al., 2023). These enzymes also produce H₂S, a gas that acts as a signalling molecule during stress. For instance, *DES1* (*At5g28030*), a cytosolic enzyme, breaks down *cysteine* into H₂S, *pyruvate*, and *ammonia*, helping to regulate redox balance and autophagy (Jia et al., 2016; Z. Liu et al., 2024). Mitochondrial *β-cyanoalanine synthase* (CAS-C1) also generates H₂S during cyanide detoxification, while *O-acetylserine(thiol) lyase* (OASTL) both synthesises and degrades *cysteine*, maintaining balance across different cell compartments (Khan et al., 2022; Z. Liu et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2022).

The regulatory interplay between *cysteine* synthesis and degradation is governed by the *cysteine synthase complex*, a hetero-oligomer of *serine acetyltransferase* (SAT) and

OASTL, which fine-tunes *cysteine* production in response to sulfur availability (Romero et al., 2014; H. Liu & Xue, 2021). However, certain *OASTL* family members, such as *DES1*, preferentially degrade *cysteine*, highlighting a dynamic equilibrium between anabolic and catabolic pathways (Z. Liu et al., 2024). The resultant H_2S mediates *persulfidation* (*S-sulfhydration*), a post-translational modification that alters protein function by turning $-SH$ groups into $-SSH$ (Aroca et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022). This affects many pathways like the *TCA cycle*, *glycolysis*, and *autophagy*, and works with *ABA signalling* to control stomatal closure and stress tolerance (Khan et al., 2022; Vojtovič et al., 2021).

Cysteine degradation products further influence plant metabolism: *pyruvate* fuels respiration, *ammonia* is assimilated into nitrogen metabolism, and H_2S enhances tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and heavy metal toxicity (Tian et al., 2024; Z. Liu et al., 2024). Compartmentalisation of these processes—via cytosolic *DES1*, mitochondrial *CAS-C1*, and chloroplast NFS-like enzymes—ensures spatial regulation of sulfur flux (Yang et al., 2022; Caubrière et al., 2023). Despite these advances, how *cysteine desulfurase* activity, H_2S signalling, and stress adaptation are connected is still not fully understood.

This study aims to understand how *cysteine desulfurase* interacts with other genes in *Solanum tuberosum* (potato) under drought, heat, and salinity stress conditions. The main focus is to find transcription factors and kinases that may take part in these stress-related gene networks. By combining RNA-Seq-based co-expression analysis with information about the functions of regulatory proteins, it aims to uncover molecular pathways linked to *cysteine desulfurases*. Since *cysteine desulfurases* play key roles in sulfur metabolism, redox balance, and hydrogen sulfide signalling, it is important to learn which genes they work with during stress. This knowledge can help us find important regulatory points that support stress adaptation in potato. These insights could support breeding or genetic engineering efforts to improve stress tolerance in potatoes.

Materials and Methods

This study used RNA-Seq expression data generated by the Potato Genome Sequencing Consortium (PGSC) for the reference genotype DM1-3 Phureja (Xu et al., 2011; Massa et al., 2011). The raw sequencing data were retrieved from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession

SRA029323, associated with BioProject PRJEB2430. From this comprehensive dataset, only the expression data corresponding specifically to abiotic stress conditions—heat (35 °C), salinity (150 mM NaCl), and drought (260 μ M mannitol)—were selected for analysis.

RNA-Seq Data Processing and Expression Analysis

At the time of analysis, the subset of RNA-Seq data was processed using the Tuxedo protocol (Trapnell et al., 2012), which was then available as a predefined workflow on the Galaxy platform (Afgan et al., 2016). Although this exact pipeline is no longer present on current versions of Galaxy, all steps were documented and consistently applied to the dataset.

Raw sequencing reads in FASTQ format were aligned to the *Solanum tuberosum* reference genome (version 4.03, from Phytozome v12.1) using TopHat (Trapnell et al., 2009). TopHat is a splice-aware aligner that first detects potential exon-exon junctions and then maps the reads using Bowtie (Langmead et al., 2009). The output consisted of sorted and indexed BAM files showing the genomic locations of aligned reads.

The aligned reads were then used in Cufflinks (Trapnell et al., 2010) for reference-guided transcript assembly and expression quantification. To enable comparison across samples, transcript assemblies were merged using Cuffmerge, and Cuffcompare was used to match assembled transcripts with the reference annotation. Although differential expression analysis was performed using Cuffdiff, this study did not rely on its p-value outputs for filtering. Instead, the $\log_2(\text{Fold Change})$ ($\log_2(FC)$) values obtained from Cuffdiff were directly used for gene expression profiling and co-expression analysis to assess relative expression changes under stress conditions.

Preparation and Normalisation of Gene Expression Data

Instead of using absolute expression levels (FPKM), $\log_2(FC)$ values were utilised to represent the relative gene expression changes under stress conditions compared to the control. The $\log_2(FC)$ values were derived from the ratio of treatment to control expression levels. In this dataset, positive values indicate upregulation, while negative values indicate downregulation of the gene under the specific

stress condition. These $\log_2(FC)$ values were subsequently used for heatmap construction and co-expression analysis to identify genes showing similar regulation patterns.

Co-expression-Based Identification of TFs and Kinases

To identify co-expression relationships, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated for each gene pair using $\log_2(FC)$ values. Gene pairs with a correlation coefficient of $r \geq 0.90$ were considered to be strongly co-expressed (Song et al., 2012).

A curated list of transcription factors (TFs) and kinases was retrieved from the iTAK database (Zheng et al., 2016), and these regulatory genes were matched against the co-expression results to identify TFs and kinases co-expressed with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene. P-values were not used as filters; instead, the stringent correlation threshold was employed to ensure high-confidence network construction.

Although *p*-values were not used to filter correlations, the high threshold of $r \geq 0.90$ was chosen to ensure the biological relevance of co-expression links and to reduce the risk of false positives. This approach aligns with previous co-expression studies (e.g., Song et al., 2012). Statistical significance values were not prioritised, as the primary objective was to construct a high-confidence interaction network rather than to test pairwise gene associations individually.

Annotation and Data Visualisation

The top upregulated and downregulated genes co-expressed with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene were annotated using the BioMart tool available in Ensembl Plants (Kinsella et al., 2011; Kersey et al., 2016). Gene-gene interactions, including transcription factors and kinases associated with the target gene, were visualised through correlation matrices and co-expression networks using Cytoscape software (Shannon et al., 2003).

Results

GO Annotation of Key Genes Interacting with *Cysteine Desulfurase*

Functional annotation of the top upregulated and downregulated genes co-expressed with the *cysteine desul-*

furase gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) revealed their involvement in various biological processes, particularly those related to stress responses, cellular signalling, and metabolism (Table 1; Figure 2).

For example, *PGSC0003DMT400080385* is associated with cytochrome-c oxidase activity, proton transmembrane transport, and copper ion binding, indicating a role in mitochondrial respiration and oxidative stress defence. *PGSC0003DMT400065426*, encoding a putative membrane protein, showed strong expression under both drought and heat stress, suggesting involvement in membrane stability and transport.

Stress-responsive transcription factors were also prominent. *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF family) and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB family) are known regulators of abiotic stress adaptation. Genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400006531* (a guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor) and *PGSC0003DMT400051014* (defence-related) point to signalling functions. Other genes were linked to mitochondrial and chloroplast processes, including *PGSC0003DMT400038370* (ubiquinone biosynthesis) and *PGSC0003DMT400023336* (regulation of the pentose phosphate cycle).

Genes involved in protein metabolism were also identified, such as *PGSC0003DMT400010044* and *PGSC0003DMT400039544*, which relate to protease activity and inhibition, respectively. Additionally, *PGSC0003DMT400052057* (a WRKY TF) was associated with phosphate ion transport and nuclear localisation.

Notably, *PGSC0003DMT400022675* and *PGSC0003DMT400023728* lacked functional annotation but showed significant expression changes under stress, suggesting potential novel regulatory roles that warrant further investigation.

Collectively, these co-expressed genes reflect a coordinated response involving transcriptional regulation, redox balance, membrane integrity, and metabolic adjustment. These insights strengthen the hypothesis that *cysteine desulfurase* acts as a regulatory hub under abiotic stress.

Expression of Key Genes Interacting with *Cysteine Desulfurase*

Expression profiles of the top genes co-expressed (Pearson $r > 0.90$) with the *cysteine desulfurase* gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*) were assessed under drought, heat, and salinity stress conditions.

Tabela 1. Gene Ontology-based functional annotation of the top upregulated and most downregulated genes interacting with *cysteine desulfurase*.

Table 1. Funkcionalna anotacija na podlagi genetske ontologije genov, ki interagirajo s *cisteinsko desulfurazo* z najbolj povečano in zmanjšano ekspresijo. genov.

Gene stable ID	Transcript stable ID	Function Summary
The most up-regulated genes		
PGSC0003DMG400002546	PGSC0003DMT400006531	Guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity, plasma membrane
PGSC0003DMG400021857	PGSC0003DMT400056255	MYB transcription factor
PGSC0003DMG400024606	PGSC0003DMT400063264	AP2/ERF transcription factor family
PGSC0003DMG401025438	PGSC0003DMT400065426	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG402014805	PGSC0003DMT400038370	Mitochondrion, protein-containing complex binding, ubiquinone biosynthesis
PGSC0003DMG400009042	PGSC0003DMT400023336	Chloroplast, negative regulation of the reductive pentose-phosphate cycle
PGSC0003DMG400019806	PGSC0003DMT400051014	Defense response
PGSC0003DMG401031302	PGSC0003DMT400080385	Cytochrome-c oxidase, proton transport, copper binding, membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG400028730	PGSC0003DMT400073927	Protein kinase activity
The most down-regulated genes		
PGSC0003DMG400009179	PGSC0003DMT400023728	Not annotated
PGSC0003DMG400015290	PGSC0003DMT400039544	Serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity
PGSC0003DMG400016970	PGSC0003DMT400043696	Membrane, phospholipid metabolic process
PGSC0003DMG402008792	PGSC0003DMT400022675	Not annotated
PGSC0003DMG400020206	PGSC0003DMT400052057	Transcription regulation, phosphate ion transport, and the nucleus
PGSC0003DMG400003044	PGSC0003DMT400007870	Thaumatococcus domain-containing protein
PGSC0003DMG402003937	PGSC0003DMT400010044	Proteolysis, serine-type endopeptidase activity
PGSC0003DMG400004549	PGSC0003DMT400011566	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG401025920	PGSC0003DMT400066701	Membrane protein
PGSC0003DMG400028369	PGSC0003DMT400072921	Nuclear transport factor

As shown in Figure 1 and summarised in Table 1, two genes—*PGSC0003DMT400065426* (membrane protein) and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* (cytochrome-c oxidase)—exhibited exceptionally high expression levels, particularly under heat and drought. *PGSC0003DMT400065426* reached a peak of $\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 28 under heat stress, while *PGSC0003DMT400080385* showed strong expression under both heat ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 27) and drought ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 24), suggesting putative *de novo* induction and critical roles in membrane stabilisation and mitochondrial function during stress adaptation.

In contrast, *PGSC0003DMT400022675* and *PGSC0003DMT400023728*, both unannotated, were

markedly downregulated under salinity and drought, as illustrated in Figure 2, implying their potential role in suppressing stress pathways.

Several genes showed significant expression ($\log_2(FC)$ value of 7–15) under heat stress, indicating selective activation in response to elevated temperature. These include: *PGSC0003DMT400038370* (ubiquinone biosynthesis in mitochondria), *PGSC0003DMT400023336* (negative regulator of the pentose-phosphate cycle in chloroplasts), and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB transcription factor).

Additionally, modest expression ($\log_2(FC)$ value of ~ 3) was observed under both drought and salinity for several genes, including: *PGSC0003DMT400073927* (protein

kinase), *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF TF), *PGSC0003DMT400006531* (guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor), and *PGSC0003DMT400051014* (defence-related gene), pointing to a modest but shared response mechanism.

Overall, these results highlight *PGSC0003DMT400065426* and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* as strong candidates for future functional validation studies, given their consistent and elevated expression under multiple abiotic stress conditions.

Co-expression Network of TFs and Kinases Interacting with Cysteine Desulfurase

To identify key regulatory components associated with *cysteine desulfurase* under stress, a co-expression network was constructed based on genes showing strong positive correlation ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene (*PGSC0003DMT400078713*). As shown in Figure 3, the resulting network comprises 202 nodes and 2,398 edges, representing highly co-expressed transcription factors (TFs) and kinases.

Annotation using the iTAK database classified the nodes into several regulatory families: 130 kinases, 10 MYB, 7 MYB-related, 12 bHLH, five bZIP, 7 C2H2, 3 C2C2-GATA, 6 NAC, 7 AP2/ERF-ERF, 2 AP2/ERF-AP2, 4 DOF, 3 HSF, 3 TCP, 1 SBP, and 1 Trihelix.

The central location of *cysteine desulfurase* in the network highlights its potential role as a regulatory hub, integrating both transcriptional and post-translational mechanisms. In particular, the presence of stress-related TF families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH—alongside a large number of kinases—suggests a coordinated network involving both gene expression modulation and phosphorylation signalling.

This integrated network underscores the multifunctional nature of *cysteine desulfurase* in stress response pathways and provides a basis for future functional validation of key TFs and kinases as potential regulators of abiotic stress tolerance in *Solanum tuberosum* (potato).

Discussion

Cysteine desulfurases (CDs) play pivotal roles in sulfur metabolism and the biosynthesis of cofactors such as *iron-sulfur (Fe-S) clusters* and *molybdenum cofactor*

(*Moco*), both of which are essential for redox regulation and metabolic stability under stress (Caubrière et al., 2023; Gotor et al., 2015). In this study, we analysed the co-expression profile of the predicted *cysteine desulfurase* gene *PGSC0003DMT400078713* in *Solanum tuberosum* under drought, heat, and salinity stress using RNA-Seq data. The results revealed 2,397 strongly co-expressed genes ($r \geq 0.90$), many of which are associated with transcriptional regulation, signalling pathways, redox balance, and membrane transport.

From these, 201 transcription factors and kinases were identified using the iTAK database. Notably, families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bZIP were prevalent, all known to mediate abiotic stress responses (Romero et al., 2014; Tian et al., 2024). For example, *PGSC0003DMT400063264* (AP2/ERF) and *PGSC0003DMT400056255* (MYB) were co-expressed with the target gene, implying their involvement in regulating sulfur-related or oxidative stress responses, possibly via *H₂S* or *Fe-S cluster*-dependent signalling (Liu et al., 2024).

Among the top upregulated genes, *PGSC0003DMT400065426* (a membrane protein) and *PGSC0003DMT400080385* (*cytochrome-c oxidase*) showed increased expression under heat and drought stress, suggesting their roles in membrane transport and mitochondrial redox regulation (Yang et al., 2022). Their functions are consistent with the subcellular roles of *cysteine desulfurases* in mitochondria and chloroplasts (Caubrière et al., 2023), where *Fe-S clusters* are synthesised, and oxidative stress is managed.

Conversely, genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400023728* and *PGSC0003DMT400096412*, which lack functional annotation, were consistently downregulated under drought and salinity. Their suppression may reflect stress-induced inhibition of sulfur-rich metabolic pathways or shifts in redox balance due to disrupted *Fe-S* assembly or *H₂S* signalling (Vojtovič et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022).

GO analysis of co-expressed genes revealed enrichment in *proton transport*, *ubiquinone biosynthesis*, *proteolysis regulation*, and *intracellular signalling*. Of particular interest is *PGSC0003DMT400006531*, a guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor, which may link membrane signalling to sulfur metabolism via persulfidation or *H₂S*-mediated pathways (Aroca et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2024).

Taken together, the co-expression patterns of *PGSC0003DMT400078713* support its role as a central regulator in stress adaptation, likely coordinating transcrip-

Figure 1. The expression levels of the top co-expressed genes ($r > 0.9$) with cysteine desulfurase under drought, heat, and salinity conditions.

Slika 1. Ravní izražanja najbolj soizraženih genov ($r > 0,9$) s cisteinsko desulfurazo v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti.

Figure 2. The expression levels of the most down-regulated genes ($r > 0.9$) co-expressed with cysteine desulfurase under drought, heat, and salinity conditions.

Slika 2. Ravní izražanja najbolj navzdol reguliranih genov ($r > 0,9$), ki se soizražajo s cisteinsko desulfurazo v pogojih suše, vročine in slanosti.

Figure 3. Co-expression network of transcription factors and kinases co-expressed with cysteine desulfurase in *Solanum tuberosum*. (A) The network includes 202 nodes and 2398 edges based on Pearson $r \geq 0.90$. (B) Nodes are colour-coded by gene family as classified using the iTAK database.

Slika 3. Mreža soizražanja transkripcijskih faktorjev in kinaz, ki se soizražajo s cisteinsko desulfurazo v *Solanum tuberosum*. (A) Mreža vključuje 202 vozlišča in 2398 robov na podlagi Pearsonovega $r \geq 0,90$. (B) Vozlišča so barvno označena po genih družinah, kot so razvrščene v bazi podatkov iTAK.

tional networks, redox signalling, and post-translational modifications under abiotic stress. These findings highlight the multifunctional nature of *cysteine desulfurases* and provide a foundation for future research into targeted stress resilience strategies in potato.

Conclusion

This study investigated the gene networks involving *cysteine desulfurases* in *Solanum tuberosum* under abiotic stress, with a particular focus on transcription factors (TFs) and kinases co-expressed with the gene *PGSC0003DMT400078713* during drought, heat, and salinity exposure. Through co-expression analysis of RNA-Seq data, combined with functional annotation and network visualisation, 2,397 genes were identified as strongly correlated ($r \geq 0.90$) with the target gene. Among these, 201 TFs and kinases belonged to well-known stress-responsive families such as AP2/ERF, MYB, NAC, and bHLH, reflecting a coordinated regulatory network involving both transcriptional and post-translational mechanisms.

Notably, a membrane-associated protein (*PGSC0003DMT400065426*) and a *cytochrome-c oxidase* (*PGSC0003DMT400080385*) involved in redox regulation and mitochondrial respiration were strongly upregulated under heat and drought, suggesting their functional role in redox homeostasis and energy metabolism. In contrast, uncharacterized genes such as *PGSC0003DMT400096412* and *PGSC0003DMT400022675* were consistently downregulated under salinity and drought, indicating possible involvement in suppressed or stress-inhibited pathways.

Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment highlighted processes such as *oxidative stress response*, *signal transduction*, *proteolysis regulation*, and *subcellular localisation*, further supporting the biological diversity of the genes co-expressed with *cysteine desulfurase*.

Together, these findings enhance our understanding of the molecular networks governing abiotic stress tolerance in *potato* and underscore the central role of *cysteine desulfurases* in *sulfur metabolism* and *redox signalling*. The identified candidate genes provide a basis for future functional validation and genetic improvement strategies aimed at enhancing stress resilience in *potato* cultivars.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, F.K.; methodology, F.K.; software, F.K.; validation, F.K. and E.F.; formal analysis, F.K.; investigation, F.K.; resources, E.F.; data curation, E.F.; writing—original draft preparation, F.K.; writing—review and editing, F.K. and E.F.; visualization, F.K.; supervision, E.F.; project administration, F.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Recep Vatansver for providing the processed RNA-seq dataset and for his assistance regarding the details of the bioinformatic analysis

Funding

This research received no external funding

Data Availability

RNA-Seq expression data generated by the Potato Genome Sequencing Consortium (PGSC) for the reference genotype DM1-3 were downloaded from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession SRA029323, associated with BioProject PRJEB2430. The research data generated during the current study and used for the analyses are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17798426>.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

- Afgan, E., Baker, D., van den Beek, M., Blankenberg, D., Bouvier, D., Čech, M., ... Goecks, J. (2016). The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible and collaborative biomedical analyses: 2016 update. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(W1), W3–W10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw343>
- Aroca, A., Gotor, C., Bassham, D. C., & Romero, L. C. (2020). Hydrogen sulfide: From a toxic molecule to a key molecule of cell life. *Antioxidants*, 9(7), 621. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9070621>
- Caubrière, D., Moseler, A., Rouhier, N., & Couturier, J. (2023). Diversity and roles of cysteine desulfurases in photosynthetic organisms. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 74(11), 3345–3360. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erad065>
- Das, R. R., Pradhan, S., & Parida, A. (2020). De-novo transcriptome analysis unveils differentially expressed genes regulating drought and salt stress response in *Panicum sumatrense*. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 78118. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78118-3>
- Edgar, R., Domrachev, M., & Lash, A. E. (2002). Gene Expression Omnibus: NCBI gene expression and hybridization array data repository. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 30(1), 207–210. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/30.1.207>
- Gotor, C., Laureano-Marín, A. M., Moreno, I., Aroca, Á., García, I., & Romero, L. C. (2015). Signaling in the plant cytosol: Cysteine or sulfide? *Amino Acids*, 47(10), 2155–2164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-014-1786-z>
- Heis, M. D., Dítter, E. M., de Oliveira, L. A., Frazzon, A. P. G., Margis, R., & Frazzon, J. (2011). Differential expression of cysteine desulfurases in soybean. *BMC Plant Biology*, 11, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2229-11-166>
- Jia, H., Wang, X., Dou, Y., Liu, D., Si, W., Fang, H., Zhao, C., Chen, S., Xi, J., & Li, J. (2016). Hydrogen sulfide-cysteine cycle system enhances cadmium tolerance through alleviating cadmium-induced oxidative stress and ion toxicity in *Arabidopsis* roots. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 39702. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep39702>
- Jin, Z., Sun, L., Yang, G., & Pei, Y. (2018). Hydrogen sulfide regulates energy production to delay leaf senescence induced by drought stress in *Arabidopsis*. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1722. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01722>
- Kersey, P. J., Allen, J. E., Armean, I., Boddu, S., Bolt, B. J., Carvalho-Silva, D., Christensen, M., Davis, P., Falin, L. J., Grabmueller, C., Humphrey, J., Kerhornou, A., Khobova, J., Aranganathan, N. K., Langridge, N., Lowy, E., McDowall, M. D., Maheswari, U., Nuhn, M., ... Staines, D. M. (2016). Ensembl Genomes 2016: More genomes, more complexity. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D574–D580. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1209>
- Khan, M. S. S., Islam, F., Ye, Y., Ashline, M., Wang, D., Zhao, B., Fu, Z. Q., & Chen, J. (2022). The interplay between hydrogen sulfide and phytohormone signaling pathways under challenging environments. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(8), 4272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23084272>
- Kinsella, R. J., Kähäri, A., Haider, S., Zamora, J., Proctor, G., Spudich, G., Almeida-King, J., Staines, D., Derwent, P., Kerhornou, A., Kersey, P., & Flicek, P. (2011). Ensembl BioMarts: A hub for data retrieval across taxonomic space. *Database: The Journal of Biological Databases and Curation*, 2011, bar030. <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/bar030>
- Langmead, B., Trapnell, C., Pop, M., & Salzberg, S. L. (2009). Ultrafast and memory-efficient alignment of short DNA sequences to the human genome. *Genome Biology*, 10(3), R25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2009-10-3-r25>
- Li, Q., Qin, Y., Hu, X., Li, G., Ding, H., Xiong, X., & Wang, W. (2020). Transcriptome analysis uncovers the gene expression profile of salt-stressed potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 62057. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-62057-0>
- Liu, H., & Xue, S. (2021). Interplay between hydrogen sulfide and other signaling molecules in the regulation of guard cell signaling and abiotic/biotic stress response. *Plant Communications*, 2(3), 100179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xplc.2021.100179>
- Liu, M., Li, Y., Li, G., Dong, T., Liu, S., Liu, P., & Wang, G. Q. (2020). Overexpression of *StCYS1* gene enhances tolerance to salt stress in the transgenic potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) plant. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 19(9), 2239–2246. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(20\)63262-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(20)63262-2)
- Liu, Z., Liu, Y., & Liao, W. (2024). Hydrogen sulfide in the oxidative stress response of plants: Crosstalk with reactive oxygen species. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(3), 1935. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25031935>
- Nicolas, M., Bouma, J., Venema, J. H., van der Schoot, H., Verstappen, F., de Zeeuw, T., Langedijk, S. E., Boer, D., Bucher, J., Staal, M., Krom, B., Elzenga, J. T. M., Visser, R. G. F., Testerink, C., & Karlova, R. (2025). Potato cultivars use distinct mechanisms for salt stress acclimation. *Plant Stress*, 15, 100798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stress.2025.100798>
- Massa, A. N., Childs, K. L., Lin, H., Bryan, G. J., Giuliano, G., & Buell, C. R. (2011). The transcriptome of the reference potato genome *Solanum tuberosum* Group Phureja clone DM1-3 516R44. *PLoS One*, 6(10), e26801. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0026801>
- Pandey, A. K., & Gautam, A. (2020). Stress responsive gene regulation in relation to hydrogen sulfide in plants under abiotic stress. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 168(2), 511–525. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pp1.13064>
- Romero, L. C., Aroca, M. Á., Laureano-Marín, A. M., Moreno, I., García, I., & Gotor, C. (2014). Cysteine and cysteine-related signaling pathways in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Molecular Plant*, 7(2), 264–276. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mp/sst168>
- Shannon, P., Markiel, A., Ozier, O., Baliga, N. S., Wang, J. T., Ramage, D., ... Ideker, T. (2003). Cytoscape: A software environment for integrated models of biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Research*, 13(11), 2498–2504. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.1239303>
- Song, L., Langfelder, P., & Horvath, S. (2012). Comparison of co-expression measures: Mutual information, correlation, and model-based indices. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 13, 328. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-13-328>
- Tang, Q., Zhou, Y., Zhou, D., Hong, J., Zhao, L., Bu, G., Chen, F., & Tang, L. (2023). The ethylene response factor RAP2.6 plays a positive role in the regulation of selenium tolerance in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 99(2), 241–250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10725-022-00901-1>
- Tian, T., Zhu, J., Li, Z., Wang, W., Bao, M., Qiu, X., Yao, P., Bi, Z., Sun, C., Li, Y., Liu, Z., & Liu, Y. (2024). Comprehensive analysis of the OASTL gene family in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) and its expression under abiotic stress. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(23), 13170. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms252313170>

- Trapnell, C., Pachter, L., & Salzberg, S. L. (2009). TopHat: Discovering splice junctions with RNA-Seq. *Bioinformatics*, 25(9), 1105–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp120>
- Trapnell, C., Williams, B. A., Pertea, G., Mortazavi, A., Kwan, G., van Baren, M. J., ... Pachter, L. (2010). Transcript assembly and quantification by RNA-Seq reveals unannotated transcripts and isoform switching during cell differentiation. *Nature Biotechnology*, 28(5), 511–515. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1621>
- Trapnell, C., Roberts, A., Goff, L., Pertea, G., Kim, D., Kelley, D. R., Pimentel, H., Salzberg, S. L., Rinn, J. L., & Pachter, L. (2012). Differential gene and transcript expression analysis of RNA-seq experiments with TopHat and Cufflinks. *Nature Protocols*, 7(3), 562–578. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2012.016>
- Vojtovič, D., Luhová, L., & Petřivalský, M. (2021). Something smells bad to plant pathogens: Production of hydrogen sulfide in plants and its role in plant defence responses. *Journal of Advanced Research*, 27, 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2020.09.005>
- Xu, X., Pan, S., Cheng, S., Zhang, B., Mu, D., Ni, P., ... Visser, R. G. F. (2011). Genome sequence and analysis of the tuber crop potato. *Nature*, 475, 189–195. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10158>
- Yang, Z., Wang, X., Feng, J., & Zhu, S. (2022). Biological functions of hydrogen sulfide in plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(23), 15107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232315107>
- Zheng, Y., Jiao, C., Sun, H., Rosli, H. G., Pombo, M. A., Zhang, P., ... Fei, Z. (2016). iTAK: A program for genome-wide prediction and classification of plant transcription factors, transcriptional regulators, and protein kinases. *Molecular Plant*, 9(12), 1667–1670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molp.2016.09.014>

Original Research

Mass of amalgam restorations and its significance for assessing the environmental impact of dental amalgam

Iztok Štampfelj^{1,2,*}, Neža Gozdnikar^{3†}, Nika Junež^{3†}, Anja Konjar^{3†}, Lorena Lina Perpar^{3†}, Eva Polšak^{3†}

Abstract

Although many countries are phasing out dental amalgam use, numerous amalgam restorations will remain in the mouths of people. Reliable estimates of the mass of amalgam restorations are severely lacking, making it difficult to assess the contribution of dental amalgam to environmental pollution with mercury. In this study, the mass of 245 amalgam restorations was measured after mechanical removal from permanent teeth extracted in Slovenia. The differences in restoration mass according to the tooth type (premolars, upper molars, lower molars) and the number of amalgam-restored surfaces (1, 2, \geq 3) were assessed by using a two-way analysis of variance. Predictions were made using a multiple linear regression model. The mass of restorations ranged from 0.03 to 3.00 g with a mean value of 0.71 g. The number of restored surfaces was a more important explanatory variable (effect size 0.54, 95% CI 0.48–0.61) than the tooth type (effect size 0.25, 95% CI 0.17–0.33). A multiple linear regression model explained 61% of the variation in restoration mass. This study provides mass estimates for amalgam restorations based on the analysis of a Slovenian sample and supports their association with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type.

Keywords

dental amalgam, mercury, permanent teeth, air pollution.

1 University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Dental Diseases and Dental Morphology, Hrvatski trg 6, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

2 Present address: University of Maribor, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Dental Diseases and Endodontics, Taborska ulica 8, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia

3 University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Medicine, Vrazov trg 2, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: iztok.stampfelj1@um.si

Citation: Štampfelj, I., Gozdnikar, N., Junež, N., Konjar, A., Perpar, L. L., Polšak, E. (2025). Mass of amalgam restorations and its significance for assessing the environmental impact of dental amalgam. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 19.10.2025 / **Accepted:** 17.12.2025 /

Published: 18.12.2025

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.24466>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Masa amalgamskih restavracij in njen pomen za ovrednotenje okoljskega vpliva dentalnega amalgama

Izvleček

Kljub postopnemu opuščanju uporabe dentalnega amalgama v mnogih državah bodo v ustih ljudi ostale številne amalgamske restavracije. Zanesljivih ocen mase amalgamskih restavracij je zelo malo, kar otežuje določitev prispevka dentalnega amalgama k onesnaženju okolja z živim srebrom. V tej raziskavi je bila izmerjena masa 245 amalgamskih restavracij, ki so bile predhodno mehansko odstranjene iz stalnih zob, ekstrahiranih v Sloveniji. Razlike med masami restavracij glede na vrsto zoba (ličniki, zgornji kočniki in spodnji kočniki) in število amalgamsko obnovljenih zobnih ploskev (1, 2 in ≥ 3) so bile ovrednotene z dvosmerno analizo variance. Za izračun napovedi je bil uporabljen model multiple linearne regresije. Masa amalgamskih restavracij je bila od 0.03 do 3.00 g, njena povprečna vrednost pa 0.71 g. Število obnovljenih zobnih ploskev je bilo pomembnejša pojasnjevalna spremenljivka (velikost učinka = 0,54, 95 % IZ 0,48–0,61) kakor vrsta zoba (velikost učinka = 0,25, 95 % IZ 0,17–0,33). Model multiple linearne regresije je pojasnil 61 % variabilnosti mase restavracij. Raziskava prispeva ocene mase amalgamskih restavracij na podlagi analize slovenskega vzorca in potrjuje njihovo povezanost s številom obnovljenih zobnih ploskev in vrsto zoba.

Ključne besede

dentalni amalgam, živo srebro, stalni zobje, onesnaženje zraka.

Introduction

Mercury is a toxic heavy metal and, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO), one of the top 10 chemicals of major public health concern (WHO, 2024). The main target organs for mercury toxicity in humans are the brain, liver, and kidneys; fetuses and small children are particularly vulnerable because mercury adversely affects their development (Clarkson, 1997). Mercury occurs in three forms, which are all toxic: elemental (or metallic), inorganic, and organic (e.g., methylmercury, which is the most toxic). Elemental mercury is released into the environment as a result of natural processes, including geothermal activity and volcanism, but the largest emissions are related to human activities, including burning of fossil fuels (which contain mercury as a trace contaminant), generation of mercury-containing wastes, mercury use in industrial processes, in products, in dental applications, and in mining for mercury and for other minerals (Pacyna et al., 2010). Elemental mercury ultimately enters the aquatic ecosystems, where it is converted to methylmercury by microorganisms, and then bioaccumulates and biomagnifies as it ascends the aquatic food chain. Human exposure mainly occurs through consumption of fish and other seafood contaminated with

methylmercury and occupationally related inhalation of elemental mercury vapours (WHO, 2024).

Contemporary dental amalgam is a mixture of mercury with an alloy that is composed mostly of silver, tin, and copper (Powers & Wataha, 2017). Dental amalgam has been used extensively for almost 200 years because of its versatility as a direct-placement dental restorative material, excellent mechanical properties, ease of manipulation, clinical longevity of restorations, and low cost. Its disadvantages are inferior aesthetic appearance (due to colour mismatch with the tooth) and absence of adhesion to tooth structure. From the very beginning, there have been speculations suggesting a link between health problems and amalgam restorations (Hyson, 2006); however, in the set amalgam mercury is bound with stable metallic bonds and its absorption by the body, while detectable, does not approach the levels known to cause adverse health effects (Berglund, 1990; Bajsman et al., 2014). No other restorative material has been as thoroughly toxicologically evaluated as dental amalgam (Frankenberger et al., 2021). Notably, several scientific committees and professional organisations, including the Scientific Committee on Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks (SCENIHR) and the International Association for Dental Research (IADR), have affirmed the safety of

dental amalgam, except for patients with allergies to amalgam components or severe renal diseases (Pezelj-Ribarić et al., 2008; Rodríguez-Farre et al., 2016; Ajiboye et al., 2020).

Of greater concern are environmental risks and indirect health effects associated with releases of mercury from dental amalgam into the environment as a result of inappropriate amalgam waste management in dental practices and pollution from crematoriums due to vaporisation of amalgam restorations in the teeth of corpses during cremation. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the dental amalgam in 2010 contributed 21–32% and 9–13% to overall EU mercury emissions to the air and surface water, respectively (Ajiboye et al., 2020). Although many countries are phasing out dental amalgam use, the related environmental issues will remain relevant for decades to come due to the amount of existing amalgam restorations in the mouths of living people. In developed countries, the legislation requires the use of highly efficient amalgam-particle separators and ensures a regulated collection system for mercury-contaminated solid waste to minimise leakages from dental clinics to the environment. In contrast, no specific legislation applies to toxic emissions from crematoriums at the EU level, and the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has provided no specific recommendations for these facilities (Mari & Domingo, 2010). Moreover, crematorium emissions have not been the subject of the Minamata Con-

vention on Mercury, signed in 2013, which aims to reduce global mercury pollution (UNEP, 2024).

From a public health point of view, it is therefore important to accurately estimate the total potential contribution of crematoriums to the annual atmospheric flux of anthropogenic mercury. However, the lack of reliable data on the mass of amalgam restorations limits our ability to model these estimates using national oral health data, and rates of mortality and corpse cremation (Santarsiero et al., 2006; Piagno & Afshari, 2020). Additionally, the mass of mercury in the cremated body (Hg input), which is inferred from the mass of amalgam restorations, is an important variable in the assessment of the effectiveness of various abatement techniques available for reducing mercury emissions from crematoriums (Ohle et al., 2021).

Only one study from Canada has so far used a large sample of amalgam restorations (from both natural and anatomical replica teeth) and developed multiple regression models to predict their mass (Adegbelembo et al., 2004). Additionally, two US studies reported mean masses for samples of only 10 and 40 amalgam restorations (Reinhardt et al., 1983; Drummond et al., 2003). The aim of the present study was to estimate the mass of amalgam restorations in a Slovenian population; the predictors included in the model were the number of restored surfaces and the type of tooth (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of amalgam restorations (from left to right): (1) one-surface restoration on a lower first premolar, (2) two-surface restoration on an upper first premolar, (3) three-surface restoration on an upper first molar, (4) four-surface restoration on a lower first molar. Tooth surfaces: m. – mesial, d. – distal, b. – buccal, li. – lingual. Dotted lines indicate the boundaries between amalgam-restored tooth surfaces. Adapted from the first Slovenian textbook of dental anatomy (Logar, 1955).

Slika 1. Shematski prikaz amalgamskih restavracij (od leve proti desni): (1) enoploskovna restavracija na spodnjem prvem ličniku, (2) dvoploskovna restavracija na zgornjem prvem ličniku, (3) triploskovna restavracija na zgornjem prvem kočniku, (4) štiriploskovna restavracija na spodnjem prvem kočniku. Zobne ploskve: m. – mezialna, d. – distalna, b. – bukalna, li. – lingvalna. Pikčaste črte označujejo meje med amalgamsko obnovljenimi zobnimi ploskvami. Prirejeno po prvem slovenskem učbeniku anatomije zob (Logar, 1955).

Materials and Methods

Amalgam-restored permanent teeth

This study was approved by the Slovenian National Medical Ethics Committee (Approval No. 0120-160/2025-2711-3). The permanent teeth containing amalgam restorations were taken from a dental collection at the Faculty of Medicine in Ljubljana (Department of Dental Diseases and Dental Morphology). This collection is a repository of de-identified teeth approved for use in teaching and research. The restorations have been placed by dentists practising in Slovenia, but the time of placement was unknown.

Removal and weighing of amalgam restorations

The amalgam restorations were removed from their cavities by crushing the teeth between two metal hammers inside a transparent plastic bag to avoid losing any fractured pieces of amalgam. Under the Motic stereomicroscope (Model SMZ-161-TP, Hong Kong, China), each removed amalgam restoration was inspected, and any remnants of the underlying base material were removed using hand cures and petite round burs with a long neck (EndoTracer, Komet Dental, Lemgo, Germany) in a Synea WA-86-LT slow-speed handpiece (W&H Dentalwerk, Bürmoos, Austria). The contents of the plastic bag were placed on a sheet of white paper and scrutinised under the stereomicroscope for the presence of amalgam particles. Each amalgam restoration was weighed using an EW600-2M scale (Kern & Sohn, Balingen, Germany) to a precision of 0.01 g. In accordance with the Slovenian legislation (Government of the Republic of Slovenia, 2008), all amalgam restorations were stored under water in tightly capped containers before they were taken over by an authorised amalgam waste recycler.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were reported as means and standard deviation (SD). Normality of the data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The differences in restoration mass according to tooth type (premolars, upper molars, and lower molars) and number of restored surfaces (1, 2, and ≥ 3) were tested by using a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). *P*-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Holm method (Holm, 1979). A multi-

ple linear regression model was used to predict restoration mass, with results presented as 95% confidence intervals. *P*-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed in R 4.0.0 (R Core Team, 2025).

Results

In this study, 245 amalgam restorations were removed from 226 permanent teeth (78 premolars, 86 upper molars, and 62 lower molars). Figure 2 shows examples of removed amalgam restorations. The mass of amalgam restorations ranged from 0.03 to 3.00 g (both limits recorded in lower molars) with a mean value of 0.71 g (SD 0.60 g) (Table 1). The total weight of amalgam removed from 522 restored tooth surfaces was 173.41 g or 0.33 g per restored surface removed. In all tooth types, the mean mass of the restorations increased with the number of restored surfaces (Fig. 3). The mean mass of restorations was similar for upper and lower molars, regardless of the number of restored surfaces, while it was lower for premolars (Fig. 3).

The effects of the individual factors on the mass of the amalgam restorations and the interaction between them were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$ for both the tooth type and number of restored surfaces; $p = 0.014$ for the interaction). The result of the *post-hoc* analysis is shown in Fig. 4. For one restored surface, all three pairwise comparisons showed no significant differences between tooth types. In contrast, the upper molar vs. premolar and lower molar vs. premolar comparisons showed significant differences for two restored surfaces ($p < 0.001$) and for ≥ 3 restored surfaces ($p < 0.001$).

The linear regression model with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type as predictors explained 61% of the variation in the masses of restorations, hence failing to account for 39% of this variation. Considering the effect of each factor, the number of restored surfaces explained more variation (effect size = 0.54, 95% CI 0.48–0.61) than the tooth type (effect size = 0.25, 95% CI 0.17–0.33) and the between-factor interaction (effect size = 0.05, 95% CI 0.01–0.10). The predicted mean mass was highest with ≥ 3 restored surfaces and lowest with one restored surface, regardless of the type of tooth, but when comparing tooth types, premolars had the lowest predicted mass of amalgam restorations for all numbers of restored surfaces (Fig. 5).

Figure 2. Amalgam restorations removed from permanent teeth (from left to right): (1) one-surface restoration from an upper molar, (2) two-surface restoration from an upper premolar, (3) three-surface restoration from a lower molar, (4) four-surface restoration from an upper molar, and (5) five-surface restoration from an upper molar.

Slika 2. Amalgamske restavracije, odstranjene iz stalnih zob (od leve proti desni): (1) enoploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika, (2) dvoploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega ličnika, (3) triploskovna restavracija iz spodnjega kočnika, (4) štiriploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika in (5) petploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika.

Tabela 1. Summary of the masses of amalgam restorations (g).

Table 1. Masa amalgamskih restavracij (g)

No. of restored surfaces	Upper molar				Lower molar				Premolar				All			
	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI
1	26	0.32	0.22	0.23–0.41	26	0.29	0.19	0.22–0.37	25	0.10	0.04	0.09–0.12	77	0.24	0.19	0.20–0.28
2	24	0.87	0.40	0.7–1.04	21	0.84	0.47	0.63–1.05	41	0.37	0.20	0.30–0.43	86	0.62	0.42	0.53–0.71
≥3	40	1.40	0.56	1.22–1.58	21	1.43	0.65	1.13–1.72	21	0.74	0.30	0.60–0.87	82	1.24	0.60	1.11–1.37
All	90	0.95	0.63	0.81–1.08	68	0.81	0.65	0.65–0.97	87	0.38	0.30	0.31–0.44	245	0.71	0.60	0.63–0.78

n – number of restorations, SD – standard deviation, CI – confidence interval.

n – število restavracij, SD – standardni odklon, CI – interval zaupanja.

Figure 3. Mean mass of amalgam restorations with 95% confidence interval, according to tooth type and number of restored surfaces.

Slika 3. Povprečna masa amalgamskih restavracij s 95 % intervalom zaupanja glede na vrsto zoba in število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev.

Figure 4. Forest plot of the mean differences in mass of the amalgam restorations between the tooth types, according to the number of restored surfaces. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, CI – confidence interval, UM – upper molar, LM – lower molar, P – premolar.

Slika 4. Gozdni diagram povprečnih razlik v masi amalgamskih restavracij med vrstami zob glede na število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, CI – interval zaupanja, UM – zgornji kočnik, LM – spodnji kočnik, P – ličnik.

Figure 5. Predicted mean mass of amalgam restorations (and 95% confidence intervals), according to the tooth type and number of restored surfaces.

Slika 5. Napovedana povprečna masa amalgamskih restavracij (in 95-odstotni intervali zaupanja) glede na vrsto zoba in število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev.

Discussion

In the present study, there was a 100-fold difference between the mass of the lightest and heaviest amalgam restoration (0.03 and 3.00 g, respectively), which greatly exceeds the ranges reported by Takaoka et al. (2010) for Japanese (0.056–0.231 g) and dental materials manufacturer Vivadent (0.2–1.8 g) (Sobolewski, 2016); however, the size of the samples was not specified in these reports. Considering that dental amalgam contains approximately 50% of mercury by mass, our results indicate that during corpse cremation, from 0.015 to 1.5 g of mercury may be released from one amalgam restoration, corresponding to the disposal of 4 to 375 fluorescent bulbs; these, on average, contain 0.004 g of mercury (Mulligan et al., 2018).

Only data from the study by Adegbenbo et al. (2004) are available for a more detailed comparison with the results of the present study, but the methodological differences between them must first be evaluated. Firstly, our study sample consisted of restorations placed in natural teeth by Slovenian dentists, whereas the comparative sample consisted of restorations placed in both natural and anatomical replica teeth by Canadian dentists and dental students, respectively. Secondly, in our study, the amalgam restorations were isolated by crushing the teeth, weighed, and then stored for recycling, whereas the authors of the comparative research took an indirect approach of subtracting the tooth masses recorded before and after drilling away the amalgam restoration from the cavity. In this respect, the indirect method is non-destructive and leaves the extracted teeth usable (e.g., for pre-clinical teaching or training); however, it has potential shortcomings, including a time-consuming and laborious process of drilling away the amalgam from numerous teeth, which is neither friendly to the environment nor the health of researchers. Thirdly, in comparison with the previous research, the cut-off value for the number of surfaces restored with amalgam was reduced from ≥ 4 to ≥ 3 because there was a very small number of restorations with ≥ 4 restored surfaces in the premolar and lower molar groups (3 and 6, respectively), in spite of the greater total sample size (245 vs. 155 restorations from the natural teeth). Thus, setting the cut-off value at ≥ 4 would yield imprecise statistical estimates, consequently hindering our ability to draw valid inferences based on such a small group size.

Some findings of the present study are in agreement with those reported in the previous investigation: The

mean restoration mass and SD ($0.71 \text{ g} \pm 0.60 \text{ g}$) are comparable with values obtained for amalgam-restored teeth extracted from Canadian patients at the time of the study ($0.67 \text{ g} \pm 0.43 \text{ g}$) or at least 15 years earlier ($0.60 \text{ g} \pm 0.46 \text{ g}$). The mean mass of the restorations within each tooth type increased as the number of tooth surfaces restored with amalgam increased. Moreover, the restorations with two or \geq three restored surfaces were significantly heavier in upper and lower molars than in premolars, paralleling the trends observed in the Canadian investigation. This has been explained by the smaller crown size in premolars than molars, the former facilitating placement of smaller restorations (Adegbenbo et al., 2004). However, another factor that may be taken into consideration is a characteristic pattern of dental destruction caused by caries: molars are more commonly affected than premolars and enter into the repeat restoration cycle earlier, which over time results in heavier restorations (Pitts et al., 2003; Schwendicke et al., 2018). Our linear regression model using the tooth type and number of restored surfaces to assess the variation of restoration masses explained 61% of this variation. This is comparable to the Canadian model, in which the same variables explained 54% of the variation observed in natural teeth. Additionally, in both studies, the number of restored surfaces was the most important explanatory variable.

In this study, the mean mass of amalgam per restored surface was 0.33 g. In contrast, Adegbenbo et al. (2002) in another study reported a value almost twice as high (0.65 g), but their sample was very small (38 restored tooth surfaces) and the tooth type was not specified. Moreover, the restorations with ≥ 2 restored surfaces were on average slightly heavier in molars from Slovenia than in those from North America (Drummond et al., 2003; Adegbenbo et al., 2004); the reverse was true for the restorations with one restored surface in molars and for the restorations in premolars, regardless of the number of restored surfaces. The reasons for this pattern are not clear, but apparently, they are neither related to (i) different methods of determining the mass of restorations nor to (ii) variable trends in dental caries prevalence and severity in the source populations.

Regarding the first, the indirect approach used in a study by Adegbenbo et al. (2004) could produce slightly overestimated restoration masses, because removal of amalgam using burs invariably results in cavity enlargement (Hunter et al., 1995; Dörter et al., 2003; Sardenberg et al., 2008; Lenzi et al., 2013). However, contrary to the expectation, the extensive restorations in molars (≥ 2 restored surfaces)

were, on average, lighter than in our study, in spite of the fact that such restorations are, in general, less regularly shaped and thus more difficult to drill away from the cavity without sacrificing tooth structure. Regarding the second, Adegbebo et al. (2004) found no significant differences between mean masses of restorations from extracted teeth collected at the time of study and at least 15 years previously, in spite of a significant reduction in the prevalence of cavitated caries lesions and the decayed, missing, and filled (DMF) index scores over decades in North America (Frencken et al., 2017). The restoration mass is dependent upon several factors, including the extent of the carious lesion at the time of diagnosis and the number of restoration cycles, i.e., replacements due to secondary caries lesions or other causes of amalgam failure, perhaps indicating a later diagnosis and/or a higher number of replacements in molars from Slovenia than in those from North America. The exact cause for the observed pattern of differences between studies is difficult to ascertain because in both, the restorations were taken from a non-random pool of extracted teeth. Besides, the concept of extension for prevention, which the profession has followed for decades (Vrbič, 1981), should also be considered as one of the factors increasing the restoration mass. According to this concept, not only was the lesion included in the cavity outline, but also the neighbouring caries-prone areas, such as non-carious grooves on occlusal surfaces. In Slovenia, this concept was abandoned in favour of the more conservative cavity designs in 1990 (Vrbič, 1990).

Estimating mercury emissions from crematoriums requires calculation of the emissions factor, which is the mean mass of mercury (in grams) contained in the amalgam restorations of deceased individuals (Santarsiero et al., 2006). The emissions factor for mercury release from crematoriums is population-specific due to variations in dental amalgam use and mortality rates among countries. For the UK, a high factor value of 3.0 g was derived in 1990 by weighing the amount of mercury in one medium-sized amalgam capsule (0.6 g) and estimating that adult individuals on average carry five amalgam restorations (Mills, 1990). In Switzerland, around the same time, an average mercury content of 2.1 g per corpse was found on the basis of postmortem clinical and radiographical examinations and unpublished data on the mass of variously sized amalgam restorations (Matter-Grütter et al., 1995). Recently, a British Columbia-specific emissions factor of 1.2 g was developed based on mortality data, mean number of amalgam-restored

tooth surfaces per person, by age category, and mean mass of 1-surface amalgam restoration (0.26 g) from the study of Adegbebo et al. (2004), assuming this value as a contribution of each restored tooth surface to the total mass of amalgam (Piagno & Afshari, 2020). In contrast, much lower values of 0.078 g and 0.060 g were recently reported for Germany, based on the environmental modelling and emissions testing conducted in 26 crematoriums, respectively (Sobolewski, 2016). The environmental modelling employed the postmortem examination-based mean number of 0.39 amalgam restorations per cremated body and the mean mass of 0.2 g of mercury per restoration, as reported by the dental materials manufacturer. A comparably low value of 0.032 g was recently obtained for Japan by monitoring mercury emission from 7 crematoriums (Takaoka et al., 2010).

As apparent from the above, the mass of amalgam restorations was not determined empirically, but rather estimated based on simplified or unpublished data, thus forming the least reliable variable in modelling mercury emissions. The present study goes some way towards overcoming this limitation. In future assessments, the predicted masses of amalgam restorations in conjunction with analysis of the oral health records of representative population samples will enable refinement of mercury emission estimates from this source of pollution, specifically, the calculation should account for both the number of tooth surfaces restored with amalgam and tooth type and provide the lower and upper values of the emissions factor.

In the EU, dentistry was identified as the largest remaining consumer of mercury, which encouraged the decision-makers to take legislative actions targeting the use of dental amalgam and the amalgam waste management (European Commission, 2020). Consequently, the use and export of dental amalgam is prohibited since 1 January 2025; however, for Member States requiring more time to adapt their national healthcare systems, including Slovenia, the ban will come into effect by 30 June 2026 (European Commission, 2024). Although patient doubts about dental amalgam safety remain, it must be emphasised that the reason for its abandonment is not medical concerns but environmental issues and indirect health effects associated with releases of mercury into the environment. Crematoriums are currently an unregulated source of harmful air pollutants, including mercury from amalgam restorations, which is a concerning issue in light of the worldwide increasing cremation rates (Mari & Domingo, 2010; Tibau & Grube, 2019). Although the contribution of crematoriums

to mercury pollution is small in comparison with some other sources, like coal-fired power plants and municipal waste incinerators, their predominant location in or close to residential areas and comparatively low chimneys might result in a completely different emission situation in the vicinity of these facilities (Ohle et al., 2021). Nevertheless, only a few studies have been published on emissions from crematoriums, mostly focusing on dioxins, volatile organic compounds, and particulate matter (Hutzinger & Fiedler, 1993; Takeda et al., 2000; Takeda et al., 2001; Luthardt et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2003; Xue et al., 2018).

Limitations

The primary limitation of his study is that the sampling type was convenience, not probabilistic. Additionally, the time of restoration placement and the age and biological sex of the patients were not known. These limitations are common if the extracted teeth from existing dental collections are used as a study material. The primary strength of the study is a direct method of determining the mass of amalgam restorations, which surpasses the previously used indirect method in terms of accuracy, safety, and time efficiency.

Conclusions

This study estimated the mass of amalgam restorations based on the analysis of a Slovenian sample, thereby providing data that should enable reliable modelling of

mercury emissions from crematoriums and assessment of their impact on the surrounding environment. The linear regression model with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type as predictors explained 61% of the variation in the masses of restorations. This is only the second study investigating the mass of amalgam restorations, and further research is needed to shed more light on its temporal and global variation.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, I.Š.; Supervision, I.Š.; Funding acquisition, I.Š.; Development of methodology, I.Š.; Writing the initial draft, I.Š.; Investigation, N.J., N.G., L.L.P., E.P., and A.K.; Writing – review & editing, N.J., N.G., L.L.P., E.P., and A.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

The project was funded by the EUTOPIA Alliance of 10 European Universities through measure S.E.1.2.

Data Availability

Research data is deposited at Zenodo (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17954485>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

References

- Adegbembo, A. O., Watson, P. A., & Lugowski, S. J. (2002). The weight of wastes generated by removal of dental amalgam restorations and the concentration of mercury in dental wastewater. *Journal of the Canadian Dental Association*, 68(9), 553–558.
- Adegbembo, A. O., Watson, P. A., & Rokni, S. (2004). Estimating the weight of dental amalgam restorations. *Journal of the Canadian Dental Association*, 70(1), 30.
- Ajiboye, A. S., Mossey, P. A., & Fox, C. H. (2020). International Association for Dental Research policy and position statements on the safety of dental amalgam. *Journal of Dental Research*, 99(7), 763–768. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022034520915878>
- Bajsmán, A., Turkušić, E., Vuković, A., Zukić, S., Zukanović, A., & Kahrović, E. (2014). Analysis of metals released from dental amalgam alloy using inductively coupled plasma–mass spectrometry. *Stomatološki vjesnik (Stomatological Review)*, 3(1), 17–25.
- Berglund, A. (1990). Estimation by a 24-hour study of the daily dose of intra-oral mercury vapor inhaled after release from dental amalgam. *Journal of Dental Research*, 69(10), 1646–1651. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220345900690100401>
- Clarkson, T. W. (1997). The toxicology of mercury. *Critical Reviews in Clinical Laboratory Sciences*, 34(4), 369–403. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10408369708998098>
- Dörter, C., Yildiz, E., & Erdemir, U. (2003). Effect of operators' skills on increase in cavity volume of restorations. *Quintessence International*, 34(1), 27–30.
- Drummond, J. L., Cailas, M. D., & Croke, K. (2003). Mercury generation potential from dental waste amalgam. *Journal of Dentistry*, 31(7), 493–501. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0300-5712\(03\)00083-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0300-5712(03)00083-6)

- European Commission. (2024). Commission welcomes provisional agreement to ban all remaining intentional uses of toxic mercury in the EU. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_679
- European Commission. (2020). Assessment of the feasibility of phasing-out dental amalgam – Final report (Framework Contract No. ENV.C.4/FRA/2015/0042 – Service request 15). <https://circabc.europa.eu/>
- Frankenberger, R., Winter, J., & Schmalz, G. (2021). Amalgam und Alternativen – Diskussionen zur Quecksilberreduktion in der Umwelt. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt Gesundheitsforschung Gesundheitsschutz*, 64(7), 847–855. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-021-03355-4>
- Frencken, J. E., Sharma, P., Stenhouse, L., Green, D., Lavery, D., & Dietrich, T. (2017). Global epidemiology of dental caries and severe periodontitis – A comprehensive review. *Journal of Clinical Periodontology*, 44(18 Suppl.), S94–S105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpe.12677>
- Government of the Republic of Slovenia. (2008). Uredba o ravnanju z amalgamskimi odpadki ... Uradni list Republike Slovenije. <https://pilsrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=URED4839>
- Holm, S. (1979). A simple sequentially rejective multiple test procedure. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 6(2), 65–70.
- Hunter, A. R., Treasure, E. T., & Hunter, A. J. (1995). Increases in cavity volume associated with the removal of class 2 amalgam and composite restorations. *Operative Dentistry*, 20(1), 2–6.
- Hutzinger, O., & Fiedler, H. (1993). From source to exposure: Some open questions. *Chemosphere*, 27(1–3), 121–129.
- Hyson, J. M. (2006). Amalgam: Its history and perils. *Journal of the Californian Dental Association*, 34(3), 215–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19424396.2006.12222190>
- Lenzi, T. L., Marquezan, M., Bonini, G. C., Camargo, L. B., & Raggio, D. P. (2013). Repairing ditched amalgam restorations is less time and tooth structure-consuming than replacement. *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry*, 14(5), 345–349. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40368-013-0091-y>
- Logar, A. (1955). Konzervirajoče zobozdravstvo I. Anatomija zob [Conservative dentistry I. Dental anatomy]. *Medicinska fakulteta*.
- Luthardt, P., Mayer, J., & Fuchs, J. (2002). Total TEQ emissions (PCDD/F and PCB) from industrial sources. *Chemosphere*, 46(9–10), 1303–1308. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535\(01\)00277-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535(01)00277-6)
- Mari, M., & Domingo, J. L. (2010). Toxic emissions from crematories: A review. *Environment International*, 36(1), 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2009.09.006>
- Matter-Grütter, C., Bailod, R., Imfeld, T., & Lutz, F. (1995). Quecksilber-Emissionsmessungen in einem Krematorium. *Schweizer Monatsschrift für Zahnmedizin*, 105(8), 1023–1028.
- Mills, A. (1990). Mercury and crematorium chimneys. *Nature*, 346(6285), 615. <https://doi.org/10.1038/346615a0>
- Mulligan, S., Kakonyi, G., Moharamzadeh, K., Thornton, S., & Martin, N. (2018). The environmental impact of dental amalgam and resin-based composite materials. *British Dental Journal*, 224(7), 542–548.
- Ohle, A., Köhler, M., Graf, S., Bernhardt, D., & Beckmann, M. (2021). Quecksilber- und Feinstaubemissionen von Krematorien: Ein Überblick. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 93(3), 390–411. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.202000122>
- Pacyna, E. G., Pacyna, J., Sundseth, K., Munthe, J., Kindbom, K., Wilson, S., ... Maxson, P. (2010). Global emission of mercury to the atmosphere from anthropogenic sources in 2005 and projections to 2020. *Atmospheric Environment*, 44(20), 2487–2499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2009.06.009>
- Pezelj-Ribaric, S., Prpic, J., Miletić, I., Brumini, G., Soskić, M. S., & Anić, I. (2008). Association between oral lichenoid reactions and amalgam restorations. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*, 22(10), 1163–1167. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3083.2008.02736.x>
- Piagno, H., & Afshari, R. (2020). Mercury from crematoriums: Human health risk assessment and estimate of total emissions in British Columbia. *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, 111(6), 1011–1019. <https://doi.org/10.17269/s41997-020-00327-0>
- Pitts, N. B., Fejerskov, O., & von der Fehr, F. R. (2003). Caries epidemiology, with special emphasis on diagnostic standards. In O. Fejerskov & E. A. M. Kidd (Eds.), *Dental caries: The disease and its clinical management* (pp. 140–163). Blackwell Munksgaard.
- Powers, J. M., & Wataha, J. C. (2017). *Dental materials: Foundations and applications* (11th ed., pp. 58–72). Elsevier.
- R Core Team (2025). *_R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing_*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <<https://www.R-project.org/>>.
- Reinhardt, J. W., Boyer, D. B., Svare, C. W., Frank, C. W., Cox, R. D., & Gay, D. D. (1983). Exhaled mercury following removal and insertion of amalgam restorations. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*, 49(5), 652–656. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3913\(83\)90391-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3913(83)90391-8)
- Rodríguez-Farre, E., Testai, E., Bruzell, E., de Jong, W., Schmalz, G., Thomsen, M., & Hensten, A. (2016). The safety of dental amalgam and alternative dental restoration materials for patients and users. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 79, 108–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2015.12.015>
- Santarsiero, A., Settimo, G., & Dell'Andrea, E. (2006). Mercury emission from crematoria. *Annali dell'Istituto Superiore di Sanità*, 42(3), 369–373.
- Sardenberg, F., Bonifácio, C. C., Braga, M. M., Imparato, J. C., & Mendes, F. M. (2008). Evaluation of the dental structure loss produced during maintenance and replacement of occlusal amalgam restorations. *Brazilian Oral Research*, 22(3), 242–246. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1806-83242008000300009>
- Schwendicke, F., Lamont, T., & Innes, N. (2018). Removing or controlling? How caries management impacts on the lifetime of teeth. *Monographs in Oral Science*, 27, 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000487829>
- Sobolewski, S. J. (2016). Quecksilbermessungen in Krematorien. *DBU Fachtagung Krematorium – Abgas und Asche*.
- Takaoka, M., Oshita, K., Takeda, N., & Morisawa, S. (2010). Mercury emission from crematories in Japan. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 10(8), 3665–3671.

- Takeda, N., Takaoka, M., Fujiwara, T., Takeyama, H., & Eguchi, S. (2000). PCDDs/DFs emissions from crematories in Japan. *Chemosphere*, 40(6), 575–586. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535\(99\)00232-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535(99)00232-5)
- Takeda, N., Takaoka, M., Fujiwara, T., Takeyama, H., & Eguchi, S. (2001). Measures to prevent emissions of PCDDs/DFs and co-planar PCBs from crematories in Japan. *Chemosphere*, 43(4–7), 763–771. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535\(00\)00431-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535(00)00431-8)
- Tibau, A. V., & Grube, B. D. (2019). Mercury contamination from dental amalgam. *Journal of Health and Pollution*, 9(22), 190612. <https://doi.org/10.5696/2156-9614-9.22.190612>
- UNEP. (2024). Minamata Convention on Mercury (Text and Annexes). <https://minamataconvention.org/en/documents/minamata-convention-mercury-text-and-annexes>
- Vrbič, V. (1981). Preventivno zalitje zobnih fisur [Preventive pits and fissure sealing]. *Zobozdravstveni vestnik (Slovenian Dental Journal)*, 36(1–2), 13–16.
- Vrbič, V. (1990). Sodobna zasnova preparacije kavitet [New cavity designs]. *Zobozdravstveni vestnik (Slovenian Dental Journal)*, 45(4–5), 83–87.
- Wang, L. C., Lee, W. J., Lee, W. S., Chang-Chien, G. P., & Tsai, P. J. (2003). Characterizing the emissions of polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins and dibenzofurans from crematories and their impacts to the surrounding environment. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 37(1), 62–67. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0208714>
- WHO. (2024). Mercury and health. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mercury-and-health>
- Xue, Y., Cheng, L., Chen, X., Zhai, X., Wang, W., Zhang, W., ... Wei, T. (2018). Emission characteristics of harmful air pollutants from cremators in Beijing, China. *PLOS ONE*, 13(5), e0194226. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0194226>

Original Research

***In vitro* conservation and multiplication of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. - A horticulturally important floriferous orchid species**

Mahika Jain¹, Saranjeet Kaur^{1,*}

Abstract

The study is envisioned to assist *ex situ* conservation of horticulturally important endangered epiphytic orchid species, *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. The *in vitro* cultures were initiated through an asymbiotic seed germination technique, using undehisced capsules, in Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium and its combinations with auxin (α -naphthalene acetic acid; NAA 1 mg l⁻¹) and cytokinin (6-benzylamino purine; BAP 1 mg l⁻¹). MS medium (control), favoured early initiation of germination in the seeds. Attempts were also made to multiply protocorms in basal medium. Although growth regulators favoured protocorm multiplication, they also multiplied in Basal MS medium. Synergistic action of NAA and BAP was observed in seedling development, similar to that of the basal medium. Seedlings were formed after 20 weeks.

Keywords

Cymbidium; epiphyte, seed germination, organic growth supplements

¹ Department of Biosciences, University Institute of Biotechnology, Chandigarh University, Gharuan, Mohali- 140413, Punjab, India

*** Corresponding author:**

E-mail address: sksekhkone7632@cumail.in

Citation: Jain, M., Kaur, S. (2026). *In vitro* conservation and multiplication of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. - A horticulturally important floriferous orchid species. Acta Biologica Slovenica 69 (1)

Received: 01.02.2025 / **Accepted:** 19.09.2025 /

Published: 14.01.2026

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.21779>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

In vitro ohranjanje in razmnoževanje *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. – vrtnarsko pomembna cvetoča vrsta orhideje

Izvleček

Študija naj bi pomagala pri ohranjanju ogrožene epifitske vrste orhideje *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*, ki je pomembna za vrtnarstvo, *ex situ*. *In vitro* kulture so bile začete s tehniko asimbiotičnega kaljenja semen, z uporabo nedeljenih plodov, v gojišču Murashige in Skoog (1962) in njegovih kombinacijah z auksinom (α -naftalenocetna kislina; NAA 1 mg l⁻¹) in citokinini (6-benzilaminopurin; BAP 1 mg l⁻¹). MS medij (kontrola) je spodbudil zgodnje začetno kaljenje semen. Poskušali so tudi pomnožiti protokorm v bazalnem mediju. Čeprav so rastni regulatorji spodbujali pomnoževanje protokormov, so se ti pomnožili tudi v bazalnem MS mediju. Pri razvoju sadik je bilo opazno sinergistično delovanje NAA in BAP, podobno kot v bazalnem mediju. Sadike so se oblikovale po 20 tednih.

Ključne besede

Cymbidium; epifit, kalitev semen, ekološki dodatki za rast

Introduction

The plants are indispensable for the precise functioning of an ecosystem. Swift plant biodiversity loss across the globe, due to the extermination of the forests, has raised concerns regarding the threat to human life. The environmentalists and conservationists have emphasised the importance of habitat conservation. Each plant species' survival is of utmost importance. Since many plant species have become extinct or endangered, orchids are no exception (CITES, 2024).

In nature, the orchids are one of the most magnificent congregations of flowering plants, found ubiquitously from the tropics to the higher elevations. Orchid blooms are quite diverse in terms of size, colour, and structure. Besides being floriferously important, the orchids act as essential ecological indicators in addition to serving medicinal purposes (Joshi et al., 2009; Kaur, 2021).

Orchids are economically and commercially significant flowering plants. They belong to the extremely advanced monocot angiosperm family Orchidaceae, which embraces 22,000-31,000 species approximately and covers 7.2% of the flowering plants in India (Antony et al., 2014). Orchid flowers possess an unexpectedly high commercial value both domestically and abroad in the floriculture industry, owing to their gorgeous, colourful, scented blossoms, with long vase life. Diverse orchids are grown for financial advantages, primarily in the floricultural business. While orchids are often cultivated for their decorative value,

they are also used across the world as food, natural cures, and other significant cultural objects (Kasulo et al., 2009; Khasim and Rao, 1999). Being highly versatile, the orchids have been collected unabatedly from their natural habitats; hence, they have become rare and are included in Appendix I and II among other rare plant species by CITES (2024). Thus, in order to conserve their gene pool presently, one of the species of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* has been selected for mass propagation under *in vitro* conditions using an asymbiotic seed germination technique.

Cymbidiums are one of the most popular orchids in horticulture, marketed as cut-flowers, buttonholes and as pot plants, producing many large and long-lasting flowers. The genus *Cymbidium* currently comprises nearly 52 species distributed throughout South and Eastern Asia, the Malay Archipelago and north and east Australia (Puy and Cribb, 2007). *C. finlaysonianum* Lindl. It is an epiphytic, sympodial, herbaceous orchid species that grows up to 90 cm tall, forming dense and wide tufts with close conical to ovoid pseudobulbs covered by the foliar bases. The plant bears flowers that are arranged in a pendulous racemose inflorescence, hanging from the base of the pseudobulb, 0.3 - 1.3 m long and carrying numerous small yellow and red fragrant flowers with a diameter of 5 - 6 cm (Opchat, 2000). Presently, efforts have been made to conserve the germplasm of *C. finlaysonianum* through an asymbiotic seed germination technique and multiplying without the use of PGRs in the nutrient pool.

Materials and Methods

Plant material

The capsules of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* were collected from naturally pollinated plants growing on the trunk of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (jackfruit tree) in the natural habitat of Chandranathpur, Assam, India (latitudinal range: 24°58'00.5"N, longitudinal range: 92°42'09.0"E). Seeds from undehisced capsules of *C. finlaysonianum* were used to initiate cultures in vitro (Fig. 1A-C).

Culture medium and surface sterilisation of the capsule

Defined asymbiotic orchid seed germination medium, such as Murashige and Skoog (1962) MS medium (Hi-media, Mumbai, India) was used to initiate the cultures. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.7 using 1 N HCl / 1 N NaOH before autoclaving. The medium was gelled with agar (Hi-media, Mumbai, India), dispensed into (25 × 150 mm) test tubes and autoclaved at 121°C at a pressure of 1.06 kg cm⁻² for 15 min. Autoclaved medium was kept at 37°C for 2–3 days to check for any contamination. Seed viability was performed by using the TTC salt (2,3,5-triphenyl-2H-tetrazolium chloride; 1%; pH 6.5) staining method. The seeds were kept in the dark while immersed in stain for eight hours at 30°C.

The capsules were first gently scrubbed with an ultra-soft brush in running tap water to remove any debris from their surface. Each capsule was rinsed thoroughly with dishwashing detergent solution. The capsule was swabbed with ethyl alcohol in a laminar air flow hood and sequentially disinfected with an aqueous solution of 0.05% mercuric chloride (Qualigens, Mumbai, India) containing 1–2 drops of “Teepol” for 2–3 minutes and 0.05% streptomycin (Angel Pharma International, India) treatment for

1-2 minutes. Finally, the capsule was rinsed thoroughly with sterilised distilled water. Thereafter, the capsule was incised longitudinally, and the seeds were scooped out into a Petri dish.

Inoculations and incubation

The culture vessels, inoculated with seeds, were incubated under a 12-h photoperiod under 40 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ light intensity (fluorescent tubes, Philips India Ltd, Mumbai, India) at approximately 25 ± 2°C temperature. The cultures were sub-cultured into their respective fresh medium as and when required.

Observations and data analysis

After 4 weeks of inoculation, a few seeds were taken out of the culture vessel with the help of a spatula. They were placed in a drop of water on a glass slide and observed under a microscope. Once the embryos emerged from the seed coat and spherules were formed, the observations were taken at 1-week intervals. Different development events of germinating seeds were observed (Table 1), and photographs were taken using a stereozoom microscope (Nikon, H600L, Japan). Calculations of seed germination were done by the formula (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014). The cultures were observed regularly under a binocular microscope (Olympus SZX10, Japan), and morphological events were recorded. Eight replicates were used per treatment. To check the reproducibility of the protocol, the experiment was repeated twice. The experiment followed a completely randomised design. The results were tested using a one-way ANOVA test and were analysed using the Tukey Multiple Comparison using SPSS (version 17) software package (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). The reproducibility of the protocol was checked by repeating the experiment.

Table 1. Evaluation of morphological events of seeds of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*.

Tabela 1. Ocena morfoloških pojavov semen *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*.

Event	Sequential morphological event
1 st event	Imbibed seed, swollen, still covered or partially covered by testa (=viable seed)
2 nd event	Enlarged seed without testa (=germination)
3 rd event	Protocorms with rhizoids
4 th event	Protocorms with a pointed shoot apex and rhizoids (appearance of shoot apex)
5 th event	Seedlings with one or more leaves (emergence of the first leaf)
6 th event	Enlargement of leaves (2-3 leaves) and the emergence of the first root

Histochemical studies

The modified seed viability technique established by Terry et al. (2003) was employed to evaluate the seed vitality using the Tetrazolium test (Alvarez-Pardo et al., 2006). The seeds were washed several times with distilled water after initially being soaked in 1% (v/v) Tween 80 for 20 minutes. For 24 hours, the seeds were suspended in distilled water. Seeds were then put in 1% (w/v) solution of 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) in a beaker after the water had been discarded. The reaction was left to run for 24 hours at 30°C in the dark. The seeds were inspected under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SXZ12, Japan) after being rinsed once with distilled water to eliminate excess stain after discarding the TTC solution. Seeds were scored as viable if the embryo was stained red or orange and as non-viable if the embryo was unstained.

Histological studies

For the purpose of tracking the origin of secondary protocorms (*neo-formations*) during protocorm multiplication, hand sections of a clump of multiplying protocorms were gently and carefully inserted into potato pith. Thin slices or sections were selected to prepare temporary slides by staining them with safranin stain. The slides were observed under a stereoscopic microscope (Nikon Digital Sight, DS, Ri1 Nikon Corporation, Japan).

Results

In the present experiment, the ability of basal MS medium and its combinations with plant growth regulators (PGRs) (auxins and cytokinin) was tested on seed germination percentage, onset of seed germination and subsequent morphogenetic changes associated with seedling development. The germination frequency varied with the kind of PGR treatment. Morphogenetic milestones observed from the germination of the seed to the development of the seedling are summarised (Tables 2-4) and illustrated (Figures 1-4).

The capsule, from where the scooped-out seeds germinated readily, was measured 10.9 ± 0.28 cm in length and 2.81 ± 0.09 cm in width (Table 2, Figure 1a and 1b). The seeds were highly reduced, creamish-white in colour, powdery or dust-like in texture and innumerable. (Figure 1c).

The seeds were embryonate and viable. To ensure viability in the seeds, the TTC test showed that the embryos

stained red and consisted of undifferentiated cells enclosed within a hyaline seed coat (Figure 1d). The germination of seeds was not obligatory to the use of PGRs, as the seeds efficiently germinated on basal medium, i.e. on MS medium (Figure 2). The seeds (Figure 3a) began germination within 3.80 ± 0.09 weeks of culture on MS basal (control) medium, with the swelling of the embryo (Figure 3a). These swollen seeds emerged as a spherule by piercing through the hyaline seed coat, as evident by the successive stages (Figure 3c-e). The spherule grew in size lengthwise while remaining attached to the seed coat and developed absorbing hair primordia (Figure 3f), developed chlorophyll and absorbing hairs at the base in a 7.10 ± 0.11 weeks old culture (Figure 3g). A close observation indicated that the later lower portion of the spherule developed more absorbing hair (Figure 3a). The spherules further grew to form a pear-shaped protocorm (Figure 3h) with absorbing hairs all around the lower portion of the protocorm in 9.30 ± 0.23 weeks. At the initial stages of protocorm formation, a shoot primordial initial (1st leaf primordia) was evident at the upper end in 13.05 ± 0.3 weeks, and later dense rhizoidal growth was observed all around at the basal portion of the protocorm (Figure 3i). Successively, another leaf primordia and root primordia were formed after 15.55 ± 0.05 weeks and 18.4 ± 0.14 weeks, respectively (Table 3). Seedlings, complete with 2-3 leaves and 1-2 roots, were developed after 20 weeks.

NAA, in the culture medium, also favoured cent per cent germination but delayed all sequential morphogenetic processes, even arresting differentiation of the protocorms and delaying chlorophyll development (Figures 3j and 3k). These protocorms were shifted to half-strength MS medium supplemented with NAA (1 mg L⁻¹) and peptone (1mg l⁻¹). Replacement of NAA with BAP also showed a similar effect, except it favoured multiplication of the protocorms (Figure 3i). A combination of auxin and cytokinin proved synergistic in action as the seeds germinated within 4.2 ± 0.07 weeks (Figure 2). The protocorms multiplied profusely (Figure 3m) and formed seedlings in 20.35 ± 0.19 weeks (Figure 3n, Table 3). The growth of spherules remained arrested in both MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹) and MS + BAP (1mg l⁻¹), which was resumed upon a shift to ½ strength MS medium supplemented with NAA and peptone at (1 g l⁻¹). The shoots rooted after 25 weeks (Table 4).

Interestingly, the protocorms multiplied profusely in MS alone and supplemented with BAP + NAA (Figure 4a and 4b). The protocorms multiplied at the base of the seedlings (Figure 4c). Histological hand sections indicated the inherent polyembryonic potential of the protocorms (Figure 4d and 4e)

Table 2. Morphological features of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* capsules at different stages of development.Tabela 2. Morfološke značilnosti kapsul *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v različnih fazah razvoja.

Characteristics	Specifications	
	Immature	Mature
Capsule Colour	Green	Yellowish-green
Seed colour	Whitish- yellow	Pale-yellow
Capsule length (cm)	10.7 ± 0.18	10.9 ± 0.28
Capsule width (cm)	1.48 ± 0.24	2.81 ± 0.09
Capsule surface	Smooth, depressed ridges	Rough, prominent ridges

Data represents Mean ± Standard error

Figure 1. *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. (a) Yellow-green undeveloped capsule measured lengthwise, (b) Capsule measured widthwise, (c) Minute dust-like seeds, (d) Viable seeds with their embryo stained red upon treatment with TTC solution (10x).

Slika 1. *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. (a) Rumeno-zelena nepreklopljena kapsula, merjena po dolžini, (b) kapsula, merjena po širini, (c) drobna semena, podobna prahu, (d) vitalna semena z zarodkom, obarvanim rdeče po obdelavi z raztopino TTC (10x).

Fig. 2 Time taken by the seeds to germinate in MS medium and its combination with growth adjuncts.

Figure 2. Represents the time taken in weeks by the seeds germinating in MS medium and its combination with growth adjuncts.

Slika 2. Predstavlja čas v tednih, ki ga potrebujejo semena za kalitev v MS-mediju in njegovi kombinaciji z dodatki za rast.

Figure 3. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination and seedling development of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in MS medium. (a) Embryonate seed with seed coat intact (10x), (b) Swelling of the embryos (10x), (c), (d) swollen seed emerging as spherule by piercing through the hyaline seed coat, (e) formation of absorbing hairs at the basal portion of the embryo (40x), (f) embryo attached to the seed coat at one point (40x), (g) globular spherule with multicellular trichomes arising from one end of the spherule (40x), (h) pear-shaped protocorm with hairs attached to its basal surface (40x), (i) Formation of 1st leaf primordium in protocorm and more rhizoids at the basal portion of the protocorm (20x), (j) Achlorophyllous spherules in MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹), (k) Cultures treated in MS media + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) after 12 weeks of inoculations showing initiation of development of chlorophyll, (l) Protocorm development in basal MS medium after 12 weeks, (m) Development of protocorms after 8.4 weeks of inoculation in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹), (n) Seedling formation in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Slika 3. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen in razvoj sadik *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v MS mediju. (a) Zarodno seme z nepoškodovano semensko lupino (10x), (b) nabrekanje zarodkov (10x), (c), (d) nabrekano seme, ki se pojavi kot krogla, ko prebije hialinsko semensko lupino, (e) nastanek absorpcijskih dlačic na bazalnem delu zarodka (40x), (f) zarodek, pritrjen na semensko lupino na eni točki (40x), (g) kroglasta kroglasta oblika z večceličnimi trichomi, ki izhajajo iz enega konca kroglaste oblike (40x), (h) hruškasta protocorm z dlačicami, pritrjenimi na njeno bazalno površino (40x), (i) Oblikovanje prvega listnega primordija v protokormu in več rizoidov na bazalnem delu protokorma (20x), (j) Achlorofilne krogle v MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹), (k) Kulture, obdelane v MS mediju + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) po 12 tednih inokulacij, ki kažejo začetek razvoja klorofila, (l) Razvoj protokorma v bazalnem MS mediju po 12 tednih, (m) Razvoj protokormov po 8,4 tednih inokulacije v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹), (n) Oblikovanje sadik v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Table 3. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination in *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* and associated morphogenetic events in MS medium and its combinations with growth adjuncts.

Tabela 3. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in povezani morfogogenetski dogodki v MS mediju in njegovih kombinacijah z dodatki za rast.

Additive	Germination (%)	Time Taken for (wks)					
		Development of			Differentiation of		Development of
		Spherule	Chlorophyll	Protocorm	First leaf	First root	
Control	100.00±0.00 ^a	5.45 ± 0.28 ^a	7.10 ± 0.11 ^b	9.30 ± 0.23 ^a	13.05±0.30 ^b	18.4 ± 0.14 ^b	20.00 ± 0.20 ^a
BAP	90.01±0.00 ^b	6.60 ± 0.38 ^b	7.35 ± 0.17 ^b	10.8 ± 0.46 ^b	Cultures shifted to ½ MS + BAP +P		
NAA	100.0±0.00 ^a	8.35 ± 0.05 ^c	12.57 ± 0.12 ^c	15.8 ± 0.69 ^c	Cultures shifted to ½ MS + NAA +P		
BAP+NAA	85.0.00±0.00 ^c	9.34 ± 0.04 ^c	6.12 ± 0.15 ^a	8.40 ± 0.12 ^a	9.80 ± 0.46 ^a	17.42 ± 0.09 ^a	20.35 ± 0.19 ^a

MS medium, Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium; Concentration of growth regulators, 1mg l⁻¹. Values in a column with the same superscripts are not significantly different at p ≤ 0.05

Table 4. Shows *in vitro* morphogenetic changes in germinating entities upon a shift to ½ MS medium.

Tabela 4. Prikazuje *in vitro* morfogogenetske spremembe v kalivih entitetah ob spremembi v ½ MS mediju.

Additives	Time Taken in (wks)		
	Differentiation of		Development of
	First leaf	First Root	
½ MS+BAP + P	13.05 ± 0.30	19.40 ± 0.14	25.00 ± 0.20
½ MS+NAA + P	17.22 ± 0.15	22.35 ± 0.19	25.00 ± 0.12

MS medium, Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium; Concentration of growth regulators = 1 mg l⁻¹, Peptone (P) = 1 mg l⁻¹; Data represents mean ± SD.

Figure 4. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination and seedling development of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in MS medium. (a) Multiplication of protocorms in MS medium basal (20x), (b) Multiplication of protocorms in MS medium + BAP + NAA (20x), (c) Protocorms multiplication at the base of shoots in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x), (d-e) Histological hand sections indicating multiplication of the protocorms in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Slika 4. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen in razvoj sadik *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v MS mediju. (a) Razmnoževanje protocormov v MS mediju basal (20x), (b) Razmnoževanje protocormov v MS mediju + BAP + NAA (20x), (c) Razmnoževanje protocormov na dnu poganjkov v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x), (d-e) Histoški ročni prerezi, ki kažejo razmnoževanje protocormov v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Discussion

Utilising *in vitro* methods aids in protecting the genetic material of vulnerable species. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination is helpful in conserving orchid species, since it reduces the time gap between pollination and seed germination (Sagawa, 1963). Additionally, tissue culture is extensively utilised in genetic transformation investigations and can be utilised to clone apomictic taxa and propagate desirable genotypes (Sagawa, 1963). In this study, seed germination of *C. finlaysonianum* was influenced by the maturity level of the capsule and growth regulators in the medium. The efficacy of Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium was tested, along with checking the germination potential of *C. finlaysonianum* seeds in basal MS medium and its combinations with PGRs. Literature survey indicates that PGRs such as auxins and cytokinins [2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D); naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)], and synthetic phenylurea derivatives (PBU, 4-CPPU, and 2,3-MDPU) are considered as the agents, that are responsible for developing genetic variability in the cultures (Sales and Butardo, 2014; Sun et al., 2013). In crops like orchid, which is floriculturally and commercially very important, and genetic uniformity is desired, the *in vitro* cultures should avoid the use of PGRs as they increase the chances of occurrence of genetic variations. Currently, seed germination does not require the addition of PGRs, and these germinated successfully in basal medium (control), indicating that there was already a sufficient level of endogenous hormones available in the seeds themselves that initiated germination in the seeds. Moreover, the nutritional requirements of orchid seeds, in terms of type and quantity, can vary at various developmental stages in the cultures (Arditti and Ernst, 1984). A similar kind of response of seed germination in basal medium is also recorded in *Coelogyne flaccida* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014) and *Vanda testacea* (Kaur, 2021).

Our experiment strongly indicates that the use of PGRs can be successfully avoided, as the seeds of *C. finlaysonianum* germinated with 100% frequency in the control (MS basal). Whereas previous studies show that in different media such as Knudson C medium (KC), New Dogashima medium (ND), and Vacin and Went medium (VW) (Rittirat et al., 2018), the seeds germinated with a maximum of 98 per cent frequency in Knudson C (Knudson, 1946) medium and Hyponex leaf fertiliser (HS) media (Rittirat et al., 2018). The germination of *C. finlaysonianum* seeds in different

media indicates their wide nutritional amplitude and simple nutritional requirements.

Plant tissue culture is a very efficient technique for clonal propagation; however, the resulting regenerants often show a number of somaclonal variations. A survey of literature indicates that plant growth regulators (PGRs), individually or in combinations, can behave as mutagens (D'Amato and Bayliss, 1985). A perusal of literature reveals that the size of orchid seed is quite small, about 0.25 to 1.2 mm (length) and 0.09 to 1.2 mm (width), and a single capsule contains about 4 million powdery seeds (Arditti, 1967), and the present species is no exception. The success of *in vitro* asymbiotic seed germination largely depends upon the capsule's maturity stage at the time of harvesting. This has been confirmed through the current study and earlier studies made in *C. flaccida* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014). Earlier, a similar kind of response was achieved in *Cephalanthera falcata*, in which seeds harvested at a very early stage germinated with poor frequency (Yamazaki and Miyoshi, 2006). In our cultures, this kind of germination response could be attributed to a less developed embryo, as earlier also suggested by Yamazaki and Miyoshi (2006) in *Cephalanthera falcata*.

Presently, 100% response of the seed procured from 18-week-old cultures was achieved due to the metabolically awakened, well-developed embryos. The result is similar to the earlier findings in *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2011), *Paphiopedilum Venustum* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014), and *Vanda testacea* (Kaur, 2021). Our results are in accord with earlier reports in *Cleisostoma ramaciferum* (Temjensangba and Deb, 2006) and in *Vanda*, where very young and mature capsules failed to germinate or resulted in a decreased germination frequency (Sharma, 1998). Earlier reports in *Phalaenopsis amabilis* var. *formosa* (Lee and Philips, 2008) and *Dendrobium nobile* (Vasudevan and van Staden, 2010) indicate the existence of a correlation between the internal organisation of immature seeds and their germinating abilities.

Cytokinin (BAP 1mg^l⁻¹) also showed a similar kind of response as that of the control in seed germination. Literature studies reveal that cytokinins are extremely important growth regulators that affect seed germination *in vitro* (Harvais, 1982). They are incorporated extensively in *in vitro* orchid seed germination medium (Arditti and Ernst, 1993). Orchid seeds contain a meagre amount of reserve nutrients as lipid droplets (Arditti and Ernst, 1984), and cytokinin assists the seeds in utilising these complex carbohydrates, without which germination could not be accomplished (De

Pauw et al.,1995).

The initiation of multiple meristematic zones composed of densely packed meristematic cells, forming new meristemoids, is already on record (Young et al., 2000; Ziv et al.,1998). The cells with dense cytoplasm and conspicuous nuclei were involved in the formation of globular bodies, which is an important characteristic feature of the embryogenic cells as earlier studied in species belonging to *Lycium barbarum* (Li et al., 2001), *Malaxis acuminata* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2010), *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* (Kaur, 2017). These globules gradually grew in size, having no vascular connections with the surrounding peripheral tissues and eventually transformed into secondary protocorms (PLBs). The PLBs proliferated further to produce secondary PLBs as reported earlier (Kaur, 2017; Zhao et al., 2008), assisted with the germplasm multiplication and conservation *in vitro*. NAA delayed morphogenetic events, but in combination with BAP proved slightly effective. A similar kind of response of NAA was earlier observed in *Vanda dearie* (Jualang et al., 2014), where NAA treatment delayed seed germination and induced necrosis in protocorm development.

Conclusion

The present experiment is a one-step protocol for *in vitro* conservation of *C. finlaysonianum* and concludes that *C. finlaysonianum* has very simple nutritional requirements for seed germination. Cent of seeds can be germinated without the inclusion of PGRs. The basal medium proved to be promising for the initiation of seed germination, multipli-

cation of the protocorms, and also supported the growth of the cultures. This simple protocol can certainly contribute to the conservation of this floriculturally important orchid species. Further experimental studies are directed to check the genetic fidelity of the regenerants and to acclimatise seedlings that are raised *in vitro*, thus restoring them to their natural habitat.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.S.; methodology, K.S.and J.M.; validation, K.S.; formal analysis, K.S.and J.M.; investigation, K.S.; resources, K.S.; data curation, K.S.; writing—original draft preparation, K.S.; writing—review, and editing,.; supervision, K.S.; All authors have read, and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the laboratory instructors for their timely help during the course of this research work.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Data Availability

Research data is deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18239738>)

Conflicts of Interest

There is no potential conflict of interest shown by authors.

References

- Alvarez-Pardo, V. M., Ferreira, A. G., & Nunes, V. F. (2006). Seed disinfestation methods for *in vitro* cultivation of epiphyte orchids from Southern Brazil. *Horticulturae Brasiliica*, 24, 217–220. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0102-05362006000200019>
- Antony, J. J. J., Sundarasekar, J., Rathinam, X., Subramaniam, S., & Marimuthu, K. (2013). Microscopical analysis of *in vitro* Mokara Broga Giant Orchid. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 26(1), 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.9755/ejfa.v26i1.17447>
- Arditti, J., & Ernst, R. (1984). Physiology of germinating orchid seeds. In J. Arditti (Ed.), *Orchid biology: Reviews and perspectives III* (pp. 177–222). Cornell University Press.
- Arditti, J., & Ernst, R. (1993). *Micropropagation of orchids*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Arditti, J. (1967). Factors affecting the germination of orchid seeds. *The Botanical Review*, 33, 1–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02858656>
- D'Amato, F., & Bayliss, M. W. (1985). Cytogenetics of plant cell and tissue cultures and their regenerates. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 3(1), 73–112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352688509382204>
- De Pauw, M. A., Remphrey, W. R., & Palmer, C. E. (1995). The cytokinin preference for *in vitro* germination and protocorm growth of *Cypripedium candidum*. *Annals of Botany*, 75(3), 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1139/b93-100>

- Harvais, G. (1982). An improved culture medium for growing the orchid *Cypripedium reginae* axenically. *Canadian Journal of Botany*, 60(12), 2547–2555. <https://doi.org/10.1139/b82-309>
- Joshi, P. R., Paudel, M. R., Chand, M., Pradhan, B., Pant, K. K., Joshi, G. P., Bohara, M., Wagner, S. H., Pant, B., & Pant, B. (2020). Cytotoxic effect of selected wild orchids on two different human cancer cell lines. *Heliyon*, 6(5), e03991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03991>
- Jualang, A. G., Devina, D., Hartinie, M., Sharon, J. S., & Roslina, J. (2014). Asymbiotic seed germination and seedling development of *Vanda* dearie. *Malaysian Applied Biology*, 43(2), 25–33.
- Kasulo, V., Mwabumba, L., & Munthali, C. (2009). A review of edible orchids in Malawi. *Journal of Horticulture and Forestry*, 1, 133–139.
- Kaur, S., & Bhutani, K. K. (2010). In vitro propagation of *Vanda testacea* (Lindl.) Reichb.f.: A rare orchid of high medicinal value. *Plant Tissue Culture and Biotechnology*, 19(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3329/ptcb.v19i1.4077>
- Kaur, S., & Bhutani, K. K. (2011). In vitro propagation of *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* (Lindl.). *Floriculture and Ornamental Biotechnology*, 5(1), 50–56.
- Kaur, S., & Bhutani, K. K. (2014). In vitro conservation and asymbiotic propagation of *Coelogyne flaccida* (Lindl.): A threatened orchid. *Plant Biosystems*, 148(5), 935–944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2013>
- Kaur, S. (2017). In vitro regeneration of shoots from nodal explants of *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* Lindl. *Journal of Horticultural Research*, 25(1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.1515/johr-2017-0003>
- Kaur, S. (2021). In vitro conservation of phytochemically enriched orchids of Indian western Himalayas. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, 33(60b), 2556–2561. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2021/v33i60B34914>
- Khasim, S., & Rao, P. R. M. (1999). Medicinal importance of orchids. *The Botanica*, 49, 86–91.
- Knudson, L. (1946). A new nutrient solution for the germination of orchid seed. *American Orchid Society Bulletin*, 15, 214–217.
- Lee, M., & Philips, R. L. (1988). The chromosomal basis of somaclonal variation – a review. *Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology*, 39(1), 413–437.
- Li, S., Dai, R. L., Qin, Z., Shen, Z. H., & Wang, Y. F. (2001). The effects of Ag⁺ on the absorption of trace metal ion during the somatic embryogenesis of *Lycium barbarum* L. *Shi Yan Sheng Wu Xue Bao*, 34(2), 127–130.
- Murashige, T., & Skoog, F. (1962). A revised medium for rapid growth and bio-assay with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 15(3), 473–497.
- Opchat, T. (2000). *Orchids in Thailand*. Bangkok: Home and Garden Publishing.
- Puy, D. D., & Cribb, P. (2007). *The genus Cymbidium* (2nd ed.). Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.
- Rittirat, S., Klaosheed, S., Thammasiri, K., & Praseryongsun, S. (2018). In vitro propagation and forest reestablishment of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl., an endangered medicinal orchid. *Walailak Journal of Science and Technology*, 15(10), 711–724.
- Sagawa, S. (1963). Green pod culture. *Florida Orchidist*, 6, 296–297.
- Sales, E. K., & Butardo, N. G. (2014). Molecular analysis of somaclonal variation in tissue culture derived bananas using MSAP and SSR markers. *International Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 8, 615–622.
- Sharma, J. (1998). Studies on *Vanda*: Effect of age of capsules (pods) on in vitro seed germination. *The Journal of the Orchid Society of India*, 12, 43–45.
- Sun, S., Zhong, J., Li, S., & Wang, X. (2013). Tissue culture-induced somaclonal variation of decreased pollen viability in *Torenia* (*Torenia fourmieri* Lindl.). *Botanical Studies*, 54(1), 36.
- Temjensangba, & Deb, C. R. (2006). Effect of different factors on non-symbiotic seed germination, formation of protocorm-like bodies and plantlet morphology of *Cleisostoma racemeferum* (Lindl.) Garay. *Indian Journal of Biotechnology*, 5, 223–228.
- Terry, J., Probert, R. J., & Liningtons, H. (2003). Processing and maintenance of the millennium seed bank collections. In R. D. Smith, J. B. Dickie, S. H. Linington, H. W. Pritchard, & R. J. Probert (Eds.), *Seed conservation: Turning science into practice* (pp. 307–325).
- Vasudevan, R., & Van Staden, J. (2010). Fruit harvesting time and corresponding morphological changes of seed integuments influence in vitro seed germination of *Dendrobium nobile* Lindl. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 60(3), 237–246.
- Yamazaki, J., & Miyoshi, K. (2006). In vitro asymbiotic germination of immature seed and formation of protocorm by *Cephalanthera falcata* (Orchidaceae). *Annals of Botany*, 98(6), 1197–1206.
- Young, P. S., Murthy, H. N., & Paek, K. Y. (2000). Mass multiplication of protocorm-like bodies using bioreactor system and subsequent plant regeneration in *Phalaenopsis*. *Plant Cell Tissue and Organ Culture*, 63(1), 67–72.
- Zhao, P., Wu, F., Feng, F. S., & Wang, W. (2008). Protocorm-like body (PLB) formation and plant regeneration from the callus culture of *Dendrobium candidum* Wall ex Lindl. *In Vitro Cellular and Developmental Biology–Plant*, 44(3), 178–185.
- Ziv, M., Ronen, G., & Raviv, M. (1998). Proliferation of meristematic clusters in disposable presterilized plastic bioreactors for large-scale micropropagation of plants. *In Vitro Cellular and Developmental Biology–Plant*, 34(2), 152–158.

Original Research

Effect of nitrogen and oxygen low-pressure cold plasma and their mixtures on the germination and early seedling growth of Tartary buckwheat

Jure Mravlje^{1,2,*}

Abstract

A key challenge of the 21st century is the growing human population and the decline of arable land; therefore, new technologies that could ensure higher yields and minimise losses on existing land without further negative impacts on the environment are being sought. Cold plasma treatment of seeds is a promising green technology in agriculture and food production. This study aimed to investigate the effects of different oxygen and nitrogen gas mixtures in a low-pressure cold plasma system on germination and early seedling growth of Tartary buckwheat (*Fagopyrum tataricum*). Our results indicate that nitrogen cold plasma is less aggressive and thus more suitable for treating Tartary buckwheat grains, as a 45-second treatment did not affect germination or early seedling growth, whereas a 90-second treatment decreased germination by less than 10% compared to the control, without affecting seedling length or biomass. Interestingly, the higher oxygen content in the gas mixture and the longer cold plasma treatment time resulted in a more pronounced negative impact on germination and early seedling growth.

Keywords

low-temperature plasma; plasma agriculture; seeds; alternative crops; plant production

1 Department of Biology, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Jamnikarjeva 101, SI-1000 Ljubljana

2 Department of Surface Engineering, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, SI-2000 Ljubljana

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: jure.mravlje@bf.uni-lj.si

Citation: Mravlje, J. (2026). Effect of nitrogen and oxygen low-pressure cold plasma and their mixtures on the germination and early seedling growth of Tartary buckwheat. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (1)

Received: 18.08.2025 / **Accepted:** 16.01.2026 /

Published: 16.01.2026

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.1.23667>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Učinek nizko-tlačne kisikove in dušikove plazme ter njunih mešanic na kaljivost in rast kalic tatarske ajde

Izvleček

Eden največjih izzivov današnjega stoletja je strmo naraščajoča človeška populacija in zmanjševanje primernih obdelovalnih površin; posledično se iščejo nove tehnologije, ki bi omogočile večji pridelek in zmanjšale izgube na že obstoječih obdelovalnih površinah brez dodatnih negativnih vplivov na okolje. Tehnologija obdelave semen s hladno plazmo velja za obetavno in okolju prijazno tehnologijo na področju kmetijstva in prehrane. Namen te študije je bil raziskati učinke različnih mešanic kisika in dušika v nizkotlačnem sistemu hladne plazme na kalitev in zgodnjo rast kalic tatarske ajde (*Fagopyrum tataricum*). Naši rezultati kažejo, da je dušikova hladna plazma manj agresivna in zato primernejša za obdelavo zrnja tatarske ajde, saj 45-sekundna obdelava ni vplivala na sposobnost kalitve ali zgodnjo rast kalic, medtem ko je 90-sekundna obdelava zmanjšala kalitev za manj kot 10 % v primerjavi s kontrolo, brez vpliva na dolžino ali biomaso kalic. Zanimivo je, da je večji delež kisika v plinski mešanici in daljši čas obdelave s hladno plazmo povzročil bolj škodljiv vpliv tako na kalitev kot na zgodnjo rast kalic.

Ključne besede

Nizko-temperaturna plazma, plazemsko kmetijstvo, semena, alternativne poljščine, rastlinska produkcija

Introduction

Plasma is the so-called fourth fundamental state of matter, fully or partially ionised gas, that can be generated by applying energy (via heat, electricity or electromagnetic field) to a gas (Conrads & Schmidt, 2000). It is composed of free electrons, ions, atoms, molecules, radicals, and other reactive species, as well as photons, including ultraviolet (UV) and vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) photons (D. Popović et al., 2021). All these generated species are responsible for the unique characteristics of plasma, which conducts electricity, although it has a net neutral (zero) charge (Tendero et al., 2006). Plasmas can be classified according to various conditions of their generation based on the relative energy levels of light (electrons) and heavy particles (ions and larger particles). The first group, referred to as the so-called thermal plasmas or local thermodynamic equilibrium plasmas, has a high electron density, and the temperature of electrons is close to that of heavy particles. The second group is so-called low temperature or cold plasmas (CP; also non-local thermodynamic equilibrium plasmas), with much lower electron density and temperature due to the much lower temperature of heavy particles than that of electrons (Moreau et al., 2008; Tendero et al., 2006). CP is

already applied in many areas of science and technology, including the processing of textiles and polymers, synthesis of nanoparticles, analytical chemistry (ICP-MS) and some daily life equipment, such as electronics (plasma TV and other display panels), lighting systems (neon lights), etc. (Misra et al., 2016).

CP is also interesting from a biological perspective, as it is suitable for the treatment of thermally unstable or sensitive samples, such as biological materials, as the heating of the samples is minimal, especially in short-term exposure times (Misra et al., 2016; Moreau et al., 2008; Tendero et al., 2006). Therefore, in the last two decades, a new interdisciplinary research field of CP technology for developing applications in many life science areas (such as agriculture, biotechnology and food science) has emerged – called "plasma agriculture" (Puač et al., 2018; Ranieri et al., 2021). It offers new, environmentally friendly approaches in agriculture as an alternative to classical pesticide and other artificial chemical usage with negative environmental impact (Sharma et al., 2019). That is of immense importance as improving efficacy and quality of food production while minimising food losses is crucial and one of the biggest challenges of the 21st century, when the human population is estimated to reach 10 billion by 2050, according to the

Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO United Nations, 2017). The main areas of research are exploring the promising antimicrobial potential of CP for seed surface decontamination (Mravlje, Regvar, & Vogel-Mikuš, 2021; Scholtz et al., 2021), controlling plant diseases (Adhikari et al., 2020) and enhancing seed germination potential (Ranieri et al., 2021; Šimek & Homola, 2021). It has been reviewed that CP treatment can stimulate seed germination, enhance early seedling growth, improve plants' stress tolerance and overall performance (Randeniya & De Groot, 2015; Starič et al., 2020). This is mainly achieved via plasma-seed surface interactions, as the surface usually becomes more hydrophilic, increasing the wettability of seeds and thus water uptake, and other surface functionalisation changes, changes in DNA, enzymatic and hormone activity, etc. (Starič et al., 2020), all of which can positively affect germination and later growth and developments of plants, enhancing their resilience to abiotic and biotic stress.

Nevertheless, despite the promising results of the last two decades, many underexplored areas in CP agriculture remain, as most of the research is focused on cereal crops, legumes and other more widely cultivated crops (Bilea et al., 2024). However, it has already been demonstrated that the response to CP treatment is species-specific and may also be variety (cultivar) dependent (Recek et al., 2023; Starič et al., 2021), as the effect of CP treatment on seed germination depends on many factors such as plant species, size and shape of the seeds, seed coat hardness, amount of endosperm, etc. (Zahoranová et al., 2016).

Buckwheat is a pseudocereal grain crop often referred to as an alternative crop, traditionally grown in Europe and Asia. It is used for flour and groat products and has many beneficial effects on human health due to its high nutritional value, as it is especially rich in phenolics (flavonoids) compared to other traditional cereal crops, therefore gaining much attention as interest in so-called "functional foods" is rapidly growing nowadays (Bonafaccia, Gambelli, et al., 2003; Bonafaccia, Marocchini, et al., 2003; Bonafaccia & Fabjan, 2003; Kreft et al., 2006). It is also gluten-free and hence safe for consumption by patients with celiac disease (Skerritt, 1986), and due to its modest growing demands, making it suitable for organic farming, its production is increasing in Europe and worldwide (V. Popović et al., 2014). Tartary buckwheat (*Fagopyrum tataricum* Gaertn.; TB) is less well-known compared to its more cultivated rela-

tive, common buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench; CB), as it is mainly grown in mountainous regions of China, India, Bhutan and Nepal, where the growing conditions are harsh (Bonafaccia, Gambelli, et al., 2003; Bonafaccia & Fabjan, 2003). It is more tolerant of cold weather, drought, and generally a very low-input plant (Luthar et al., 2021). It is also very rich in flavonoids and other phenolic substances, especially rutin, as it can have up to more than 100 times higher % of rutin per dry weight of grain compared to common buckwheat (Bonafaccia & Fabjan, 2003). Due to its high content of flavonoids and other phenolics, TB is also more resistant to plant diseases, pests, and UV-B radiation, making it feasible to grow as an organic and ecological crop with little need for artificial fertilisers or other chemicals (Luthar et al., 2021).

There have been some papers published on the effect of CP treatment on CB grain, with little or no positive effect, depending on the CP source and treatment conditions (Mravlje et al., 2022; Mravlje et al., 2021; Šerá et al., 2012) on germination of CB in vitro; however, it was reported that although the percentage of emerged seedlings was lower in field conditions, the growth and yield of CP pre-treated CB was strongly improved (Ivankov et al., 2021). It was also demonstrated that CP treatment can increase the phenolic and flavonoid content and antioxidant activity of CB groat and flour (Amiri et al., 2023) and effectively reduce surface fungal colonisation (Mravlje et al., 2022; Mravlje et al., 2021). The effects of CP treatment on TB have been less studied. The potential of plasma-activated water for improving the growth and performance of TB sprouts has been demonstrated (Wang et al., 2022), and effective fungal decontamination of TB grains with a negative impact on germination at longer exposures to low-pressure CP was reported (Mravlje et al., 2022; Mravlje et al., 2021). It was suggested that TB grains may be more sensitive to powerful CP treatments due to their smaller size and lower biomass compared to CB grains (Mravlje et al., 2022).

This study aimed to examine the effects of low-pressure CP treatment generated by different gas admixtures (nitrogen, oxygen and their combinations) on the germination ability of TB grain, which has not been reported before, as finding optimal conditions for CP treatment of specific plant species is crucial for further development of CP technology and its implications in agriculture. We hypothesise that there will be different responses in the TB grain germination ability to either pure nitrogen or pure oxygen plasma treatments and their different admixtures.

Materials and Methods

Tartary buckwheat grain material

The TB grains were obtained from Rangus Mill (Šentjernej, Dolenjska, southeastern Slovenia), from the 2021 harvest and stored under suitable conditions (dry and dark environment at room temperature) until the experiments were performed in spring 2022.

Cold plasma treatment

The TB grains were treated in a custom-made, large-scale, radiofrequency (RF) low-pressure plasma reactor previously described in detail (Holc et al., 2019; Primc & Mozetič, 2019) as shown in Figure 1. In short, it consists of a 2 m long reactor with a 0.2 m diameter (inner diameter 0.18 m and a volume of approximately 50 L) powered by inductively coupled discharge. Plasma is generated inside an excitation coil (wrapped around a glass vacuum discharge) connected to a 27.12 MHz RF generator (Induktio UHFG-8). The vacuum chamber was pumped with a two-stage rotary pump (Leybold Trivac D65B). TB grains, approximately 200 in number, were evenly distributed on a metallic mesh and placed inside the tube in the coil area. Plasma was generated at a pressure of 50 Pa (working pressure around 10 Pa), under a

2.5 kV voltage and around 1.5 kW working power. TB grains were treated for 45 or 90 s with either pure (>99.99% purity) oxygen or nitrogen plasma, or their mixtures in different ratios: 25% oxygen and 75% nitrogen (1/4 oxygen), 50% oxygen and 50% nitrogen (1/2 oxygen), 75% oxygen and 25% nitrogen (3/4 oxygen). The gas (or gas admixture) was leaked into the vacuum chamber on the opposite side of the pumping duct using the mass flow controller (Aera FC7700 Advanced Energy). Immediately after CP treatment, grains were packed into sterile PVC bags, and further experiments were performed the same day. Control TB grains were not treated with CP, while the vacuum control was only exposed to vacuum conditions for the maximum time (90 s).

Germination tests

Germination tests were performed to evaluate the effect of CP treatment on the germination ability of TB grains. In short, 20 grains of each CP treatment (10 different treatments), control and vacuum control grains were evenly distributed on plastic petri dishes (75 mm in diameter) with two layers of filter paper and moistened with 4 mL of bidistilled water. For each group of grains, a germination test was performed in six replicates. In total, 120 grains per treatment (1200 per whole experiment) were analysed. The Petri dishes were incubated in plant growth chambers at

22 °C and 60% relative humidity, in the dark. If necessary, sterile distilled water was added to the Petri dishes to maintain constant moisture during germination. The number of germinated grains was counted every 24 h for the first three days and then on the 6th and 8th days. The germination rate (GR%) was calculated according to Equation (1). The visible penetration of the radicle through the seed coat was used as the criterion for germination.

$$(1) \text{ GR (\%)} = (\text{number of germinated grains}) / (\text{total number of grains}) \times 100$$

To better evaluate the germination process (germination speed), mean germination time (MGT) was calculated according to Equation (2) found by Ellis and Roberts (1981) (Ellis & Roberts, 1981).

$$(2) \text{ MGT} = \sum D \times n / \sum n$$

Where n is the number of seeds germinated on day D , and D is the number of days counted from the beginning of germination.

Seedling length and biomass were measured in 10 randomly selected seedlings per petri dish (in all six replicates), or if fewer than 10 seedlings emerged per petri dish, all seedlings were measured.

Statistical analysis

The reported results are expressed as mean \pm standard error (SE) of six replicates. Statistical significance between groups (treatments) was determined using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Duncan's post hoc test (Statistica StatSoft version 7). The significance level was set at a p -value of less than 0.05. The graphs were prepared with MS Excel®.

Results and Discussion

Our findings revealed distinct and varied effects of different CP mixtures on the germination rate of Tartary buckwheat (Figure 2). All CP treatments exhibited a delay in germination, as seen in MGT (Figure 3). This was previously reported in the CP treatment of buckwheat grain using different low-pressure oxygen CP setups (Mravlje et al., 2022; Mravlje et al., 2021). Up to this point, there has been no evidence of a significant positive effect of CP treatment on buckwheat germination in either low-pressure or atmospheric pressure CP devices (Ivankov et al., 2021; Mravlje

et al., 2022; Mravlje et al., 2021; Šerá et al., 2012; Starič et al., 2023). Most studies report an increasing inhibitory effect on buckwheat germination with increasing treatment time (Mravlje et al., 2021; Šerá et al., 2012; Starič et al., 2023), indicating that buckwheat is very sensitive to CP treatment. In addition to treatment time, the type of plasma reactor (Šerá et al., 2012) and exposure mode (Mravlje et al., 2022) significantly impact the response of buckwheat seeds. The adverse effect is especially profound in the case of powerful low-pressure CP reactors already at shorter treatment times (Mravlje et al., 2022; Starič et al., 2023), as low-pressure CP reactors are known to be a source of intense radiation, especially in the vacuum UV range (D. Popović et al., 2021). This adverse effect could probably be attributed to higher electron density, more UV radiation and heat with longer CP exposure times, which is believed to be responsible for the adverse effect on seed germination (Bol'shakov et al., 2004), as high temperatures (exceeding 45 °C) are considered lethal at physiological level due to protein denaturation and disruption of membrane lipids, leading to the death of seed cells and tissues (Jemaa Essemine et al., 2010).

The only significant positive effect on germination rate and early sprout growth was observed after treating TB grain with plasma-activated water (PAW), with around 10% increase in germination rate (and 16% in sprout biomass) documented in the PAW-treated group (Wang et al., 2022). One thing to mention is that buckwheat grain usually exhibits relatively high germination rates in the control group (generally well over 60 or even 80%), as shown in the above-mentioned papers; therefore, improving the germination rate after CP treatment significantly is challenging. Nevertheless, to this date, all published data on the CP treatment of buckwheat used either air or pure oxygen as the feeding gas. However, evidence from the CP treatment of other seed species suggests a crucial role of different feeding gases (Pet'ková et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2016) or their ratios (Szóke et al., 2018) in determining seed germination rate or germination time (Dufour et al., 2021). Our results confirm this and suggest that nitrogen CP treatment is more suitable for TB grain treatment, as no adverse effects were observed after shorter (45 s) CP treatment with pure nitrogen either in final germination rate (Figure 2) or MGT (Figure 3). Longer (90 s) CP treatment with pure nitrogen also did not significantly affect MGT compared to the control; however, a 10% lower final germination rate than the control group was observed. Vacuum conditions themselves did not influence germination in TB, although

a slight increase in germination (around 15%) compared to the control group was observed on the 2nd day. Pure oxygen CP treatment had a more adverse effect on TB germination, reducing the final germination rate by more than 20% or even 80% after 45 or 90 s of CP treatment,

respectively, compared to the control group. This finding aligns with our previously reported results, which showed an adverse effect of pure oxygen low-pressure CP was observed with increased treatment time in both CB and TB grain (Mravlje et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Germination rate (in %) in each treatment (mean \pm SE, N=6). Different letters (superscripts) represent statistically significant differences between the treatments (one-way ANOVA, Duncan post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Slika 2. Stopnja kalivosti (v %) pri posameznih obdelavah (povprečje \pm SE, N=6). Različne črke (nadpisane) označujejo statistično pomembne razlike med obdelavami (enostranska ANOVA, Duncanov post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Figure 3. Mean germination time (MGT) in days calculated for each treatment (mean \pm SE, N=6). Different letters (superscripts) represent statistically significant differences between the treatments (one-way ANOVA, Duncan post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Slika 3. Povprečni čas kalitve (MGT) v dneh, izračunan za vsako obdelavo (povprečje \pm SE, N=6). Različne črke (nadpiski) predstavljajo statistično pomembne razlike med obdelavami (enostranska ANOVA, Duncanov post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Interestingly, we observed a notable pattern: as the oxygen-to-nitrogen ratio increased, the effect on germination became more negative, especially in the MGT at 90 s CP treatments. This can be attributed to the fact that in low-pressure plasma systems, increasing the oxygen percentage in the mixture results in greater surface erosion of the material (Philip et al., 2002). Oxygen plasma systems (or mixtures containing higher % of oxygen) have already proved to be more efficient in the microbial inactivation process, as it was demonstrated that reactive oxygen species (ROS), including the O_3 , metastable state O_2 , and atom O, play a crucial role in the microbial inactivation (Philip et al., 2002; Szóke et al., 2018). Plasma mixtures containing more oxygen also proved more efficient at inactivating cells, cell leakage and DNA damage in different bacterial species (Lu et al., 2014). A more adverse effect of oxygen plasma compared to nitrogen on the DNA damage of barley seeds was reported, suggesting ROS generated by the CP treatment could have a more negative impact on seeds than reactive nitrogen species (RNS) (Pet'ková et al., 2021). It has already been demonstrated that ROS and RNS species generated by plasma play a crucial role in germination and plant growth (Zhou et al., 2016). They demonstrated that interactions between plasma-generated species, such as H_2O_2 and N species, and seeds led to accelerated germination and improved seedling length in mung beans. Adding nitrogen to the helium plasma decreased germination time and an increase in the vigour of lentil seeds, while adding oxygen to the mixture had no positive effect and even showed an

adverse effect on lentil seeds (Dufour et al., 2021). Using optical emission spectroscopy, they showed that N_2^* , N_2^+ , NO and OH promoted seed vigour, while O species had limited beneficial effects, especially O_3 , which clearly showed an inhibitory effect on seed vigour.

Our results are in line with these findings, as increasing the oxygen content of the mixture led to a more adverse effect on germination and early seedling growth (Table 1). Treatment with pure nitrogen CP, regardless of treatment time, had no inhibitory effect on seedling length and biomass. In contrast, treatment with pure oxygen CP led to decreased seedling length and biomass after 45 s, and the effect was even more adverse after 90 s. Different ratios of oxygen compared to nitrogen decreased seedling length and biomass, comparable to pure oxygen plasma after 45 s. Interestingly, the most negative effect on seedling growth was observed after 90 s of CP treatment in a gas mixture containing 75% oxygen and 25% nitrogen. This suggests that the combination of CP-generated ROS and RNS may have adverse effects, potentially exceeding those of ROS alone. This calls for further research, as it has already been noted that the role of plasma-generated ROS and RNS in seed response is still far from understood (Dufour et al., 2021). And since it is known that the response of seeds to CP treatment is not only species but also cultivar (variety) dependent (Recek et al., 2023; Starič et al., 2021), it is essential to characterise and optimise CP treatments for specific seeds to make this promising technology a feasible and effective solution for the challenges of modern agriculture and food industry.

Table 1. Average sprout length per treatment (mean \pm SE, N=6). Different letters (superscripts) represent statistically significant differences between the treatments (one-way ANOVA, Duncan post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Tabela 1. Povprečna dolžina poganjkov po posameznih obdelavah (povprečje \pm SE, N=6). Različne črke (nadpisane) označujejo statistično pomembne razlike med posameznimi obdelavami (enostranska ANOVA, Duncanov post hoc test, $p < 0,05$).

Treatment	Seedling length [mm]	Seedling biomass [mg]
Control	83,8 \pm 1,6 ^a	78,6 \pm 3,5 ^a
Vacuum control	84,9 \pm 1,4 ^a	82,1 \pm 4,1 ^a
N ₂ 45 s	76,1 \pm 1,2 ^a	76,9 \pm 3,6 ^a
¼ O ₂ 45 s	51,0 \pm 1,7 ^{bc}	44,8 \pm 4,2 ^c
½ O ₂ 45 s	61,6 \pm 1,5 ^b	57,6 \pm 3,1 ^b
¾ O ₂ 45 s	56,7 \pm 2,7 ^{bc}	44,8 \pm 4,2 ^c
O ₂ 45 s	61,3 \pm 2,6 ^b	52,6 \pm 2,5 ^{bc}
N ₂ 90 s	79,8 \pm 1,6 ^a	75,3 \pm 5,2 ^a
¼ O ₂ 90 s	59,6 \pm 2,7 ^b	42,4 \pm 3,4 ^c
½ O ₂ 90 s	61,7 \pm 8,1 ^b	44,2 \pm 5,8 ^c
¾ O ₂ 90 s	23,3 \pm 8,2 ^d	24,6 \pm 3,7 ^d
O ₂ 90 s	46,4 \pm 4,7 ^c	30,2 \pm 2,8 ^d

Conclusions

There is an urgent need for innovative, environmentally friendly, and economically sustainable technologies in the food and agriculture sector to reduce reliance on pesticides and other xenobiotics in plant production. The research field of cold plasma (CP) agriculture appears to offer a promising, environmentally friendly alternative, leaving no harmful residues for either humans or the environment. The results published in this paper reported the effect of different gases (nitrogen, oxygen and their mixtures in various ratios) in a low-pressure CP system on germination and early seedling growth of Tartary buckwheat for the first time. We found that treatment with pure nitrogen did not affect germination or early seedling growth after shorter (45-second) exposure, with a decrease in germination of less than 10% compared to the control after 90-second exposure, and no significant effect on seedling growth or biomass. On the other hand, pure oxygen CP treatment decreased the germination ability of Tartary buckwheat grains by more than 20% compared to the control group, already after 45-second exposure, while longer (90-second) exposure caused an 80% decrease in germination rate compared to the control group. Both exposures also adversely affected early seedling growth, and the effect intensified with increased CP treatment time. This trend was also confirmed across different ratios of oxygen and nitrogen gas mixtures, as it was found that an increased % of oxygen in the gas mixture has a more adverse effect on both germination and early seedling growth, which is particularly visible in the MGT, especially after longer CP exposure time. Therefore, we suggest that nitrogen CP (or a mixture containing a lower % of oxygen) is

more suitable for treating Tartary buckwheat grains. However, further research should also focus on how different gas mixtures affect not only germination ability and early seedling growth, but also decontamination efficacy and the growth of treated grains on a longer timescale (e.g., field experiments).

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, J.M.; methodology, J.M.; formal analysis & investigation, J.M.; resources, J.M.; data curation, J.M.; writing—original draft preparation, review and editing, J.M.; visualisation, J.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Pia Starič and Alenka Novak for their assistance with the experimental part and Prof. Katarina Vogel-Mikuš, Prof. Marjana Regvar and Prof. Miran Mozetič for funding acquisition. We also thank Rangus Mill for providing us with buckwheat grains for our experiments.

Funding

This research was funded by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS): program groups (P1-0212-Plant biology and P2-0082-Thin-film structures and plasma surface engineering), and project J1-3014.

Data Availability

Research data are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18246860>)

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Adhikari, B., Pangomm, K., Veerana, M., Mitra, S., & Park, G. (2020). Plant disease control by non-thermal atmospheric-pressure plasma. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00077>
- Amiri, M., Arab, M., & Mortazavian, A. (2023). Effect of cold plasma treatment on phenolic and flavonoid content and antioxidant activity of whole buckwheat grain and flour. *Scientific Reports*, 15, 25132. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-10281-x>
- Bilea, F., Garcia-Vaquero, M., Magureanu, M., Mihaila, I., Mildažienė, V., Mozetič, M., Pawlat, J., Primc, G., Puač, N., Robert, E., Stancampiano, A., Topala, I., & Žukienė, R. (2024). Non-thermal plasma as environmentally-friendly technology for agriculture: A review and roadmap. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 43, 428–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352689.2024.2410145>
- Bol'shakov, A. A., Cruden, B. A., Mogul, R., Rao, M. V. V. S., Sharma, S. P., Khare, B., & Meyyappan, M. (2004). Radio-frequency oxygen plasma as a sterilisation source. *AIAA Journal*, 42, 823–832.
- Bonafaccia, G., & Fabjan, N. (2003). Nutritional comparison of tartary buckwheat with common buckwheat and minor cereals. *Zbornik Biotehniške Fakultete Univerze v Ljubljani Kmetijstvo*, 81, 349–355.

- Bonafaccia, G., Gambelli, L., Fabjan, N., & Kreft, I. (2003). Trace elements in flour and bran from common and tartary buckwheat. *Food Chemistry*, 83, 1–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146\(03\)00228-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146(03)00228-0)
- Bonafaccia, G., Marocchini, M., & Kreft, I. (2003). Composition and technological properties of the flour and bran from common and tartary buckwheat. *Food Chemistry*, 80, 9–15.
- Conrads, H., & Schmidt, M. (2000). Plasma generation and plasma sources. *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, 9, 441–454. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0963-0252/9/4/301>
- Dufour, T., Gutierrez, Q., & Bailly, C. (2021). Sustainable improvement of seeds vigor using dry atmospheric plasma priming: Evidence through coating wettability, water uptake, and plasma reactive chemistry. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 129. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0037247>
- Ellis, R. A., & Roberts, E. H. (1981). The quantification of aging and survival in orthodox seeds. *Seed Science and Technology*, 9, 373–409.
- FAO United Nations. (2017). The future of food and agriculture: Trends and challenges. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i6583e.pdf>
- Holc, M., Primc, G., Iskra, J., Titan, P., Kovač, J., Mozetič, M., & Junkar, I. (2019). Effect of oxygen plasma on sprout and root growth, surface morphology and yield of garlic. *Plants*, 8, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants8110462>
- Ivankov, A., Naučienė, Z., Degutytė-Fomins, L., Žūkienė, R., Januškaitienė, I., Malakauskienė, A., Jakštas, V., Ivanauskas, L., Romanovskaja, D., Šlepetienė, A., Filatova, I., Lyushkevich, V., & Mildažienė, V. (2021). Changes in agricultural performance of common buckwheat induced by seed treatment with cold plasma and electromagnetic field. *Applied Sciences*, 11, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11104391>
- Jemaa Essemine, S., Ammar, S., & Bouzid, S. (2010). Impact of heat stress on germination and growth in higher plants: Physiological, biochemical and molecular repercussions and mechanisms of defence. *Journal of Biological Sciences*, 10, 565–572.
- Kreft, I., Fabjan, N., & Yasumoto, K. (2006). Rutin content in buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench) food materials and products. *Food Chemistry*, 98, 508–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2005.05.081>
- Lu, H., Patil, S., Keener, K. M., Cullen, P. J., & Bourke, P. (2014). Bacterial inactivation by high-voltage atmospheric cold plasma. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 116, 784–794. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.12426>
- Luthar, Z., Golob, A., Germ, M., Vombergar, B., & Kreft, I. (2021). Tartary buckwheat in human nutrition. *Plants*, 10, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10040700>
- Misra, N., Schluter, O., & Cullen, P. (2016). Cold plasma in food and agriculture (1st ed.). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-801365-6.09991-1>
- Moreau, M., Orange, N., & Feuilloley, M. G. J. (2008). Non-thermal plasma technologies: New tools for bio-decontamination. *Biotechnology Advances*, 26, 610–617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2008.08.001>
- Mravlje, J., Regvar, M., Starič, P., Mozetič, M., & Vogel-Mikuš, K. (2021). Cold plasma affects germination and fungal community structure of buckwheat seeds. *Plants*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10050851>
- Mravlje, J., Regvar, M., Starič, P., Zaplotnik, R., Mozetič, M., & Vogel-Mikuš, K. (2022). Decontamination and germination of buckwheat grains upon treatment with oxygen plasma glow and afterglow. *Plants*, 11, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11101366>
- Mravlje, J., Regvar, M., & Vogel-Mikuš, K. (2021). Development of cold plasma technologies for surface decontamination of seed fungal pathogens: Present status and perspectives. *Journal of Fungi*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7080650>
- Pet'ková, M., Švubová, R., Kyzek, S., Medvecká, V., Slováková, L., Ševčíčová, A., & Gálová, E. (2021). The effects of cold atmospheric pressure plasma on germination parameters and induction of DNA damage in barley. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22062833>
- Philip, N., Saoudi, B., Crevier, M. C., Moisan, M., Barbeau, J., & Pelletier, J. (2002). The respective roles of UV photons and oxygen atoms in plasma sterilisation. *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 30, 1429–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPS.2002.804203>
- Popović, D., Mozetič, M., Vesel, A., Primc, G., & Zaplotnik, R. (2021). Review on vacuum ultraviolet generation in low-pressure plasmas. *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, 18, e2100061. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.202100061>
- Popović, V., Sikora, V., Berenji, J., Filipović, V., Dolijanović, Ž., Ikanović, J., & Dončić, D. (2014). Analysis of buckwheat production in the world and Serbia. *Ekonomika Poljoprivrede*, 61, 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.5937/ekopolj1401053p>
- Primc, G., & Mozetič, M. (2019). Neutral reactive gaseous species in reactors suitable for plasma surface engineering. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 376, 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2018.11.103>
- Puač, N., Gherardi, M., & Shiratani, M. (2018). Plasma agriculture: A rapidly emerging field. *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, 15, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.201700174>
- Randeniya, L. K., & De Groot, G. J. J. B. (2015). Non-thermal plasma treatment of agricultural seeds: A review. *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, 12, 608–623. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.201500042>
- Ranieri, P., Sponsel, N., Kizer, J., Rojas-Pierce, M., Hernández, R., Gatiboni, L., Grunden, A., & Stapelmann, K. (2021). Plasma agriculture: Review from the perspective of the plant and its ecosystem. *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, 18, e2000162. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.202000162>
- Recek, N., Zaplotnik, R., Vesel, A., Primc, G., Gselman, P., Mozetič, M., & Holc, M. (2023). Germination and growth of plasma-treated maize seeds planted in fields. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24, 6868. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24076868>
- Scholtz, V., Jirešová, J., Šerá, B., & Julák, J. (2021). A review of microbial decontamination of cereals by non-thermal plasma. *Foods*, 10, 2927. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10122927>

- Šerá, B., Gajdová, I., Černák, M., Gavril, B., Hnatiuc, E., Kováčik, D., Kříha, V., Sláma, J., Šerý, M., & Špatenka, P. (2012). How various plasma sources may affect seed germination and growth. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Optimisation of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (OPTIM) (pp. 1365–1370). <https://doi.org/10.1109/OPTIM.2012.6231880>
- Sharma, A., Kumar, V., Shahzad, B., Tanveer, M., Sidhu, G. P. S., Handa, N., ... & Thukral, A. K. (2019). Worldwide pesticide usage and its impacts on ecosystem. *SN Applied Sciences*, 1, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1485-1>
- Šimek, M., & Homola, T. (2021). Plasma-assisted agriculture: History, presence, and prospects. *European Physical Journal D*, 75, 210. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjd/s10053-021-00206-4>
- Skerritt, J. H. (1986). Molecular comparison of alcohol-soluble wheat and buckwheat proteins. *Cereal Chemistry*, 63, 365–369.
- Starič, P., Kolmanič, A., Junkar, I., & Vogel-Mikuš, K. (2023). Chemical alterations of grain surface by cold plasma: Comparison of buckwheat and wheat. *Heliyon*, 9, e20215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20215>
- Starič, P., Mlakar, S. G., & Junkar, I. (2021). Response of two different wheat varieties to glow and afterglow oxygen plasma. *Plants*, 10, 1728.
- Starič, P., Vogel-Mikuš, K., Mozetič, M., & Junkar, I. (2020). Effects of nonthermal plasma on morphology, genetics and physiology of seeds: A review. *Plants*, 9, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9121736>
- Szőke, C., Nagy, Z., Gierczik, K., Székely, A., Spitzkó, T., Zsuboril, Z. T., Galiba, G., Marton, C. L., & Kutasi, K. (2018). Effect of afterglows of low-pressure Ar/N₂-O₂ microwave discharges on barley and maize seeds. *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, 15, e1700138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.201700138>
- Tendero, C., Tixier, C., Tristant, P., Desmaison, J., & Leprince, P. (2006). Atmospheric pressure plasmas: A review. *Spectrochimica Acta Part B*, 61, 2–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sab.2005.10.003>
- Wang, Y., Nie, Z., & Ma, T. (2022). Effects of plasma-activated water on growth of tartary buckwheat sprouts. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 9, 849615. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.849615>
- Zahoranová, A., Henselová, M., Hudecová, D., Kaliňáková, B., Kováčik, D., Medvecká, V., & Černák, M. (2016). Effect of cold atmospheric pressure plasma on wheat seedlings vigor and microbial inactivation. *Plasma Chemistry and Plasma Processing*, 36, 397–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11090-015-9684-z>
- Zhou, R., Zhou, R., Zhang, X., Zhuang, J., Yang, S., Bazaka, K., & Ostrikov, K. K. (2016). Effects of atmospheric-pressure microplasmas on mung bean seed germination. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep32603>

ABS

Acta Biologica Slovenica 2026 Vol. 69 | Št. 1